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Istanbul, Turkey - December 17, 2025

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**APPLIED RESEARCH.
GLOBAL SOLUTIONS**

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FEATURES OF THE SYSTEMIC INFLAMMATORY RESPONSE DEPENDING ON THE SURGICAL FACTOR IN COMBINED TRAUMATIC BRAIN INJURY IN CHILDREN

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Abstract. *Based on a study of the examination results of 19 pediatric patients with combined traumatic brain injury, the authors reached the following conclusion. During the first 24 hours, the GL scale assessment of the total brain function cannot provide a differentiated, objective picture of the severity of primary brain injury after severe combined trauma, despite the highest values for the ISS scale. Perioperative anesthesia in the acute phase of severe combined traumatic brain injury significantly improves the effectiveness of anti-inflammatory and stress-protective therapy, reduces the risk of infectious complications, accelerates apoptosis, and impairs reparative functions.*

Keywords: *systemic inflammatory response, combined traumatic brain injury, children.*

Relevance. The increase in trauma increases not only the frequency but also the severity of traumatic brain injury (TBI), which is associated with extracranial injuries in 50–70% of cases. Mortality from combined traumatic brain injury (CTBI) ranges from 12% to 69%. In the overall structure of peacetime trauma, the proportion of combined and multiple injuries ranges from 5% to 12%, and among the most severe, up to 40%. TBI is a nearly constant component of severe combined injuries, occurring in such cases with a frequency of 50–72% to 80–82%.

The extremities are injured in 22.9% of cases, the chest in 31%, and the abdomen in 25–29%. Multiple extracranial injuries in combination with TBI occur in 15% of cases. There is convincing evidence that in patients with brain injury, a hyperthermic reaction increases the likelihood of a fatal outcome. According to Badjatia N. (2009), 70% of patients with brain injury have an elevated body temperature during their stay in the intensive care unit, compared to only 30–45% of patients in general intensive care units. Moreover, only half of these cases had fever (infectious cause). The authors found that among neurosurgical ICU patients, only 50% of fever cases have an infectious cause. Despite numerous studies examining the temperature response in brain injury, due to a lack of information in the literature on age-related changes in the mesocircadian rhythm of body temperature in the acute phase of severe traumatic brain injury (TBI), we attempted to identify distinguishing characteristics and features between the surgical and non-surgical groups based on a retrospective analysis.

Purpose of the study. To study and identify the characteristics of the systemic inflammatory response during conservative therapy, depending on the surgical intervention (extracranial and cranial + extracranial) for severe combined traumatic brain injury.

Material and methods. Data were analyzed from 19 children hospitalized at the Russian Scientific Center for Emergency Medicine in 2024 for severe combined traumatic brain injury (SCTBI) associated with road traffic accidents (13) and falls from a height (6). Patients were divided into 3 groups: Group 1 (5) received conservative therapy as indicated; Group 2 (7) underwent extracranial corrective surgery within the first few hours as indicated; and Group 3 (7) patients underwent simultaneous cranial and extracranial surgery upon admission, as indicated, involving a neurosurgeon, abdominal surgeon, and traumatologist. As their condition improved, hemodynamics and respiration stabilized, and reflexes and consciousness returned, patients were transferred to a specialized department. Results and discussion.

Table 1. Patient characteristics

	Age, years	ISS, points	GL, points	Amount of days in hospital	Amount of days in the ICU
1 group	10,8±3,8	13±1,2	8,2±0,9	28,0±15,2	13,0±10,8
2 group	11,0±4,0	18,9±1,6*	8,3±0,8	12,3±4,9	10,4±6,5
3 group	11,4±3,3	24,3±0,9***	7,1±0,6	8,8±2,6*	2,2±,3*

* — significant difference relative to Group 1

*** — significant difference relative to Group 2.

No significant differences were found in age or GL scores for acute cerebral insufficiency upon admission. However, a significant difference in the severity of traumatic injuries, as measured by the ISS scale, was found. In Group 2, the ISS score was 53% higher than in Group 1, while in Group 3, it was 85% higher than in Group 1 and 31% higher than in Group 2 ($p < 0.05$, respectively) (Table 1). Thus, while the GL score is an integral indicator of extreme factors causing acute cerebral insufficiency, it cannot provide a differentiated, objective representation of the severity of primary brain injury in the first 24 hours after severe combined trauma. This is confirmed by a significantly shorter duration of treatment in the intensive care unit (ICU) by 80% (8 days) and inpatient stay by 33% (4 days) in Group 3 compared to Group 2. According to the indications, all patients in Group 3 underwent craniotomy with removal of epidural (5) and subdural (2) hematomas, along with additional extracranial surgeries as indicated (diagnostic laparoscopy, primary surgical debridement of wounds, hematoma removal, and limb bone repositioning) (Table 2).

Table 2. Patient Characteristics

Type of injury	1 group (5 patients)	2 group (7)	3 group (7)
Road accident	80% (4)	71% (5)	58% (4)
Catastrophic injury	20% (1)	29% (2)	42% (3)
Severe traumatic brain injury	40% (2)	29% (2)	58% (4)
Severe traumatic brain injury	80% (4)	58% (4)	42% (3)
Severe brain injury	100% (5)	14% (1)	42% (3)
Moderate brain injury	40% (2)	14% (1)	29% (2)
SAH	40% (2)	42% (3)	0
Pneumocephalus	40% (2)	0	29% (2)
Parietal bone fracture	20% (1)	14% (1)	0
Left hemisphere hematoma Thalamus	0	14% (1)	0
Blood contusion of the brainstem	20% (1)	14% (1)	0
Blood contusion of the right parietal lobe	20% (1)	0	14% (1)
Temporal bone fracture extending to the skull base	20% (1)	0	14% (1)
Occipital bone fracture extending to the skull base	0	0	14% (1)
Epidural hematoma	0	0	71% (5)
Subdural hematoma	0	0	14% (1)
Closed spinous process fracture T3 (T9, T10–3rd degree)	20% (1)	0	1
Closed fracture of the ischium	20% (1)	0	0

Type of injury	1 group (5 patients)	2 group (7)	3 group (7)
Closed fracture of the femoral neck	20% (1)	0	14% (1)
Closed fracture of the clavicle	20% (1)	14% (1)	0
Bilateral hemipneumothorax	0	14% (1)	0
Displaced fracture of the humerus	0	28% (2)	14% (1)
Pulmonary contusion	60% (3)	28% (2)	28% (2)
Liver contusion	20% (1)	0	0
Acute pneumonia	40% (2)	0	28% (2)
Stage 1 coma	80% (4)	14% (1)	56% (4)
Stage 1 traumatic shock	40% (2)	42% (3)	42% (3)
Stage 2 traumatic shock	20% (1)	28% (2)	56% (4)
Stage 3 traumatic shock	0	14% (1)	28% (2)

In all groups, road traffic accidents were predominant, accounting for 80% in group 1, 71% in group 2, and 58% in group 3. In group 1, the severity of the condition was mainly due to closed traumatic brain injury (CTBI) (80%), severe brain contusion (100%), pulmonary contusion (60%), acute pneumonia (40%), coma (1) (80%), and traumatic shock (60%) (Table 2). In group 2, the severity of the condition was more influenced by cranial (CTBI 58%, SAH 42%) and extracranial injuries (fractures requiring surgical correction, immobilization 56%, pulmonary contusion 28%, traumatic shock 84%). Group 3 was characterized by surgical removal of 85% of identified intracranial hemorrhages and removal of bone fragments from damaged skull bones in both closed and acute TBI.

Table 3 presents the surgical interventions performed, which significantly impacted the optimization of comprehensive intensive care for children with TSBI. All patients in Group 3 underwent primary surgical debridement (PSD).

Table 3. Surgeries performed

Patients	2 group	3 group
1	Closed intramedullary osteosynthesis of the left femur with elastic nails.	Craniotomy, epidural hematoma removal
2	Osteosynthesis of the left femur	Craniotomy, epidural hematoma removal, diagnostic laparoscopy
3	Closed reduction of femoral bone fragments	Craniotomy, epidural hematoma removal
4	Reduction of humeral bone fragments	Craniotomy, epidural hematoma removal, diagnostic laparoscopy
5	Diagnostic laparoscopy	Craniotomy, epidural hematoma removal

Patients	2 group	3 group
6	Thoracoscopy, laparoscopy, pleural drainage	Craniotomy, subdural hematoma removal
7	Diagnostic laparoscopy, femoral osteosynthesis	Craniotomy, subdural hematoma removal.

A comparative assessment of average body temperature values was conducted during the first 7 days and throughout the entire period of intensive care in the ICU. For this purpose, groups 1a (the first 7 days) and 2a (the first 7 days) were analyzed. Table 4 shows the average values of the phase structure of the circadian rhythm of body temperature by group.

Table 4 Comparative assessment of the circadian rhythm of the systemic inflammatory response

Group	Mesor	Acrophase	Batiphase	Amplitude	Daily fluctuations
1 (7 days)	37,2±0,2	37,6±0,2	36,9±0,3	0,4±0,1	0,6±0,2
2 (7 days)	37,0±0,1	37,3±0,2	36,8±0,1	0,3±0,1	0,5±0,3
3 (7 days)	37,2±0,3	37,9±0,4	36,7±0,3	0,7±0,2	1,0±0,4
1 (29 days)	37,1±0,2	37,5±0,3	36,8±0,2	0,4±0,2	0,6±0,2
2 (19 days)	37,0±0,1	37,4±0,2	36,8±0,1	0,3±0,1	0,6±0,2

No significant differences in the average parameters of the phase structure of the circadian rhythm of body temperature (CRBT) in the group of children who underwent complex conservative therapy depending on the type of surgical intervention were found (Table 4).

Mesozoic Circadian Rhythm of Temperature Average circadian rhythm of body temperature

Table 5.

Hours	1 (7 days)	2 (7 days)	3 (7 days)	1 (29 days)	2 (19 days)
8	37,3±0,2	37,1±0,1	37,4±0,4	37,1±0,2	37,1±0,1
9	37,3±0,2	37,1±0,1	37,4±0,3	37,1±0,3	37,1±0,1
10	37,3±0,2	37,1±0,2	37,4±0,3	37,1±0,2	37,1±0,2
11	37,2±0,2	37,2±0,2	37,2±0,3	37,1±0,2	37,2±0,2
12	37,2±0,2	37,1±0,2	37,0±0,2	37,1±0,2	37,1±0,2
13	37,1±0,4	37,1±0,3	37,1±0,3	37,1±0,3	37,1±0,2
14	37,1±0,4	37,0±0,2	37,1±0,4	37,1±0,3	37,1±0,2
15	37,2±0,3	37,0±0,1	37,2±0,3	37,1±0,3	37,1±0,2

Hours	1 (7 days)	2 (7 days)	3 (7 days)	1 (29 days)	2 (19 days)8
16	37,2±0,3	37,0±0,2	37,3±0,2	37,1±0,3	37,1±0,2
17	37,2±0,2	37,0±0,1	37,3±0,3	37,1±0,2	37,1±0,2
18	37,1±0,2	37,0±0,1	37,5±0,4	37,1±0,2	37,0±0,2
19	37,1±0,2	36,9±0,1	37,4±0,3	37,1±0,2	37,0±0,2
20	37,2±0,1	37,0±0,2	37,3±0,2	37,1±0,2	37,0±0,2
21	37,4±0,2	37,0±0,2	37,2±0,3	37,2±0,2	37,0±0,2
22	37,2±0,2	37,1±0,1	37,4±0,6	37,1±0,3	37,0±0,2
23	37,3±0,2	37,0±0,1	37,2±0,4	37,1±0,3	37,1±0,2
24	37,0±0,6	37,0±0,1	37,2±0,3	37,0±0,3	37,0±0,2
1	36,9±0,5	36,9±0,1	37,1±0,2	37,0±0,2	37,0±0,1
2	37,2±0,1	37,0±0,1	37,1±0,2	37,1±0,2	37,0±0,2
3	37,3±0,2	37,0±0,1	37,2±0,2	37,1±0,2	37,0±0,1
4	37,2±0,2	37,0±0,1	37,2±0,2	37,0±0,2	37,0±0,1
5	37,2±0,2	37,0±0,1	37,2±0,3	37,0±0,2	37,0±0,1
6	37,3±0,2	37,0±0,1	37,3±0,3	37,0±0,2	37,0±0,2
7	37,4±0,1	37,0±0,1	37,3±0,3	37,1±0,2	37,0±0,2

Table 6.

Days	1 group	2 group	3 group
1	36,6±0,5	36,8±0,1	37,0±0,2
2	37,3±0,1	37,1±0,1*	37,4±0,2
3	37,1±0,1	37,1±0,1*	37,4±0,2
4	37,3±0,1	37,1±0,1*	37,6±0,4*
5	37,5±0,1	37,0±0,1	36,9±0,2
6	37,2±0,1	36,8±0,1	37,2±0,2'''
7	37,3±0,2	37,2±0,2*	36,7±0,1'''
8	37,4±0,1*	37,1±0,1*	
9	37,3±0,2	37,1±0,1*	
10	37,2±0,1	37,1±0,1*	
11	37,5±0,1*	37,5±0,2*	
12	37,2±0,3	37,2±0,1*	
13	37,4±0,2*	37,0±0,1	
14	37,4±0,3	37,0±0,1	
15	37,0±0,2	36,9±0,1	
16	37,0±0,1	36,9±0,1	
17	36,8±0,02	36,8±0,1	
18	36,9±0,1	36,9±0,1	
19	37,1±0,1	37,1±0,2	
20	37,0±0,1		

Days	1 group	2 group	3 group
21	36,8±0,1		
22	37,0±0,1		
23	37,1±0,1		
24	37,1±0,3		
25	36,9±0,2		
26	36,7±0,1		
27	36,8±0,1		
28	36,7±0,1		
29	36,7±0,01		

* — significant relative to the value on day 1
 ''' — significant difference relative to the value in Group 2

Fig. 1. Dynamics of the CRTT mesomorph

Fig. 2. Average circadian rhythm.

The effectiveness of conservative intensive care for severe traumatic brain injury in Group 1 was demonstrated by a tendency for temperature to increase to subfebrile levels during the first 7 days (Table 5). On days 8, 11, and 13, significant increases in body temperature were observed by 0.6 °C, 0.7 °C, and 0.8 °C ($p < 0.05$) relative to the baseline daily average (36.6 ± 0.5 °C), which allowed for the stabilization of the mesocircadian rhythm of body temperature at normal values. While Group 2 significantly differed from Group 1 in terms of injury severity according to the ISS by 45% ($p < 0.05$), the temperature dynamics did not differ significantly from those in Group 1. Thus, a significant increase in temperature by 0.3–0.7 °C was noted on days 2, 3, 4, and 7–12, which characterized the adequacy of intensive anti-inflammatory therapy in the acute period in Group 2. Perioperative anesthesia for extracranial surgeries with traumatic brain injury contributed

to the effect. Only in Group 3, on day 4, a significantly significant increase in the mesoscale circadian rhythm of body temperature of 0.6 °C was detected. Moreover, on day 7, a significant decrease in the indicator was observed by 0.5 °C below the indicator in Group 2 and by 0.6 °C below the indicator in Group 1. The identified difference was due to a comparatively more active stress-protective, anti-inflammatory correction in the early postoperative period after surgery due to combined traumatic brain injury.

Intergroup differences were manifested not only in the duration of intensive correction of the identified deviations, which was the longest in Group 1 (29 days), 19 days in Group 2, and 7 days in Group 3 (Fig. 1). Differences were also expressed in the most pronounced systemic inflammatory response (SIR) in Group 3 on day 4, the peak of the inflammatory response in Group 2 on day 11, and in Group 1 on day 5. Throughout the observation period, fluctuations in the mesomorph of the circadian rhythm of body temperature occurred within a somewhat distorted circadian rhythm. The peak of the acrophase of the circadian rhythm of temperature was closest to the norm in Group 3 (18 hours), in Group 1 (21 hours), and in Group 2, the most significant shift in the peak of the acrophase to 11 hours was noted (Fig. 2).

Fig. 3. Circadian temperature rhythm amplitude dynamics.

Fig. 4. Diurnal temperature fluctuations.

It has been established that the greater the amplitude of the circadian temperature rhythm, the more unstable the immune system's response to traumatic stress. This increases the risk of infectious complications, impairs reparative processes, accelerates apoptosis, and overall negatively impacts the optimization of treatment in critically ill patients. The highest circadian temperature rhythm amplitudes were observed in Group 3 on Day 4, in Group 1 on Day 23, and in Group 2 on Day 10

(Fig. 3). The dynamics of diurnal temperature fluctuations confirm the instability of the thermoregulatory center during these days of intensive care (Fig. 4).

Fig. 5. Duration of CRTT inversion

The longest inversion of the circadian rhythm of body temperature was observed in Groups 1 and 2, and in percentage terms in Groups 2 and 3 (70%, 72%).

Conclusion. During the first day, the assessment of the circadian rhythm of body temperature using the GL scale cannot provide a differentiated, objective representation of the severity of primary brain injury during the first day after severe combined trauma, despite the highest values for the severity of combined trauma using the ISS scale. Perioperative anesthesia support in the acute period of severe combined traumatic brain injury significantly increases the effectiveness of anti-inflammatory and stress-protective therapy, reduces the risk of infectious complications, and accelerates apoptosis and reparative functions.

References

1. <https://medi.ru/info/2217/>
2. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/infuzionnaya-terapiya-v-pervye-sutki-tyazheloy-cherepno-mozgovoy-travmy-u-detey>
3. <https://studfile.net/preview/1819228/page:4/>
4. <https://euroasia-science.ru/pdf-arxiv/ocenka-gemodinamiki-v-ostrejshej-faze-tyazheloy-cherepno-mozgovoy-travmy-u-detey-39-42/>
5. <https://www.eurolab-portal.ru/encyclopedia/traumatology/48810/>

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THE INFLUENCE OF HIGH SOLAR ACTIVITY ON INDIVIDUAL MINUTE RATES IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION STUDENTS

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Abstract. *The purpose of this study was to examine the time perception characteristics (individual minute — IM) of young male students at the Institute of Physical Education, Tyumen State University, during periods of high solar activity (magnetic storms — MS) in the fall of 2025. Study Material. The article presents the results of a study of IM values in 36 young men over three autumn months, based on sleep duration, athletic skill level, and sport type. Results. It was found that 37.8% of young men experienced signs of discomfort during MS, while IM was significantly ($p < 0.05$) shortened and depended on sleep duration and only slightly on athletic skill level and sport type.*

Keywords: *young male students, Tyumen, individual minute, magnetic storms.*

Relevance. During the fall of 2025, magnetic storms of varying intensity and duration were virtually continuous. Little has been studied regarding the characteristics of physiological processes in humans due to forced prolonged exposure to high levels of electromagnetic radiation. An unresolved issue in this situation is the identification of individual characteristics of physiological adaptation, for example, by studying the MI. The duration of the astronomical MI is one of the criteria for the endogenous organization of biological rhythms of human life. In healthy individuals, MI is a relatively stable indicator characterizing the endogenous organization of time and the adaptive capacity of the body [Leontyev D. A., Osin E. N.].

The functioning of the so-called “internal clock” reflects the activity and efficiency of physiological processes occurring in the human body and depends, among other things, on the characteristics of the type of higher nervous activity and the general condition of the body [Fonsova N. A., Shestova I. A.; Merdenova L. A. et al.].

Despite numerous studies examining the individual assessment of time indicators [Vernadsky V. I.; Koryagina Yu. V., Tristan V. G.; Melnikova S. L., Melnikov V. V.], they do not touch upon some aspects of the “internal chronometer” when the usual rhythm of life is disrupted. The perception of time, or the ability to adequately navigate in time, is one of the most complex forms of subjective reflection of the external world by a person [Gubin D. G.; Nazmutdinova V. I., Prokopyev N. Ya.; Prokopyev N. Ya., Nazmutdinova V. I.; Rakshina N. S. Khodasevich M. I. et al.]. The study of issues related to the health of modern students is the most important state task associated with the preservation of the labor and intellectual potential of our country [Davletshina L. A., Pershina T. A.; Smirennikova E. V. et al.; [D. D. Per-everzev, V. V. Ilyin], which is consistent with RF Government Resolution No. 434 “On the Targeted Project for the Development of Labor Potential for Knowledge-Intensive Production.”

In the theory and practice of physical education, issues of subjective assessment of time perception are given due attention [Ali Muhammad Ali et al.; Bulgakova Ya. V.; Smirnova E. I., Sukhostav O. A.; Sobyanyan F. I. et al.: Tikhomirov A. I.]. We hypothesized a reliable correlation between the duration of nighttime sleep in young men attending a physical education university and a high level of MB.

Aim of the study: to examine the characteristics of time perception (TP) in adolescent students of the Institute of Physical Education of Tyumen State University during high solar activity in the fall of 2025.

Materials and Methods. A random sample of 36 adolescent students studying at the Institute of Physical Education of Tyumen State University was voluntarily examined. The young men underwent a medical examination, which included a study of their MI, during three autumn months of 2025 during intense solar activity. MI duration was determined using the “Individual Minute Test” proposed in 1969 by Canadian (Fig. 1) chronobiologist and professor at the University of Minnesota

(USA) Franz Halberg (July 5, 1919 — June 9, 2013). To do this, the subject starts a stopwatch, closes his eyes and begins to silently count the seconds (from 1 to 60) and, having reached the number 60, records it in a self-monitoring diary..

Fig. 1. Franz Halberg.

During the study, we asked the young men to go to bed at 11:00 PM and wake up at 7:00 AM, i. e., to maintain a sleep duration of eight hours, and to abstain from medications and alcoholic beverages.

All measurements were taken from 10:00 AM to 12:00 PM during class time.

The study results were processed on a personal computer using modern electronic software (STATISTIKA). The analysis was based on mathematical calculations, including the arithmetic mean, the standard error of the arithmetic mean, and the standard deviation. The significance of differences was assessed using the Student's t-test.

The principles of voluntariness, individual rights, and freedoms guaranteed by Articles 21 and 22 of the Constitution of the Russian Federation, as well as Order No. 774n of the Russian Ministry of Health and Social Development of August 31, 2010, "On the Ethics Council," were observed. The study was conducted in compliance with the ethical standards set forth in the Declaration of Helsinki and the European Community Directives (8/609EC) and with the students' informed consent.

Results and Discussion.

The intensity and duration of the meteorological event in Tyumen, particularly in September 2025, is illustrated in Figure 1 from the Russian Hydrometeorological Center.

Chart 1. Intensity and duration of magnetic storms in Tyumen.

It was found that during periods of intense magnetic storms, 37.8% of the young men we surveyed experienced signs of discomfort. These included lethargy, drowsiness, irritability, headaches, dizziness, tinnitus, photophobia, tachycardia, increased blood pressure, and reluctance to do morning hygiene exercises and exercise.

We analyzed MI values for the following sports:

- speed-strength sports (jumping, sprinting, throwing, martial arts, weightlifting);
- complex coordination sports (acrobatics, gymnastics);
- cyclic sports (swimming, cross-country skiing, biathlon);
- sports games (football, volleyball, basketball, tennis).

The study results (Table 1) indicated that MI during the MB period was significantly ($p < 0.05$) shortened only by the duration of nighttime sleep.

Table 1

Individual minute duration in male students at the Institute of Physical Education during high solar activity in the fall of 2025 (M±m)

Solar Activity	Night sleep			
	8 hours	7 hours	6 hours	5 hours
Normal	59,84±1,27	58,12±1,26	56,65±1,32	55,87±1,29
High	55,18±1,32	53,33±1,37	51,67±1,40	50,26±1,38
Difference	4,66	4,79	4,98	5,61

Solar Activity	Sports qualification			
	MCMK	MC	KMC	I разряд
Normal	59,93±1,23	58,67±1,29	57,97±1,27	56,71±1,24
High	58,61±1,28	56,86±1,34	56,14±1,32	53,19±1,30
Difference	1,32	1,81	1,83	3,52
Solar Activity	Sports			
	Speed-strength	Complex coordination	Cyclic,	Sports games
Normal	58,58±1,21	58,72±1,25	58,80±1,29	58,66±1,24
High	57,49±1,24	57,04±1,28	56,93±1,30	56,78±1,27
Difference	1,09	1,68	1,87	1,88

The shorter the night's sleep, the shorter the MI. We also noted, firstly, that during the MB, the athletic qualifications of young men had a slight, but significant, effect on the absolute duration of the MI. For example, among Masters of Sports of International Class (MSIC), the difference was 1.32 minutes, while for young men with a first-class sports qualification, it was 3.52 minutes. Secondly, statistical analysis of the MI test results showed that the type of sport had no significant effect ($p>0.05$). Research has shown that as the duration of night's sleep decreases in young men, the absolute duration of the MI during the MB, albeit slightly, decreases compared to normal days. This should be taken into account both when conducting classroom training with students and during sports or health training.

Based on the analysis of the above material, several conclusions can be drawn.

First, male students at the Tyumen State University Institute of Physical Education (IPE) during the fall 2025 IB experience a shorter MI duration, which we interpret as a negative impact of solar electromagnetic waves on the autonomic nervous system, and through it, on central hemodynamics. This confirms our hypothesis that the duration of nighttime sleep in young men studying at the physical education university is significantly correlated with high solar activity.

Second, given that a nighttime sleep duration of less than 8 hours negatively impacts both the overall health of young men and the duration of MI, we recommend a minimum of 8 hours of sleep to maintain health.

Third, male students with the sports qualifications of Master of Sports of International Class and Master of Sports of Russia demonstrate a more highly organized "internal clock" and possess greater adaptive capacity to counteract the negative effects of environmental factors, including high solar activity. Fourth, the type of sport does not affect the duration of MI.

Conflict of Interest. The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Study Transparency. The study was not sponsored. The authors are solely responsible for submitting the final version of the manuscript for publication.

Declaration of Financial and Other Relationships. All authors participated in the development of the study topic, design, and writing of the manuscript. The final version of the manuscript was agreed upon and approved by all authors. The authors did not receive any fees for the study.

References

1. Ali Mohammad Ali. *The Individual Minute Test in Assessing the Functional Status of Young Men of the Syrian National Road Racing Team at the Pre-Competition Stage of the Training Process.* / Ali Mohammad Ali, N. Ya. Prokopyev, E. A. Semizorov // *Sciences of Europe.* — No. 87, 2022. — P. 10–15.
2. Vernadsky V. I. *The Problem of Time in Modern Science.* *Bulletin of the USSR Academy of Sciences. Dept. of Mathematics and Natural Sciences.* / V. I. Vernadsky. — Moscow, 1932. — No. 4. — P. 511–541.
3. Gubin D. G. *Circaweek (Circaseptan) Rhythms in Physiology (review)* / D. G. Gubin. // *Advances in Modern Natural Science*, 2015. — No. 1–8. — P. 1268–1272.
4. Davletshina L. A. *Statistical analysis of the generalizing integral indicator of the socio-economic situation of the constituent entities of the Russian Federation* / L. A. Davletshina, T. A. Pershina. // *University Bulletin.* 2018. — No. 5. — P. 11–19.
5. *Study of the duration of an individual minute among VSMU students* / M. I. Khodasevich, M. S. Roshchevkina, A. N. Pashkov, L. G. Velichko, O. V. Myachina // *Youth Innovation Bulletin*, 2019. — Vol. 8. — No. 2. — P. 314–315.
6. Koryagina Yu. V., Nopin S. V. *Experience of using the computer program “Researcher of temporal and spatial properties” for testing athletes of various sports* // *Omsk Scientific Bulletin.* — 2004. — No. 4 (29). — P. 127–130.
7. Koryagina Yu. V. *Chronobiological mechanisms of the accuracy of time and space perception and their role in the training of athletes of various specializations* / Yu. V. Koryagina, V. G. Tristan. // *Physical education and sport — health of the population of Russia: proc. All-Russian scientific-pr. conf.* — December 17–20, 2001. — P. 170–174.
8. Melnikova S. L. *The indicator of individual perception of time as a characteristic of the general condition of the body* / S. L. Melnikova, V. V. Melnikov // *Bulletin of new medical technologies.* — 2002. — Vol. 9. — 2. — P. 20–23.
9. Nazmutdinova V. I. *Dynamics of time perception by adolescent students with different motor activity as an adaptation criterion* / V. I. Nazmutdinova, N. Ya. Prokopyev. // *Problems of Education in Northern Cities: Proceedings of the Scientific and Practical Conference of the Nyagan Branch of Tyumen State University.* Editor-in-Chief O. S. Prokofieva. — Nyagan, April 20, 2006. — pp. 112–118.

10. Pereverzev, D. D. *Analysis of Physical Health Indicators of Students Involved in Sports, Compared to Students Not Involved in Physical Education* / D. D. Pereverzev, V. V. Ilyin // *Problems of Physical Education Education: Content, Focus, Methodology, Organization: Proceedings of the IX International Scientific Congress.* — Cheboksary, 2024. — pp. 315–317.

11. *Prospects for Using the Properties of Subjective Time Scales to Assess Exercise Tolerance* / Ya. V. Bulgakova [et al.]. // *Theory and Practice of Physical Education* — 2022. — No. 1. — P. 36–38. DOI: 10.24412/0040-3601-2022-1-36-38.

12. Prokopyev N. Ya. *Individual minute indicators of correspondence students of the Faculty of Physical Education at the beginning of the academic year* / N. Ya. Prokopyev, V. I. Nazmutdinova. // *Current issues in physical education and sports training: Materials of the regional scientific and practical conference.* — Tyumen, 2004. — P. 56–57.

13. Rakshina, N. S. “*Perception of Time by First-Year Students Majoring in General Medicine with Different Levels of Personal Anxiety.*” In: *Healthy Lifestyle and Health Protection: Collection of Scientific Articles from the II All-Russian Scientific and Practical Conference with International Participation.* Edited by M. A. Popova. — Surgut, March 30, 2018. — pp. 140–143.

14. Smirennikova, E. V. “*A Review of Modern Methodological Approaches to Assessing Demographic Potential.*” In: *Fundamental Research.* 2018. — No. 11–2. — pp. 307–313.

15. Smirnova E. I. *Assessment of Subjective Perception of Time as a Diagnostic Tool for Determining the Content and Effectiveness of Physical Exercises* / E. I. Smirnova, O. A. Sukhostav // *Bulletin of Omsk State Pedagogical University. Humanitarian Research.* 2025. — No. 3 (48). — P. 205–209. DOI: 10.36809/2309-9380-2025-48-205-20

16. Sobyenin F. I. *The Experience of Time in Sports (Psychological and Pedagogical Aspect)* / F. I. Sobyenin, Yu. B. Nikiforov, S. V. Mikhel // *Bulletin of Tambov University.* Tambov, 2019. — Vol. 24. — No. 1 (79). — P. 90–97.

17. Tikhomirov, A. I. “*Athletes’ Operational Sense of Time Depending on the Biomechanics of the Sport*” / A. I. Tikhomirov // *Scientific Notes of P. F. Lesgaft University.* — 2007 — No. 11 (33). — P. 82–86.

18. Fonsova, N. A. “*The Function of Time Counting as the Basis of Individual Adaptive Activity of the Nervous System*” / N. A. Fonsova, I. A. Shestova // *Scientific Reports of Higher Education. Biological Sciences.* — 1988. — N3. — P. 59–72.

19. *Characteristics of the General Condition of the Body Based on Indicators of Individual Time Perception* / L. A. Merdenova, E. A. Takoeva, I. R. Tagaeva, M. I. Nartikoeva // *Bulletin of New Medical Technologies.* 2018. — Vol. 25. — No. 4. — P. 96–100.

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EFFECTIVENESS OF USING A REPOSITIONING ORTHOSIS IN THE ORTHOPEDIC REHABILITATION OF A PATIENT WITH TEMPOROMANDIBULAR JOINT

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Abstract: *This article presents a clinical case of orthopedic rehabilitation of a female patient with temporomandibular joint dysfunction caused by impaired occlusal relationships of the dental arches. As part of a comprehensive treatment approach, an orthopedic stage involving the use of a repositioning orthosis was implemented to restore the physiological position of the mandible and stabilize the neuromuscular and joint function. The application of the orthosis created favorable conditions for the subsequent orthodontic treatment stage and the achievement of long-term functional balance of the stomatognathic system.*

Key words: *temporomandibular joint, orthosis, occlusion disorders, repository.*

Introduction

Modern research in orthopedic dentistry demonstrates the high prevalence of functional disorders of the temporomandibular joint, making them of significant clinical and social relevance. TMJ dysfunction often develops against

a background of occlusal imbalance and can be accompanied by pain, limited mobility of the mandible, abnormal noises, and, ultimately, a deterioration in patients' quality of life. Therefore, the development and implementation of effective methods for correcting these disorders remains a priority in practical dentistry [5].

One of the key areas of conservative and orthopedic treatment for TMJ dysfunction is the restoration of occlusal relationships approaching physiological ones, using specialized intraoral devices, including occlusal splints, mouth guards, and orthoses. The use of these devices allows for the redistribution of chewing loads, reduction of muscle tension, and the creation of conditions for stabilization of the joint-muscle complex [10, 11].

In clinical practice, special attention is paid to repositioning orthoses, the use of which is aimed at creating a therapeutically justified position of the mandible. However, the selection of the optimal orthopedic device and the determination of the sequence of treatment stages require an individual approach and a thorough clinical and functional analysis, which emphasizes the need for further study of the effectiveness of repositioning devices in the treatment of temporomandibular joint dysfunction [6].

The aim of the study was to evaluate the effectiveness of using a repositioning orthosis in the comprehensive treatment of TMJ dysfunction by normalizing occlusion.

Materials and Methods.

This study examined a female patient with a verified clinical diagnosis of temporomandibular joint dysfunction (K07.60) and anterior dental crowding (K07.30). To objectively assess the structural and functional changes in the joint apparatus, a CT scan of the TMJ was performed before and after orthopedic treatment. The diagnostic algorithm included a comprehensive set of clinical procedures: collecting complaints and anamnestic data, a physical examination, determining the centric relation of the jaws using a sheet gauge and a Lucia jig, recording the spatial position of the maxilla using a facebow, and analyzing occlusal contacts in an articulator. Based on the data obtained, a custom-made repositioning orthosis was manufactured, which the patient used for six months to stabilize the position of the mandible and normalize temporomandibular joint function.

Study Results

Patient M., 40, presented to the orthopedic dentistry clinic complaining of intermittent clicking in the area of her right temporomandibular joint, the intensity of which decreased during eating and sleep. The patient also reported pain in the right parotid-masticatory region, which intensified with wide mouth opening (Figs. 1, 2).

Figure 1. View of the dental arches of the upper and lower jaws before treatment

Figure 1. Appearance of closed dentition on the right and left sides before treatment

Amnestic data indicated that the patient had been experiencing discomfort and pain in the parotid-masticatory region for approximately three years. An objective clinical examination revealed that, with maximum mouth opening, the mandible deviates to the left, indicating impaired coordination of movements in the temporomandibular joint. Static palpation of the TMJ revealed mild tenderness. A functional test involving clenching the teeth resulted in pain over the left temporomandibular joint. Additionally, a decrease in the interocclusal height of 3–4 mm was recorded, which may indicate an occlusal imbalance. A single plastic crown was found in the 4.7 region, which did not meet functional and aesthetic requirements, as well as failed filling restorations in the 4.6 and 3.6 region. Congenital adentia was noted on 4.5 and 3.5. The mucous membrane of the tongue was pale pink in color, moderately moist, and showed no signs of inflammatory or degenerative changes. To clarify the morphological state of the articular structures, a multispiral computed tomography study of the temporomandibular joints with the dental arches closed was performed, followed by a three-dimensional reconstruction of the cranial bones (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. CT scan of the TMJ in the closed-mouth position before occlusion therapy.

CT scan results before treatment: Sagittal sections show narrowing of the joint spaces on both sides in the anterior region, with asymmetry in the position of the condyles. Left TMJ: Anterior 2.20, Upper 3.01, Posterior 4.40. Right TMJ: Anterior 1.40, Upper 2.81, Posterior 3.81.

Clinical diagnosis: K07.6 — temporomandibular joint pain dysfunction syndrome, K08.1 — partial absence of teeth in the mandible, Kennedy class III, K07.30 — crowding of the anterior teeth, forced pathological occlusion, Z97.2 — use of irrational denture designs.

Treatment stages: The first step was establishing centric relation using a sheet gauge and Lucia jig, followed by facebow fixation and plaster modeling in an articulator (SAM, Germany). The optimal therapeutic position of the mandible was determined, and a repositioning orthosis for the mandible was fabricated from a transparent plastic material (Figs. 5, 6).

Figure 5. Models in the articulator in the central relation position.

Figure 6. A patient wearing a repositioning orthosis.

After several days of using the removable repositioning device, the patient noted a significant improvement in her general condition: joint clicking disappeared, and pain in the right parotid region decreased. Treatment with the orthosis continued for six months, during which multiple adjustments were made. By the end of the treatment, the patient reported a complete absence of pain and clicking in the TMJ region. Static and dynamic palpation of the temporomandibular joints and masticatory muscles were painless. The next step is planned to be orthodontic correction followed by rational prosthetic replacement of teeth 36, 46, and 47. A control CT scan of the TMJ revealed a symmetrical arrangement of the condyles on both sides, confirming the effectiveness of the treatment (Fig. 7).

Figure 7. CT scan of the TMJ in the closed-mouth position after occlusion therapy.

CT scan of the TMJ at the end of treatment: Right TMJ: Anterior 2.80 mm, Upper 2.80 mm, Posterior 3.61 mm. Left TMJ: Anterior 2.61 mm, Upper 2.80 mm, Posterior 3.40 mm.

Conclusions

Orthopedic correction of the patient's occlusal relationship resulted in complete elimination of pain in the right temporomandibular joint and restoration of symmetrical positioning of the condyles on both sides, as confirmed by CT scan data. The first stage of treatment can be considered successfully completed. Further therapy involves continued orthodontic work, and final restoration of chewing function, aesthetics, and occlusion stabilization will be achieved through appropriate prosthetics.

References

1. Emam, M. E., et al. (2025). *The efficacy of anterior repositioning splints in the management of temporomandibular disc displacement: A systematic review and metaanalysis*. *BMC OralHealth*, 25, 639.
2. Okeson, J. P. (2003). *Management of Temporomandibular Disorders and Occlusion (5th ed.)*. St. Louis: Mosby.
3. De Laat, A., &Lundh, H. (2018). *Can anterior repositioning splint effectively treat temporomandibular joint disc displacement?* *ScientificReports*, 8, 36988.
4. Gupta, A., et al. (2016). *Efficacy of splint therapy for the management of temporomandibular disorders: A metaanalysis*. *Journal of Oral Rehabilitation*, 43(9), 672683.
5. Forssell, H., et al. (2005). *Temporomandibular dysfunction and repositioning splint therapy*. *Journal of Craniomandibular Disorders*, 19(1), 1522.
6. Yang, C., et al. (2004). *The role of mandibular repositioning splint in the orthodontic treatment of patients with TMJ dysfunction*. *European Journal of Orthodontics*, 26(2), 189196.
7. Liu, Y., et al. (2000). *The treatment of temporomandibular disorders through repositioning splint therapy: A followup study*. *Journal of Prosthetic Dentistry*, 84(4), 421427.
8. Sidorenko, A. N. (2012). *Complex treatment of temporomandibular joint dysfunction combined with habitual dislocation of the mandible*. *Russian Dental Journal*, (4), 36–38.
9. Yatsuk, A. V., & Sivolapov, K. A. (2023). *Treatment and rehabilitation of patients with temporomandibular joint pathology*. *Bulletin of Peoples' Friendship University of Russia. Series: Medicine*, 27(1), 110–118.
10. Gurevich, Yu. Yu., & Prokhorova, V. O. (2025). *Rehabilitation of a patient with temporomandibular joint dysfunction using an orthosis*. *BHO*, (4), 159164.
11. Oreshaka, O. V., Dement'eva, E. A., Ganisik, A. V., & Sharov, A. M. (2019). *Epidemiology of temporomandibular joint disorders*. *Clinical Dentistry (Russia)*, 4(92), 97–99.

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**THE PROBLEM OF LOCAL AND SYSTEMIC SHIFTS IN THE
NEUROIMMUNOENDOCRINE SYSTEM UNDER THE INFLUENCE
OF PASSIVE SMOKING POLLUTANTS IN THE CONTEXT OF
PREMATURE POPULATION AGING**

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Abstract. *The study of the influence of passive smoking on the development of the gerontological process of schoolchildren in Baku due to the violation of their anthropometric indicators and the assessment of its impact on the health and rate of rapid maturation of children and adolescents, based on a general review of literary sources and data obtained as a result of a social survey of the population, as well as according to the indicators of the level of morbidity in different age groups of schoolchildren by analyzing their outpatient cards, is a relevant and in-demand topic of research, therefore, the adoption of preventive measures to limit smoking to improve the health and life of people is justified. These indicators are measured to identify the physical characteristics of children exposed and unexposed to passive smoking. By examining anthropometric indicators, it is possible to assess physical development and its compliance with age norms. This is especially important in childhood.*

Key words: *aging, smoking, passive smoking, pollutants, immune reactions, genetic factors*

External pollutants (air and environmental pollutants) have a damaging effect on the skin by inducing free radical formation, triggering an inflammatory cascade in the skin, activating an AhR-dependent mechanism (a transcription factor that regulates cell proliferation, inflammatory processes, and melanogenesis), and disrupting the skin microflora [1–4]. Smoking is known to be one of the main sources of pollutants. Numerous studies have noted the contribution of genetic factors to the predisposition to smoking. Regions of chromosomes 2, 4, 5, 6, 9, 10, 14, 16, 17, and 18, which are responsible, in particular, for the synthesis of dopamine receptors, are involved in the inheritance of a predisposition to smoking [5,6–8]. Smoking, by causing cellular aging, accelerates biological aging, making it one of the most common causes of preventable death. On average, cigarette smoking reduces overall life expectancy by 6–8 years, with each cigarette shortening life by approximately 11 minutes. Between the ages of 45 and 64, mortality rates for tobacco users are three times higher than for those who have never smoked. Cigarette smoke contains key environmental pollutants that negatively impact every system in the body, causing changes similar to premature aging. According to research, smoking accelerates skin aging by increasing the production of an enzyme called matrix metalloproteinase (MMP) [9–12]. In healthy skin, this enzyme breaks down collagen fibers, reducing collagen synthesis, which supports the outer layer of skin. This leads to premature aging and wrinkles on the face and skin, causing uneven skin tone, pigment spots, yellowing of tooth enamel, gum inflammation, thinning hair, and an increased risk of cataracts. Researchers have found that skin cells exposed to tobacco smoke produce significantly more destructive enzymes that enhance neutrophil elastase activity, thereby damaging elastic fibers and producing defective elastin [13–15]. These changes in elastic fibers are similar to those caused by sun exposure, with the only difference being that in smokers, they affect the reticular dermis rather than the papillary dermis. Smoking is also a risk factor for osteoporosis, which increases the risk of fractures, decreased fertility (making it more difficult to get pregnant), and early menopause (1.5 years earlier). Compared to nonsmokers, people who smoke or use smokeless tobacco products are more likely to develop oral cancer [16–18]. Cells of the body's three main regulatory systems — the nervous, immune, and endocrine — synthesize identical signaling molecules that mediate intercellular interactions. These molecules include peptide hormones, biogenic amines, polyunsaturated fatty acids, and others [19,20]. A significant amount of data has been accumulated concerning the state of neuroimmunoendocrine regulation in individual nosological forms; however, further development is needed, for example, on the influence of exogenous harmful factors on the intercellular signaling system, indicating their negative contribution to the state of intercellular signaling; on the other hand, it is still a matter of the future to identify what doses and duration of action of exogenous

pollutants affect the signaling mechanisms of homeostasis regulation, and which components of polluting factors have certain effects [21]. Undoubtedly, one of the most common negative exogenous factors is smoking. The impact of smoking on the neuroimmunoendocrine system in general, as well as its effect on the specific stage, has not been studied [22–25]. The role of exogenous factors, especially smoking, which causes an increase in the blood serum of a number of signaling molecules, such as C-reactive protein, fibrinogen, homocysteine, creatinine, and low-density lipoprotein cholesterol, has been confirmed [26–28]. Under the influence of smoking, there is an increase in the number of leukocytes and T-lymphocytes. T-lymphocytes are the most sensitive to long-term intensive smoking and can be regarded as biomarkers of active tobacco consumption [29,30–32]. Under the influence of cigarette smoke, chronic inflammation of the upper respiratory tract develops, and 20% of healthy smokers may experience bronchial conductivity disorders, while the local concentration of proinflammatory cytokines increases [33,34]. It is important to note that local increases in proinflammatory cytokine concentrations occur, among other things, with passive smoking. It has been found that the level of environmental pollution is significantly associated with elevated levels of chronic immune inflammation signaling molecules [35,36]. Pollutants not only affect the respiratory tract but also activate systemic inflammatory responses. This is confirmed by studies of immune responses in active and passive smokers [37]. It was found that passive smokers, compared to absolutely non-smokers, have significant changes in the leukocyte system: increased levels of granulocytes, lymphocytes, T-cells, and a significant increase in the level of soluble adhesion molecules and immunoglobulins — Ig M and Ig G. Thus, this direction — the impact of pollutants on the respiratory and immune systems, is promising and relevant in the context of the high prevalence of passive smoking and the deterioration of the environmental situation in the context of studying the problem of premature aging of the population [38–41]. A relatively new area of research is the genotoxicity of tobacco smoke and its role in accelerating the aging process in humans. The biological process of cellular aging occurs due to the irreversible cessation of cell division and growth, which, in turn, occurs due to Deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) damage [42–44]. Tobacco smoking leads to oxidative and genotoxic stress, with reactive oxygen species (ROS) playing a particularly important role, and the latter being linked to DNA damage.

Purpose of work. The study of the impact of passive smoking on the development of the gerontological process of schoolchildren in Baku due to the violation of their anthropometric indicators and the assessment of its impact on the health and rate of rapid maturation of children and adolescents is a relevant and in-demand topic of research, therefore, the adoption of preventive measures to limit smoking to improve the health and life of people is justified.

Materials and methods. We decided to determine the measurements of height, weight, and chest circumference by dividing schoolchildren into two groups — those exposed and those not exposed to passive smoking. The study was conducted as part of a study of the impact of passive smoking in families on children’s health and academic performance. We developed a questionnaire containing seven sets of questions on various social and hygienic aspects of passive smoking. The questionnaires were divided into two parts: one for students and the other for their parents. The study was conducted in five city secondary schools (Yasamal, Narimanov, and Sabunchi districts). To eliminate selectivity, we proceeded as follows. We decided to conduct and compare anthropometric measurements in a class of five children whose records were anonymously examined for illnesses at district clinics over the course of a year, as well as five children from the same class, randomly selected. Only fully completed questionnaires were included in the study. A total of 6,000 questionnaires were distributed to schoolchildren. Of these, 2,363 fully completed questionnaires contained responses from 3,895 parents—1,885 fathers and 2,010 mothers. Each of the 2,363 questionnaires represented one schoolchild, meaning that 2,363 families were surveyed. Six hundred eighty-seven families also had other children, either high school graduates or preschool-aged. Based on smoking intensity, families were divided into two groups: 818 families (tobacco-dependent) and 1,545 families (tobacco-nondependent, i.e., the control group). Based on passive smoking intensity, the tobacco-dependent group of families was divided into: Group 1—204 families, with mild smoking, less than 5 cigarettes per day; Group 2—252 families, with moderate smoking, 5–15 cigarettes per day; and Group 3—362 families, with parents who smoked heavily, with severe smoking, more than 15 cigarettes per day. Measurements were conducted separately for boys and girls. Observations were conducted in the most anthropometrically significant age groups of schoolchildren. Each anthropometric indicator — weight, height, and chest circumference — was analyzed separately and, where necessary, compared with others.

Results and discussion. The current period is characterized by extraordinary interest in the problems of the older generation, driven by several factors: the COVID-19 pandemic has exposed the fragility of geriatric care and the imperfections of inpatient social services for older adults, as more than half of the deaths from the new infection occurred in people over 65 years of age. According to WHO guidelines, areas of focus for improving care for older adults include frailty, intrinsic capacity, and resilience. Resilience is a new concept that has been actively studied in recent years. The formation of resilience is based on a complex of factors — genetic, immune, the state of the intestinal microbiota, the level of stress hormones, etc. Physical and psychological resilience are distinguished. It refers to the ability of an older person to cope with stress, both physical (for

example, a sudden increase or decrease in the level of physical activity) and psychological (retirement, loss of loved ones, etc.).

Table
Analysis of the gerontological condition of children and adults based on their growth and body weight development indicators

Weight and chest circumference indicators in different groups of schoolchildren											
Girls											
Exposed to passive smoking				Not exposed to passive smoking				Reliability of the difference			
n		M ±m		n		M ±m		t		p	
Age, years											
Weight	Height	Weight	Height	Weight	Height	Weight	Height	Weight	Height	Weight	Height
6,0–6,9											
20	20	22,5±0,5	118,4±0,8	18	18	25,7±0,6	121,3±0,8	4,10	2,45	<0,001	<0,05
7,0–7,9											
28	28	25,1±0,4	121,6±0,6	21	21	28,4±0,5	125,2±0,8	5,16	2,95	<0,001	<0,01
8,0–8,9											
18	18	31,3±0,5	124,8±0,7	22	22	30,8±0,4	128,7±0,7	0,78	2,33	<0,05	<0,05
9,0–9,9											
21	21	32,3±0,5	128,5±0,8	17	17	35,5±0,4	141,3±0,8	5,00	2,83	<0,001	<0,05
10,0–10,9											
26	26	36,8±0,4	138,3±0,6	25	25	39,4±0,4	142,0±0,6	4,56	2,59	<0,001	<0,01
11,0–11,9											
19	19	41,3±0,5	143,6±0,7	20	20	40,8±0,5	149,4±0,7	0,70	2,08	>0,05	<0,05
12,0–12,9											
26	26	43,6±0,4	149,1±0,6	24	24	42,4±0,4	153,8±0,7	2,11	2,44	<0,05	<0,05
13,0–13,9											
25	25	44,6±0,4	153,9±0,6	19	19	49,7±0,6	158,2±0,8	7,08	2,40	<0,001	<0,05
14,0–14,9											
20	20	49,1±0,5	157,8±0,7	21	21	52,4±0,5	162,2±0,7	4,65	2,21	<0,001	<0,05
15,0–15,9											
24	24	52,7±0,5	161,8±0,7	23	23	56,6±0,5	166,3±0,7	5,49	4,15	<0,001	<0,001
16,0–16,9											
23	23	57,0±0,4	166,0±0,8	23	23	60,8±0,5	170,3±0,8	5,94	2,94	<0,001	<0,01

Note: n is the number of schoolchildren; M ±m is the average value of the indicator

Figure
Average values of development indicators in different groups of schoolchildren

According to the data in Table 1, in general, the height of girls in the 1st group, compared to the 2nd group, is 2.8–5.8 cm less. In particular, the weight of schoolchildren in the 1st group in some age groups was even greater than that of schoolchildren in the 2nd group — in girls by 0.5–1.2 kg. We are inclined to explain the reason for this situation as follows. Schoolchildren exposed to passive smoking are not distinguished by physical activity, lead a sedentary lifestyle, as a result of which they gain weight. Against the background of slowing growth, weight gain, although not very large, is quite acceptable. Basically, in the 1st group, girls weigh 2.6–5.3 kg less than schoolchildren in the 2nd group. At first glance, the differences in anthropometric indicators between schoolchildren with and without passive smoking are not that great. For example, height is less among girls by 4.08 ± 0.21 cm ($t=0.94$; $p>0.05$). We have already noted that growth is a systemic indicator of the body’s normal functioning and its dynamic, consistent development. Therefore, even a slight growth retardation, which is facilitated by passive smoking, indicates poor body function. On average, girls weigh 2.56 ± 0.18 kg more ($t=0.15$; $p>0.05$). Excess weight itself is an independent risk factor that adversely affects children’s health.

Conclusion. There is compelling evidence that smoking is associated with accelerated biological aging, as well as an increased risk of frailty and cognitive impairment. Many mechanisms explaining the link between smoking at different stages of life and accelerated aging of various organs and body systems have now been deciphered. It is well known that some people appear older than their actual age. The main causes of this accelerated facial aging are excessive exposure to solar ultraviolet radiation, smoking, excessive alcohol consumption, weight loss after age 40, eating disorders and weight gain before age 40, and the use of antidepressants. The main health problems in adolescence include injuries, poor diet, physical inactivity, obesity, and mental health disorders. The World Health Organization (WHO) has recognized that good health, from prenatal development through adolescence and young adulthood, is one of the keys to successful social and economic development in every country. To increase the body's reserve capacity and reduce the negative effects of environmental exposure, children with adequate or low physical development are recommended to optimize their daily routines, engage in targeted physical training, participate in therapeutic exercise groups, and engage in psychotherapy. Global experience shows that many common illnesses in school-aged children can be effectively, easily, and affordably addressed through the implementation of school-based programs on health protection and promotion, as well as healthy nutrition. Effective implementation of programs to limit tobacco consumption and public policies to combat tobacco use is an integral part of preventing chronic noncommunicable diseases, reducing morbidity and premature mortality, and increasing life expectancy in the country.

References:

1. Thun M. J., Carter B. D., et al. *50-Year Trends in Smoking-Related Mortality in the United States // N Engl J Med.* — 2013. — Vol. 368. — P. 351–364.
2. Babayev P. N. *Features of tobacco smoking in families of Baku and assessment of the effectiveness of measures to protect children from the effects of passive smoking/Azerb.med.journal/Dept. of Public Health and Health Organization/Azerb. med.univ. Baku/2013/pp. 68–73.*
3. Ibragimova E.E., Yakubova E. F., Yakubova Z. A. *Assessment of the impact of smoking on visceral organs and regulatory functions of the body. Population Health and Environment.* 2018;3(300):51–54/doi.org/10.35627/2219–5238/2018–300–3–51–54.
4. Künzli N., Perez L., von Klot S. et al. *Investigating air pollution and atherosclerosis in humans: concepts and outlook. Prog Cardiovasc Dis.* 2011;53(5):334–343. DOI: 10.1016/j.pcad.2010.12.006.
5. Shirokhova, N. M. *Community-acquired pneumonia in elderly and senile individuals: features of diagnosis and clinical course: diss. ... candidate of medical sciences / N. M. Shirokhova.* — M., 2012.

6. P.N. Babayev, N. R. Jabbarova/Tobacco smoking and dysfunction of metabolic processes in the body/Modern achievements of Azerbaijan medicine/Baku/No. 3, 2024. pp. 89–93.

7. Babayev P. N. Nagieva R. K. Passive smoking as an immunological risk factor for ophthalmological morbidity in schoolchildren and its socio-hygienic characteristics / Allergology and clinical immunology / Department of Public Health and Healthcare Organization / Azerbaijan Medical University of Baku / 2021 / pp. 17–26

8. Mustafin, R. N. Epigenetic hypothesis of the role of peptides in aging / R. N. Mustafin, E. K. Khusnutdinova // *Advances in Gerontology*. — 2018. — Vol. 31, No. 1. — P. 10–21.

9. Proshchaev K.I., Ilnitsky A. N., Pavlova T. V., Bashuk V. V., Pavlova L. A., Sovenko G. N., Chizhova M. A. Local and systemic neuroimmunoendocrine shifts under the influence of pollutants in the context of premature aging: analysis of the state of the problem // *Fundamental research*. — 2011. — No. 6. — P. 150–153;

10. Leshchenko I.G., Galkin R. A. Guide to surgical diseases of the elderly. — 2nd edition, revised and enlarged. — Samara: Fort, 2016.

11. Sakharova G.M., Antonov N. S. Tobacco smoking and reproductive function of women // *Russian Medical Journal*. — 2013. — No. 1. — P. 12–20.

12. Souza ES, Crippa JA, Pasian SR, Martinez JA. University of São Paulo Reasons for Smoking Scale: a new tool for the evaluation of smoking motivation. *J Bras Pneumol*. 2010;36(6):768–778.

13. P.N. Babayev, S. F. Mirgadi /Frequency and structure of morbidity among schoolchildren exposed to the harmful effects of passive smoking/Modern achievements of Azerbaijani medicine/No. 2.2024/pp. 152–157

14. Huttunen R., Heikkinen T., Syrjänen J. Smoking and the outcome of infection // *J Intern Med*. — 2011. — Vol. 269. — P. 258–269.

15. Almirall J., Serra-Prat M., Bolibar I. Passive smoking at home is a risk factor for community-acquired pneumonia in older adults: a population-based case-control study // *Community Acquired Infection*. — 2015. — Vol. 2. — P. 32–37.

16. P.N. Babayev, R. G. Musayev/Passive smoking as a social and public ailment among schoolchildren in Baku/Modern achievements of Azerbaijani medicine/Baku,/No. 1, 2024. p. 244–24832.

17. Golenkov A. V. Social and psychological characteristics of tobacco addiction among residents of Chuvashia. *Narcology*. 2013;1:28–32.

18. Yui R.I., Semchenkova S. A., Kruglikovskaya T. F., Ergazina M. Zh. Cytogram of buccal epithelium in elderly people living in urban and rural areas // *Morphology and evidence-based medicine*. — 2013. — No. 4. — P. 39–41.

19. Gladyshev G. P. Thermodynamic theory of evolution and aging // *Uspekhi gerontol*. 2012. Vol. 25. No. 3. P. 373–385.

20. Safarova G. *Heterogeneity of population ageing in Russia and policy implications // In: Population ageing in Central and Eastern Europe. Societal and policy implications / Ed. A. Hoff. England and USA: Ashgate, 2011. P. 53–76.*

21. Tsareva N. M. *Relevance of anti-tobacco propaganda among children and adolescents / Tsareva N. M., Tsareva Yu. A. // Actual problems of children's life safety and ways to solve them: collection of materials of the All-Russian scientific and practical conference with international participation / under the general editorship: N. V. Timushkina, D. V. Vorobyov. — Balashov, 2017. — P. 443–448.*

22. Babayev P. N. *Frequency and structure of morbidity among schoolchildren depending on the intensity of exposure to passive smoking / Modern achievements of Azerbaijani Medicine / Department of Public Health and Health Organization / Azerbaijani Medical University. Baku / 2021 / pp. 76–81.*

23. Arkhipova N. S., Arieveva A. L., Popova E. K., et al. *Survival of geriatric patients of indigenous and non-indigenous nationalities with ischemic heart disease in the Republic of Sakha (Yakutia): analysis of five-year follow-up observation // Uspekhi gerontol. 2012. Vol. 25. No. 1. P. 95–99.*

24. Golenkov A. V. *Regional statistical models of tobacco smoking. Russian Medical Journal. 2013;4:8–10.*

25. Babaev P. N. *The relationship between seeking medical care and susceptibility to psychosomatic diseases of schoolchildren with the factor of passive smoking Svpn. 2020. Omsk No. 2 (107) pp. 75–81.*

26. Egorova A. G., Klimova T. M. *Mortality of the working age population of the Republic of Sakha (Yakutia): trends and forecast // Yakut. honey. magazine 2013. T. 43. No. 1. P. 8–11.*

27. Baranov V. S. *The human genome, missing heredity and genetic passport // Med. genetics. 2011. Vol. 10. No. 9. Pp. 3–10.*

28. Baranov V. S., Baranova E. V. *Human Genome. Epigenetics of Multifactorial Diseases and Personalized Medicine // Biosphere. 2012. Vol. 4. No. 1. P. 76–85.*

29. Moskalov A. A. *Genetics and epigenetics of aging and longevity // Ecological Genetics. 2013. Vol. 11. No. 1. P. 3–11.*

30. Artamonova G. V., Maksimov S. A., Tabakaev M. V., Shapovalova E. B. *Health losses from myocardial infarction caused by anthropogenic pollution of the atmosphere of an industrial center. Hygiene and Sanitation. 2015;94(3):30–34.*

31. Fuertes E., van der Plaats D., Minelli C. *Antioxidant genes and susceptibility to air pollution for respiratory and cardiovascular health. Free Rad Biol Med. 2020;151:88–98. DOI: 32.1016/j.freeradbiomed.2020.01.181.*

32. Babayev P. N., Musayev R. G., Mirgadi S. F. *Decreased immunity of schoolchildren under the influence of passive smoking/Jurnal of Azerbaijan Allergy and Clinical Immunology/vol/ 12; No. 1/Baku. 2024/pp. 51–66*

33. Yitshak Sade M., Kloog I., Liberty I. et al. The association between air pollution exposure and glucose and lipids levels. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab.* 2016; 101(6):2460–2467. DOI: 10.1210/jc.2016-1378.

34. Perez C., Hazari M., Farraj A. Role of autonomic reflex arcs in cardiovascular responses to air pollution exposure. *Cardiovasc Toxicol.* 2014; 15(1):69–78. DOI: 10.1007/s12012-014-9272-0.

35. Wang M., Hou Z., Xu H. et al. Association of estimated long-term exposure to air pollution and traffic proximity with a marker for coronary atherosclerosis in a nationwide study in China. *JAMA New Open.* 2019; 2(6): e196553. DOI: 10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2019.6553.

36. Features of clinical examination of elderly and senile patients / K. I. Proshchaev [et al.] // *Advances in Gerontology.* — 2013. — No. 3. — P. 79–82.

37. Ilnitsky, A. Healthy aging / A. Ilnitsky, N. Pozdnyakova, I. Noskova // *Science and innovation.* — 2016. — No. 166 (12). — P. 18–21.

38. Galiakberova, I. L. Problems and prospects of using the neuropsychological approach in a population study of population viability / I. L. Galiakberova, E. A. Mysnikova // *World of Science.* — 2017. — No. 4 (5). — P. 6.

39. Babayev P.N., Musayev R. G. Passive smoking as a social problem among schoolchildren in Baku / *Azerbaijan Medical University / Scientific and practical conference in Baku.* 2024, pp. 85–88.

40. Ilnitsky, A. N. Specialized geriatric examination / A. N. Ilnitsky, K. I. Proshchaev // *Gerontological Journal named after V. F. Kuprevich.* — 2012. — No. 4–5. — P. 66–84.

41. P.N. Babayev, R. G. Musayev, N. R. Jabbarova, A. G. Jafarova Non-communicable diseases that negatively affect the health of schoolchildren due to their exposure to passive smoking. / *Modern achievements of Azerbaijan medicine / No. 1,* 2022. pp. 160–166

42. Babaev P.N., Musaev R. G., Dzhabbarova N. R. Explanatory work to identify the awareness of schoolchildren, as well as their parents, about the dangers of passive smoking and assessing the role of parents, teachers and health workers in this area / *Higher school: scientific research. Interuniversity international congress / Moscow.* 2025 / pp. 146–153

43. Performance Depending on the Material and Educational Level of Their Parents/ *Azerbaijan-Turkey 1st International Conference of Allergists and Immunologists.* Baku/2024. pp.73–74

44. Kolpakova A.F., Sharipov R. N., Volkova O. A. The impact of air pollution with suspended substances on the cardiovascular system. *Siberian Medical Journal (Irkutsk).* 2015; 30(3):7–12.

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THE INFLUENCE OF THE FATHER'S MEDICAL HISTORY ON THE RISK OF DEVELOPING PATHOLOGICAL CONDITIONS IN LATE PREMATURE NEWBORNS

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Abstract. *Newborn health is determined by multiple factors, including genetic, epigenetic, and environmental influences. In recent years, interest has grown in the role of the father in shaping the health of his offspring, particularly in the transmission of environmentally induced epigenetic markers via sperm. The aim of this study was to evaluate the relationship between paternal medical history and the risk of developing various pathological conditions in late preterm infants. Data from 77 newborns and their fathers were analyzed. Statistical analysis utilized the Student's t-test, Fisher's exact test, and ROC analysis. Significant (tens to hundreds of times) increases in the risk of developing certain pathologies were identified, including Down syndrome in paternal infertility, congenital pneumonia and hypertrophic cardiomyopathy in paternal ENT pathologies or hypertension, and hemorrhagic disease of the newborn in children whose fathers were born prematurely. The findings highlight the need to consider paternal history when assessing risks and developing disease prevention strategies in newborns.*

Keywords: *paternal history, late preterm infants, epigenetics, risk factors.*

Introduction

Childhood is an important period for the development of various body systems. In recent years, research into prognostic markers for the development of pathologies in children has remained highly relevant. The majority of scientific work has focused on the influence of maternal factors on the health of offspring. Limited data indicate the influence of physiological, behavioral, and environmental factors associated with the father on the health of the newborn [1]. The discovery of the phenomenon of “epigenetic inheritance” made it possible to elucidate the mechanism by which these factors influence each other. Epigenetic inheritance refers to the transmission of information unrelated to the DNA base sequence to offspring over several generations through the germline [2]. Paternal environmental exposure (including nutrition, mental state, and exposure to toxins) can cause epigenetic changes in his sperm. Epigenetic changes include DNA methylation, chromatin modification, and the presence of small and long non-coding RNAs (ncRNAs), which, without disrupting the DNA sequence, can lead to altered phenotypes in offspring [3]. Disruptions in the functioning of epigenetic regulatory systems have been shown to play an important role in the pathogenesis of the most common non-communicable diseases [4]. To understand and further study the role of the father in the transmission of epigenetic signals induced by environmental factors, a concept was formulated at the Paternal Origins of Health and Disease (POHaD) symposium held in Zurich in 2017. This highlights the urgent need for further research in this area [5].

Study Objective

To evaluate the influence of various aspects of paternal medical history on the development of neonatal diseases in late preterm infants using statistical analysis methods.

Materials and Methods

A retrospective analysis of data from infants born at 34 0/7 to 36 6/7 weeks of gestation was conducted, along with data on their fathers, obtained through a questionnaire. The study included assessment of the following parameters: paternal age, his history of harmful habits, his history of somatic pathologies, and information on the incidence of diseases in his immediate family.

Statistical analysis was performed using StatTech 4.8.0 software. The Student’s t-test was used to compare mean values in groups with different neonatal pathologies. Fisher’s exact test was used to assess the relationship between the presence of specific paternal diseases and the risk of developing neonatal pathologies. To assess the discriminatory power of paternal age in predicting certain pathologies in newborns, ROC analysis was used. A $p < 0.05$ level was considered statistically significant.

Results and Discussion

Maternal factors influencing the development of congenital defects of the kidneys and urinary tract are currently not fully understood. Current research links fetal renal pathologies to factors such as acute respiratory infections during pregnancy, gestational diabetes, maternal kidney disease, certain medications, and maternal age [6,7]. Our study found that paternal age is a statistically significant predictor of dilated renal pelvis in late preterm infants (Q63.8) (see Figures 1 and 2).

Figure 1 — ROC curve characterizing the discriminatory ability of the father’s age in predicting the dilation of the renal pelvis in a late premature newborn

Figure 2 — Sensitivity and specificity analysis of the model depending on the probability thresholds. The sensitivity and specificity of the resulting predictive model were 87.1% and 55.6%, respectively.

Dilation of the renal pelvis in late preterm infants was predicted by paternal age greater than or equal to 27.000 (AUC = 0.713; 95 % CI: 0.556–0.870, $p = 0.038$).

Maternal factors influencing the development of congenital defects of the kidneys and urinary tract are also not fully understood. Current research links fetal renal pathologies to factors such as acute respiratory infections during pregnancy, gestational diabetes, maternal kidney disease, certain medications, and maternal age [6,7]. A history of paternal infertility was associated with an 82.200-fold increased risk of Down syndrome (Q90) in the newborn. The differences were statistically significant ($p = 0.042$; methods used: Fisher’s exact test; 95 % CI: 2.635–2564.669) (see Figure 3).

Figure 3 — Analysis of the probability of Down syndrome (Q90) depending on paternal infertility

Data analysis showed that children whose fathers had a history of ENT pathologies had a 139-fold higher risk of developing congenital pneumonia (P23.0) ($p = 0.028$; methods used: Fisher’s exact test; 95 % CI: 3.851–5016.948) (see Figure 4).

Figure 4 — Analysis of the risk of developing congenital pneumonia (P23.0) depending on paternal ENT pathology

Analysis of the probability of developing hypertrophic cardiomyopathy (I42.2) in a late preterm neonate revealed statistically significant differences depending on paternal risk factors. When assessing the impact of paternal ENT diseases, it was found that their presence increases the likelihood of hypertrophic cardiomyopathy (I42.2) in the child by 139 times ($p = 0.028$; methods used: Fisher’s exact test; 95 % CI: 3.851–5016.948) (see Figure 5). According to the data presented in Figure 6, arterial hypertension in the father also increased the risk of hypertrophic cardiomyopathy (I42.2) in the child by 139 times ($p = 0.028$; method used: Fisher’s exact test; 95 % CI: 3.851–5016.948).

Previous studies also indicate a similar relationship between maternal hypertension during pregnancy and the development of cardiac pathologies in the child [8].

Figure 5 — Analysis of hypertrophic cardiomyopathy (I42.2) depending on the presence of ENT diseases in the father

Figure 6 — Analysis of hypertrophic cardiomyopathy (I42.2) depending on paternal hypertension

The study revealed an interesting pattern: an increased risk (83.400-fold) of developing hemorrhagic disease of the newborn (P53) was observed in late pre-term infants whose fathers were also born prematurely ($p = 0.042$; method used: Fisher's exact test; 95 % CI: 2.673–2.601.804), see Figure 7.

Figure 7 — Correlation between the paternal history of preterm birth and the risk of developing hemorrhagic disease of the fetus and newborn (P53) in their offspring.

Figure 8 — Analysis of other transient neonatal coagulation disorders (P61.6) depending on the arterial hypertension in the family history of the father

Somatic diseases in immediate paternal relatives had a statistically significant impact on the development of pathologies in late preterm infants. Thus, the presence of arterial hypertension in the father's family history increased the likelihood of developing transient neonatal coagulation disorders (P61.6) in the child by more than 20 times ($p = 0.032$, respectively; methods used: Fisher's exact test; 95 % CI: 1.626–262.707) (see Figure 8). A family history of cerebrovascular accident in the

father was associated with a 14,000-fold increase in the risk of developing transient neonatal thrombocytopenia (P61.0) ($p = 0.037$; methods used: Fisher's exact test; 95 % CI: 1.661–117.968; see Figure 9).

Figure 9 — Analysis of transient neonatal thrombocytopenia (P61.0) depending on the paternal family history of cerebrovascular accident

A paternal family history of cerebrovascular accident is associated with an increased risk of certain neurological disorders in the child. Such anamnesis increased the probability of seizure syndrome by almost a hundred times ($p < 0.001$; methods used: Fisher's exact test; 95 % CI: 6.787–1400.757; see Figure 10) and more than 40 times increased the risk of developing vegetative-visceral dysfunctions ($p = 0.012$; methods used: Fisher's exact test; 95 % CI: 3.016–622.558; see Figure 11) and tetraparesis (95 % CI: 1.571–1250.994).

Figure 10 — Analysis of the risk of seizure syndrome depending on the cerebrovascular accident in the father's family history

Figure 11 — Analysis of vegetative-visceral dysfunctions in relation to a paternal family history of cerebrovascular accidents

The study found a correlation between paternal addictions (alcohol and drug dependence) and a 45-fold increase (95% CI: 1.595–1269.644 for alcohol dependence; 95% CI: 1.595–1269.644 for drug dependence) in the risk of developing polycythemia in late preterm infants (P61.1).

It is important to emphasize that this study has several limitations. First, it is retrospective, making it difficult to establish cause and effect. Second, the data used were based on self-reported data from parents of late preterm infants without confirmation by medical records, which may impact the accuracy and completeness of the information. A third limitation is the small sample size, due to the refusal of many parents to provide information. Conclusion

Modern research suggests that the sperm epigenome may serve as a mechanism for the transmission of exogenous factors from father to child [9]. Our results confirm these data, revealing a statistically significant correlation between heredity and the development of diseases. Analysis of paternal medical histories revealed that factors such as age, somatic diseases (hypertension, ENT pathologies), infertility, unhealthy habits, and a family history of cardiovascular disease and cerebrovascular accidents significantly influence the incidence of late preterm infants.

In light of the available, albeit limited, data on the etiology of “epigenetic diseases,” it is advisable to consider the paternal medical history when planning a pregnancy. Particular attention should be paid to men in high-risk groups: those who are occupationally exposed to endocrine disruptors, lead an unhealthy lifestyle, or have fertility problems [10].

References:

1. Razvarina, I. N. *Specifics of risk factors for children's health from the father's side* / I. N. Razvarina, Yu. E. Shmatova, A. N. Gordievskaya // *IV All-Russian Demographic Forum with International Participation: Collection of forum abstracts, Moscow, December 2–3, 2022 / Editor-in-Chief T. K. Rostovskaya.* — Moscow: Federal Research Sociological Center of the Russian Academy of Sciences, 2022. — P. 50–51;

2. Champroux A, Cocquet J, Henry-Berger J, Drevet JR, Kocer A. *A Decade of Exploring the Mammalian Sperm Epigenome: Paternal Epigenetic and Transgenerational Inheritance.* *Front Cell Dev Biol.* 2018 May 15;6:50. doi: 10.3389/fcell.2018.00050. PMID: 29868581; PMCID: PMC5962689;

3. Zhang Y, Shi J, Rassoulzadegan M, Tuorto F, Chen Q. *Sperm RNA code programmes the metabolic health of offspring.* *Nat Rev Endocrinol.* 2019 Aug;15(8):489–498. doi: 10.1038/s41574-019-0226-2. Epub 2019 Jun 24. PMID: 31235802; PMCID: PMC6626572.] [Liao H, Lu D, Reisinger SN, Mehrabadi MR, Gubert C, Hannan AJ. *Epigenetic effects of paternal environmental exposures and experiences on offspring phenotypes.* *Trends Genet.* 2025 Sep;41(9):735–761. doi: 10.1016/j.tig.2025.04.015. Epub 2025 Jun 3. PMID: 40467385;

4. Nikitin, A. I. *Paternal factors and offspring health* / A. I. Nikitin // *Medicine: theory and practice.* — 2019. — V. 4, No. 5. — P. 388;

5. Soubry A. *POHaD: why we should study future fathers.* *Environ Epigenet.* 2018 Apr 26;4(2): dvy007. doi: 10.1093/eep/dvy007. PMID: 29732171; PMCID: PMC5920283;

6. Erman M.V., Balatsky S. Yu. *Congenital anomalies of kidney development in children // Knowledge of propaedeutics is the basis of clinical thinking of a pediatrician: a collection of works dedicated to the 80th anniversary of prof. A. Ya. St. Petersburg: InformMed, 2015. Pp. 148–164;*

7. *Congenital malformations of the kidneys and urinary tract: an analysis of modern diagnostic principles and prognostically significant markers of renal tissue damage / V. S. Pavlova, D. S. Kryuchko, Yu. L. Podurovskaya, N. A. Pekareva // Neonatology: news, opinions, training.* — 2018. — Vol. 6, No. 2 (20). — Pp.

8. Aye CYL, Lewandowski AJ, Lamata P, Upton R, Davis E, Ohuma EO, Kenworthy Y, Boardman H, Frost AL, Adwani S, McCormick K, Leeson P. *Prenatal and Postnatal Cardiac Development in Offspring of Hypertensive Pregnancies.* *J Am Heart Assoc.* 2020 May 5;9(9): e014586. doi: 10.1161/JAHA.119.014586. Epub 2020 Apr 30. Erratum in: *J Am Heart Assoc.* 2021 Jan 19;10(2): e014640. doi: 10.1161/JAHA.119.014640. PMID: 32349586; PMCID: PMC7428573;

9. Soubry A, Hoyo C, Butt CM, Fieuws S, Price TM, Murphy SK, Stapleton HM. Human exposure to flame-retardants is associated with aberrant DNA methylation at imprinted genes in sperm. *Environ Epigenet* 2017;3:1–13;

10. Soubry A. POHaD: why we should study future fathers. *Environ Epigenet*. 2018 Apr 26;4(2): dvy007. doi: 10.1093/eep/dvy007. PMID: 29732171; PMCID: PMC5920283

DRY EXTRACT OF MILK THISTLE SEEDS: OBTAINING AND STANDARDIZATION

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Abstract. *The medicinal plant milk thistle (*Silybum marianum*) was used by ancient healers as a tonic for liver diseases, capable of alleviating congestion in the liver and spleen, and as an effective remedy for jaundice. In Turkmen folk medicine, milk thistle seeds were used to treat pain caused by gallstones, jaundice, disorders of the liver and biliary tract, spleen, hemorrhoids, and constipation, as well as a strengthening and tonic agent for the body. The scientific article describes the preparation and standardization of a dry extract from milk thistle seeds. In our previous studies of the phytochemical composition of milk thistle (*Silybum marianum*) growing in Turkmenistan, its seeds showed a moisture content of 4.9%, total ash of 5.5%, ash insoluble in 10% hydrochloric acid of 3.8%, flavolignan content of 2.9%, and seed oil of 20.12%. The phytochemical composition and quality indicators of milk thistle seeds have proven compliance with GF standards.*

Keywords: *milk thistle, flavanolignan, dry extract, standardization, spectrophotometry, high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC).*

Introduction. The medicinal plant milk thistle (*Silybum marianum*) was used by ancient healers as a tonic for liver diseases, capable of alleviating congestion in the liver and spleen, and as an effective remedy for jaundice. In Turkmen folk medicine, milk thistle seeds were used to treat pain caused by gallstones, jaundice, disorders of the liver and biliary tract, spleen, hemorrhoids, and constipation, as well as a strengthening and tonic agent for the body. Milk thistle belongs to the

genus of the same name within the Asteraceae family. Scientific data indicates that there are two species of this medicinal plant worldwide, with one species found in Turkmenistan [1; 2; 8; 12].

According to scientific data, milk thistle seeds contain 40 different medicinal and nutritional substances. The seeds contain up to 30% oil, primarily composed of linoleic acid — 54%, oleic acid — 36%, and palmitic acid — 8%. The main active component of milk thistle seeds is considered to be flavolignan compounds, also known as the silymarin complex. This compound includes silybin A and B, silychristin, isosilychristin, isosilybin A and B, dehydrosilybin, silydianin, and the flavonoid taxifolin. The primary components are the diastereoisomers silybin A and B, which account for 50–70% of the flavolignans, followed by silychristin, silydianin, and isosilybin [2; 7; 8].

The safety and high therapeutic effect of milk thistle as a phytopreparation for the treatment of liver diseases have been scientifically confirmed by scientists of the World Health Organization. In 1970, the silymarin flavonolignan complex from milk thistle was officially recognized in the medical system as a medicinal product with hepatoprotective properties [6].

When using milk thistle seeds for medicinal purposes, according to the European and American Pharmacopoeias, a standard of 1.5–2% silymarin in the dry weight of mature fruits is considered normal. However, extensive scientific data indicates that the amount of silymarin in seeds can vary depending on the plant's genotype and cultivation conditions. According to some scientific data, its content ranges from 0.62 to 6%. According to the European Pharmacopoeia, the standard content of flavonolignan compounds in dry milk thistle extract, obtained by various methods, is considered to be 35–65% [4; 5; 11].

In our previous studies of the phytochemical composition of milk thistle (*Silybum marianum*) growing in Turkmenistan, its seeds showed a moisture content of 4.9%, total ash of 5.5%, ash insoluble in 10% hydrochloric acid of 3.8%, flavolignan content of 2.9%, and seed oil of 20.12%. Additionally, light brown and yellowish-brown dry extracts were obtained by Soxhlet extraction [3].

The purpose of research is to obtain a dry extract from milk thistle seeds (*Silybum marianum*) grown in Turkmenistan and to standardize the resulting dry extract.

Materials and Methods. For this study, milk thistle seeds collected in the Nyare valley of Garrygala etrap on July 25, 2025, were used.

Method for Obtaining Dry Extract from Milk Thistle Seeds. The isolation of dry extract from milk thistle (*Silybum marianum*) seeds under laboratory conditions was carried out by Soxhlet extraction. The extraction process consisted of the following stages: seed grinding, sieving, defatting in petroleum ether, extraction in 70% alcohol, vacuum filtration, vacuum evaporation, freeze-drying

(lyophilization), grinding in a grinding chamber, and sieving on a vibratory sieve. The methodology for obtaining dry extract from milk thistle under laboratory conditions is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Method for obtaining dry extract of milk thistle seeds under laboratory conditions

This is a translation to the above scheme

Milk thistle seeds	Soxhlet extraction, extractant — petroleum ether, 6 hours	Milk Thistle Seed Oil	Soxhlet extraction, extractant — 70% ethanol, 6 hours	Vacuum filtration	vacuum evaporation, thickening t=400C
Milk Thistle Extract	Vibrating sieve screening, 5 minutes		Grinding in a grinding mill, 200 rpm, 5 minutes		Lyophilization (or Freeze-drying) -45°C 200 mTorr, 24 hours

Moisture Content Analysis of Dry Milk Thistle Seed Extract [5]. The moisture content of the dry milk thistle seed extract was determined according to a pharmacopoeial method (European Pharmacopoeia 10.0). For the analysis, 0.5 g of the dry extract was weighed on an analytical balance and then placed into pre-dried

and weighed porcelain crucibles. The crucibles containing the samples were left in a drying oven at 105 °C for 2 hours. After drying, the crucibles with the samples were cooled in a desiccator and re-weighed on an analytical balance. The moisture content of the dry extract was calculated using the following formula:

$$x (\%) = \frac{(M - M_1)}{M} * 100;$$

M—Mass of the extract before drying, g.
M₁ — Mass of the extract after drying, g.

Total ash of dry milk thistle seed extract [5].

3.0 g of dry extract were placed into empty crucibles. The dry extract was then incinerated to ash in a muffle furnace for 20 minutes, first at 100 °C and subsequently at 500 °C. Afterward, the crucibles containing the ash were transferred to a desiccator and cooled to room temperature. The crucibles with the ash were weighed on an analytical balance, and the mass was calculated using a formula:

$$X = \frac{m_1 * 100 * 100}{m_2 * (100 - W)}$$

where, m₁ — ash weight, g;
m₂ — mass of the sample, g;
W — sample humidity.

$$X = \frac{m_1 * 100 * 100}{m_2 * (100 - W)};$$

Ash of Silybum marianum Dry Extract, Insoluble in 10% Hydrochloric Acid [5]. To the residue inside the crucible after igniting the dry extract, 15 ml of 10% hydrochloric acid solution was added. The crucible was covered with a watch glass and heated on a water bath for 10 minutes. The watch glass was rinsed, 5 ml of hot water was added to the crucible, and the mixture was filtered through ashless filter paper. The filter with the precipitate was washed with hot water until there was a negative reaction for chlorides in the running water. It was then transferred to the same crucible, dried, ignited, heated, and weighed. The amount of ash insoluble in 10% hydrochloric acid solution in absolutely dry raw material was calculated as a percentage using the formula.

$$x = \frac{(m_1 - m) * 100 * 100}{m_2 * (100 - W)};$$

where: m₁ — ash weight, g;
m — filter weight, g;
m₂ — weight of raw materials, g;
W — humidity of raw materials, %.

The pH value of the dry extract [7]. To determine the pH value of a dry extract, standard solutions with different pH values (pH 1.65, 3.56, 4.01, 6.86, 9.18, 12.43) were prepared, and a pH meter was calibrated. 1.0 g of the dry extract was dissolved in 50 ml of distilled water, and the pH value was determined.

Solubility test of dry milk thistle extract. The solubility test of dry milk thistle extract was conducted according to the pharmacopoeial monograph method. [9].

Table 1. Definition of Solubility for Pharmaceutical Substances and Excipients

Term	Approximate volume of solvent (ml) required to dissolve 1.0 g of the substance	Dry extract of milk thistle (<i>Silybum marianum</i>) (Water solubility)	Dry extract of milk thistle (<i>Silybum marianum</i>) (Solubility in 96% alcohol)
Very easily dissolves	To 1		
Easily dissolves	From 1 to 10		
Soluble	From 10 to 30		Soluble
Moderately soluble	From 30 to 100	Moderately soluble	
Slightly soluble	From 100 to 1000		
Dissolves very little	From 1000 to 10000		
Almost insoluble	More than 10000		

Phytochemical Analysis of Dry Milk Thistle (*Silybum marianum*) Seed Extract [5; 10]. For the phytochemical analysis, extracts of dry milk thistle seeds were prepared at a 1:10 ratio using water, 80% ethanol, and petroleum ether.

Carbohydrate Analysis. Benedict's Test. Take 1.0 mL of the extract, filtered through paper, and add 1.0 mL of Benedict's reagent. Heat the mixture in a boiling water bath. The formation of a red precipitate indicates the presence of sugars in the dry extract.

Protein and Free Amino Acid Analysis. Biuret Test. To 2.0 ml of extract, diluted copper sulfate solution is added drop by drop. The formation of a red or pink hue indicates the presence of peptides with at least two peptide bonds.

Flavonoid Analysis. Alkaline Reagent Test. Add 3–4 drops of 2% sodium hydroxide solution to 2.0 ml of the extract. The formation of a bright yellow color in the solution, and its decolorization after adding 2–3 drops of diluted hydrochloric acid and shaking, indicates the presence of flavonoids.

Aluminum Chloride Test. To 1.0 ml of extract, filtered through a paper filter, add 2–3 drops of 5% aluminum chloride solution. If the extract contains flavonoids with two hydroxyl groups at the C3 and C5 positions, a lemon-yellow color will form.

Wilson's Test. To 2 ml of the extract, add 1–2 drops of boric acid solution and 1 drop of oxalic acid solution. If the plant extract contains 3- and 5-hydroxyflavones and 3- and 5-hydroxyflavonols, a light yellow color with a yellowish-green tint will form.

Tannin Test. Ferric Chloride Test. To 5.0 ml of the extract, add 2–3 drops of a 10% ferric chloride solution. A change in the solution's color to dark green indicates the presence of phenolic compounds.

Potassium Dichromate Analysis. Add 3–5 drops of a 5% potassium dichromate solution to 3.0 ml of the extract. If tannins are present, the solution darkens or a yellow-brown precipitate forms.

Saponin Test. Froth Test. Add 5.0 ml of purified water to 0.1 g of extract and shake vigorously. The formation of persistent froth indicates the presence of saponins.

Alkaloid Test. *Wagner's Reaction.* Dissolve the dry extract in dilute hydrochloric acid and filter. Use the filtered solution for the alkaloid test. To 1.0 ml of the plant extract, add 1.0 ml of Wagner's reagent. The formation of a reddish-brown precipitate indicates the presence of alkaloids.

Glycoside Test. *Keller-Kiliani Reaction.* To 1.0 ml of the extract, add 0.5 ml of 0.1 N acetic acid, 2–3 drops of 2% ferric chloride solution, and then 5.0 ml of 98% sulfuric acid. The formation of two phases, i.e., reddish-brown and blue-green, indicates the presence of glycosides.

Steroid Test. *Liebermann-Burchard Reaction.* Dissolve the dry extract in 2.0 ml of chloroform, add 10 drops of acetic anhydride, 5 drops of concentrated sulfuric acid, and mix. A color change from red to blue-green indicates the presence of steroids.

Cyanide Test. Place 0.05 g of dry milk thistle (*Silybum marianum*) extract into a test tube, pour 10 ml of 96% alcohol over it, and shake. Add 0.25 g of zinc powder and 1.0 ml of concentrated hydrochloric acid and mix. The formation of a burgundy color indicates a positive result.

Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC) Procedure. For the analysis, silymarin and a lyophilized extract of milk thistle were used. Each was dissolved in 10 mL of 60% ethanol solution at a concentration of 0.020 g. The ethanol extract of milk thistle was then diluted 1:1 with 60% ethanol. As standard substances, 0.002 g of rutin was dissolved in 10 mL of methanol, and 0.005 g of quercetin was dissolved in 10 mL of methanol. The samples were applied to silica gel thin-layer plates. 10 μ L each of silymarin and the standard solutions were spotted, along with 30 μ L of the extract solution. The mobile phase consisted of anhydrous formic acid, acetone, and dichloromethane in a volumetric ratio of 8.5:16.5:75.

After air drying, the silica gel plates with the spotted samples were sprayed with the reagent — vanillin-sulfuric acid. This reagent was prepared by dissolving 1.0 g of vanillin in 2 mL of sulfuric acid and subsequently mixing it with 100 mL of 95% ethanol. The silica gel plates with the reagent were heated in an oven at 105–110 °C for 5 minutes. They were then examined under ultraviolet (UV) light at wavelengths of 254 nm and 365 nm [5].

Determination of Flavonolignans in Dry Extract [4]. To determine the quantity of flavonolignans, calculated as silybin, 0.02 g of precisely weighed dry extract was placed into a 25 mL volumetric flask and brought to the mark with

distilled water (Solution A). Then, 5.0 mL of Solution A was transferred to another 25 mL volumetric flask and brought to the mark with 96 % ethyl alcohol (Solution B). The optical density of Solution B was measured using a spectrophotometer at a wavelength of 289 nm in a 1.0 cm quartz cuvette. 96 % ethyl alcohol was used as the reference solution. The optical density of the standard alcoholic solution of silybin was also determined at a wavelength of 289 nm.

Preparation of Standard Silybin Solution. 20 mg of standard silybin was placed into a 100 mL volumetric flask, then 80 mL of 96 % alcohol was added, and the mixture was heated in a water bath at 70 °C-80 °C. After cooling, the solution was brought to the mark with 96 % ethanol (Standard Solution A). 1.0 mL of Standard Solution A was placed into a 25 mL volumetric flask, brought to the mark with 96 % ethanol, and mixed by shaking (Standard Solution B).

The quantity of flavonolignans (X) in the dry extract of milk thistle was calculated as a percentage (%) in terms of silybin using the following formula:

$X = \frac{D * m_0 * 100 * 25 * 25}{D_0 * m * 100 * 25 * 5};$	where D — Optical density of the test solution; D ₀ — optical density of a standard solution of silybin; m — dry extract mass, g; m ₀ — mass of silybin standard solution, g.
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Ultraviolet spectrophotometric analysis of milk thistle dry extract was compared with the standard silybin spectrum from the Photochem CAD 3.0 database and the standard silybin's absorbance in the ultraviolet range. The characteristic wavelength for flavonolignan compounds was 288±2 nm, and this absorbance was also observed in the milk thistle dry extract at a wavelength of 288 nm.

Figure 2. From left to right: silybin spectrum (288 nm) presented in the Photochem CAD 3.0 database, silybin standard (288 nm), and UV spectra of a dry extract prepared from milk thistle seeds (288 nm).

The content of flavonolignans in a dry extract of milk thistle seeds was determined by direct spectrophotometry using an ultraviolet spectrophotometer (Agilent Cary 60, UV-Vis) at a wavelength of 288 nm, which is characteristic of silybin, and calculated as silybin. The metrological characteristics of the obtained results for flavonolignan content are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Metrological characteristic of the content of flavonolignans in dry extract of milk thistle (*Silybum marianum*).

Nº	Sample mass, g	Optical density (D)	X, %	Metrological characteristics
1	0.0210	2.408	39.13	Arithmetic mean: $\bar{X} = 40.12$ Standard Deviation: $S \approx 1.163$ Standard Error (SE): 0.368 Confidence Limit: lower — 39.29 Confidence Limit: upper — 40.96
2	0.0220	2.436	37.79	
3	0.0201	2.403	40.80	
4	0.0198	2.398	41.33	
5	0.0211	2.409	38.96	
6	0.0202	2.403	40.60	
7	0.0205	2.408	40.08	
8	0.0203	2.407	40.46	
9	0.0202	2.406	40.65	
10	0.0197	2.395	41.49	

Chromatographic Study. For the chromatographic investigation of flavonolignan compounds in dry milk thistle (*Silybum marianum*) seed extract, a high-performance liquid chromatograph (HPLC) (Agilent Technologies, 1260 Infinity HPLC system) equipped with a diode array detector (DAD) was used.

Data acquisition, chromatogram processing, and absorption spectra analysis were performed using Chemstation software (Agilent Chemstation for LC 3D). A C-18 column (Zorbax Eclipse Plus C-18, rapid resolution 4.6x100 mm, 3.5 μ m) served as the stationary phase. The mobile phase consisted of a mixture of 85% phosphoric acid: methanol: distilled water in a volume ratio of 0.5:46:64, operated in isocratic mode. The flow rate of the mobile phase was 0.8 mL/min, the column temperature was 25 $^{\circ}$ C, the injection volume was 50 μ L, and the detection wavelength was 288 nm. The duration of the analysis was 35 minutes. For the study, 5.0 mg of standard silymarin and dry milk thistle seed extract were dissolved in 50 mL of the solvent prepared as the mobile phase. The solutions were then filtered through a 0.45 μ m filter (Chromafil PET 45/25), and 50 μ L of each was injected into the chromatograph column [6].

Figure 3. Liquid Chromatographic Analysis of Standard Silymarin and Dry Milk Thistle Seed Extract

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The results of the phytochemical quantitative analysis of the dry extract from milk thistle seeds are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Results of Phytochemical Quantitative Analysis

Raw material	Humidity, %	Total ash content, %	Insoluble ash in 10% hydrochloric acid, %	Common flavonolignans, %
Milk thistle seeds	3.98	1.8	0.42	40.12

High-quality phytochemical analysis of dry milk thistle seed extract was performed by preparing extracts with water, 96% ethanol, and petroleum ether. The obtained results are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Phytochemical Analysis of Milk Thistle Seeds

№	Phytochemical composition	Extractants		
		Water	Ethanol, 96 %	Petroleum ether
1	Carbohydrates			
	Benedict's Test	+	+	-
2	Proteins and amino acids			
	Biuret Test	-	+	+
3	Flavonoids			
	Alkaline Reagent Test	+	+	-
	Aluminum Chloride Test	+	+	-
	Wilson's Test	+	+	-
4	Flavonolignans			
	Cyanide Test	+	+	-
5	Tannins			
	Ferric Chloride Test	+	+	+
	Potassium Dichromate Analysis	+	+	-
6	Saponins			
	Froth Test	+	-	+
7	Alkaloids			
	Wagner's Reaction	-	+	-
8	Glycosides			
	Keller-Kiliani Reaction	+	+	-
9	Steroids			
	Libermann-Burchard Reaction	+	+	-

Thin-Layer Chromatography (TLC). In this method, flavonolignans form a yellowish-green fluorescent band, appearing in the same band as the silybin standard. Below this, a pink fluorescent band characteristic of taxifolin is formed.

Determination of Flavonolignan Content in Dry Extract. According to the European Pharmacopoeia, the standard content of flavonolignans in dry milk thistle extract is 30–65%. In our studies, the average flavonolignan content was 40.12%. High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) analysis of the dry milk thistle extract was conducted by comparing it with a silybin standard. A total of 18 substance peaks were detected during the analysis. The obtained results and information regarding the detected substances are presented in Table 5.

Table 5. Substances identified in the analysis of standard silymarin and dry milk thistle seed extract by High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC)

№	Silymarin standard	Milk thistle dry extract	Identified substances
	Rt, minute	Rt, minute	Name
1	1.278	1.205	-
2	-	1.444	-
3	-	1.563	-
4	1.847	1.870	-
5	-	2.090	-
6	-	2.402	Taxifolin
7	-	2.608	-
8	3.727	3.747	-
9	3.963	4.025	-
10	4.300	4.290	Isosilicrystine
11	-	4.676	-
12	5.672	5.697	-
13	5.900	5.930	-
14	6.826	6.859	-
15	7.812	7.845	-
16	8.851	8.769	-
17	21.060	21.038	Silibin
18	25.242	25.202	Isosilibin

The standardization indicators for dry milk thistle extract were determined through the conducted research. These indicators are presented in Table 6.

Table 6. Standardization indicators of dry milk thistle extract

Indicators	Standard *	Dry milk thistle extract
Description	A homogeneous, light yellowish-brown amorphous powder with a characteristic odor and a bitter taste.	+
Solubility	Soluble in alcohol, moderately soluble in water.	+
Establishment	Cyanide test	+
The weight that is lost during drying.	< 4.0%	3.98
pH	4.5–6.5	4.74
Total ash content	< 2.0%	1.8
Insoluble powder 10%-HCl	< 0.5%	< 0.42%
The content of flavolignans	30–65%*	40.12
*[7]		

References

1. Berdimuhamedow G. *Medicinal plants of Turkmenistan. Vol. I.* — A.: Turkmen State Publishing Service, 2010. — 89–90 s.
2. Bijak M. Silybin, a Major Bioactive Component of Milk Thistle (*Silybum marianum* L. Gaernt.)-Chemistry, Bioavailability, and Metabolism. *Molecules*. 10 November 2017, 22, 1942; www.mdpi.com/journal/molecules.
3. Durdyev T., Danatarov B., Akmuradov A. Obtaining a dry extract of milk thistle seeds using innovative methods // *Innovative Technologies of Turkmenistan. Scientific and Practical Electronic Journal*. 2023–3 (3).
4. *European pharmacopoeia 10.0. Milk thistle dry extract, refined and standardized.* P. 1538–1540.
5. Kurkin V. A., Rosikhin D. V. Standardization of Milk Thistle Syrup // *Pharmacy*, 2017; 66 (1): 19–22.
6. Kvasnicka F. et al. Analysis of the active components of silymarin // *Journal of Chromatography A*, 990 (2003) 239–245.
7. Naumenko A. G., Shevchenko A. M. Selection of a rational technology for obtaining a dry extract of the spotted milk thistle fruit // *Modern Problems of Science and Education*. 2015. No. 2–2.
8. Nikitin V. V., Geldikhanov A. M. *Determinant of plants of Turkmenistan.* — L.: Nauka, Leningrad Publishing House, 1988. — 680 p.

9. Roberto Marceddu et al. Milk Thistle (*Silybum marianum* L.) as a Novel Multipurpose Crop for Agriculture in Marginal Environments: A Review. *Agronomy* 2022, 12, 729. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy12030729>.

10. Rosikhin D. V. *Pharmacognostic study on the substantiation of the complex use of marsh marigold (*Silybum marianum* (L.) Gaertn.): thesis for the degree of Candidate of Pharmaceutical Sciences.* — Samara, 2018. — 24 p.

11. Shchekatikhina A. S., Gavrilenko N. V., Kurchenko V. P. *Assessment of the content of the isomers of the flavolignans of the marsh milk thistle in hepatoprotective preparations // Bulletin of BSU.* — Ser. 2. — 2010. — No. 2. — Pp. 73–78.

12. *State Pharmacopoeia of the Russian Federation. XIV edition. Volume IV.* Moscow, 2018.

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THEORETICAL RESEARCH ON GRAIN DISINTEGRATION BY IMPACT OF A BLADE IN A HAMMER CRUSHER

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Abstract. *In-depth theoretical research into the patterns of disintegration of grain feed components and their energetics is necessary to achieve more energy-efficient processes and equipment with new working elements. Knowing the laws of change in grain resistance to grinding depending on its various conditions (humidity, temperature, holding time under load, etc.), it is possible to select its optimal properties for obtaining a product of a given quality with minimal energy consumption. Having experimental values of the dynamic characteristics of the mechanical properties of grain at our disposal, it is possible to resolve the issue of the magnitude of the breaking speed upon impact with a blade. The objective of the study was to establish patterns of crack growth in the body of the grain and its final failure upon free impact with a blade, and to theoretically determine the magnitude of the breaking speed upon impact with a blade in a hammer mill of grain. The research methodology included the main postulates of the method of rigid-plastic analysis of grain deformations upon impact, proposed and developed by S. V. Melnikov and F. G. Plokhov. The concept of striking the grain kernel with a blade developed by U. K. Sabiev was used. The study established that microcracks existing in the grain kernel act as stress concentrators. The crack grows at a rate greater than the speed of the hammer knife blade's movement (penetration) and leads to brittle fracture of the grain kernel, reducing the energy consumption of the grinding process.*

Key words: *destructive speed; blade impact; grain; crushing; crusher.*

Introduction. Existing mechanized technologies for the production of live-stock products represent a way of organizing the operation of technical means, including for forage production [1]. The significant number of various feed materials processed by grinding in hammer mills, and accordingly the amount of energy spent on the process, make its rationalization based on the generalization and replenishment of theoretical data very relevant [2].

The need for new technologies and new working elements for grinding grains has been pointed out by a number of domestic and foreign authors [3–10]. This formulation of the issue can be explained by the emergence of new scientific directions in the grinding of grain feed, one of which is the concept of striking the grain with a blade [11], developed by Professor Sabiev U. K. The authors of the article investigated the process of grain destruction according to this concept, but with a free blade strike. The working element of the grinder is a hammer knife, capable of effectively grinding components with different mechanical and technological properties.

As is well known, the grain kernel of any crop, including barley, contains microcracks. These are small cracks that can form during grain growth, maturation, and storage. These cracks occur for various reasons, including adverse weather conditions such as sudden fluctuations in temperature and humidity, nutrient deficiencies in the soil, and so on. The actual strength of the grain kernel is primarily determined by the presence of these cracks. Acting as a characteristic stress concentrator, the crack accumulates elastic energy, which, as the crack develops, is used to fracture adjacent surfaces.

Thus, the splitting caused by the blade impact grains is happening along the cracks due to a concentrated blow, and further growth of the crack under the influence of the wedge of the hammer blade.

Such theoretical model grinding grain the material allows us to make a reasonable transition from empirical selection conditions crushing, to theoretical determination of the magnitude of the destructive speed upon impact of a blade in a hammer crusher based on from features structure of the grain.

The goal research is to establish the patterns of crack growth in the body of the grain and its final destruction during a free impact with a blade, and the theoretical determination of the magnitude of the destructive speed during impact with a blade in a hammer grain crusher.

Research materials and methods. The study was conducted using the largest, undamaged grains of the Timofey winter barley variety, with a moisture content of 11.5–13.5%; the 1,000-grain weight was 17.4–54.9 g.

The fracture of bodies upon impact with a blade is a complex process requiring study in fracture mechanics, impact dynamics, and materials science. The main study methods can be divided into experimental, theoretical, and numerical.

In this theoretical study, we will a priori assume that the barley grain is a semi-brittle material. Under successive loading of a grain with microcracks, a stress-strain state can be achieved that satisfies either the force or strain criterion. Simultaneous fulfillment of both is also possible.

In this case, the most suitable method for use in theoretical research is the rigid-plastic analysis of grain deformations upon impact, proposed by S. V. Melnikov and improved by a number of researchers.

The essence of this method is that an elastic material is considered rigid when subjected to deformation when the impact produces stresses less than plastic ($\sigma < \sigma_s$), and plastic when the stresses are greater than plastic ($\sigma \geq \sigma_s$). The study does not examine the deformation process itself, but only the residual state of the impacting body.

Research results and discussion. K. E. Voroshilov Luhansk State Agrarian University has developed a hammer-type chopper, the technical novelty of which is confirmed by Utility Model Patent RU 218136 U1, issued May 12, 2023.

During the research, a number of prototypes of this working tool were manufactured, ranging from a comb-type knife to a three-section hammer knife. The evolution of the universal grinding tool is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Evolution of the creation of a universal grinding organ:

a — root crop comb knife; *b*, *c* — non-disassemblable samples of the experimental hammer knife; *g* — single-section universal grinding element; *d* — two-section universal grinding element; *e* — three-section universal grinding element

For use in a hammer crusher, a two-section universal crushing element is used (Fig. 1, *d*).

Rigid-plastic analysis method as applied to the dynamic fracture of grain by a hammer knife. Let us assume that at the onset of impact, the grain has a velocity U . After a time interval dt , measured from the onset of impact, part of the grain begins to deform.

Rigid-plastic analysis method as applied to the dynamic fracture of grain by a hammer knife. Let us assume that at the onset of impact, the grain has a velocity

U . After a time interval dt , measured from the onset of impact, part of the grain begins to deform.

In this case, the crack propagates towards the undeformed part (rigid body) with the velocity C . The equation of motion of the rigid body of the grain can be written as follows:

$$\rho_0 X \frac{dU}{dt} = -\sigma_{vd}, \quad (1)$$

where: ρ_0 — density of the material;

X is the distance from the rear end of the grain to the elastic-plastic boundary;

σ_{vd} — stress at which grain destruction occurs.

The change in grain length during deformation will be equal to:

$$\frac{dX}{dt} = -(U + C), \quad (2)$$

From expressions (1) and (2) after some transformations we obtain:

$$\rho_0 (U + C) dU = \sigma_{vd} \frac{dX}{X}, \quad (3)$$

The grain velocity during the destruction process changes from the initial velocity V_0 to 0, and its dimensions along the impact line from a to X_1 (X_1 is the value of the remaining undeformed part).

Integrating expression (3), we find:

$$\rho_0 \frac{(U + C)^2}{2} \Big|_{V_0}^0 = \sigma_{vd} \ln X \Big|_a^{X_1}, \quad (4)$$

where:

$$\sigma_{vd} = \frac{\rho_0 (V_0^2 + 2V_0 C)}{2 \ln \frac{a}{X_1}}, \quad (5)$$

where σ_{vd} is the dynamic strength limit.

the unknown speed C based on the collision time.

Assuming the grain movement to be uniformly retarded, we find:

$$t = \frac{2(a - X_1)}{V_0}, \quad (6)$$

But during this same time, the grain is deformed at a speed of C by the amount $(a - X_1)$.

Hence,

$$\frac{2(a - X_1)}{V_0} = \frac{a - X_1}{C}, \quad (7)$$

where:

$$C = \frac{V_0}{2}, \quad (8)$$

Substituting the value of C into equation (5), we obtain the final expression for determining the dynamic tensile strength:

$$\sigma_{vd} = \frac{\rho_0 V_0^2}{\ln \frac{a}{X_1}} \left[\frac{\text{kgA}}{\text{cm}^2} \right] \quad \sigma_{vd} = 0,098 \frac{\rho_0 V_0^2}{\ln \frac{a}{X_1}} [\text{MPa}] \quad (9)$$

The ratio of dynamic destructive stresses to the corresponding static stresses can be characterized by the dynamic coefficient:

$$K_d = \frac{\sigma_{vd}}{\sigma_{dest}}, \quad (10)$$

where σ_{is} the average value of destructive stresses found during static tests [14].

If we take into account that for barley grains the static destructive stresses fluctuate within the range of $\sigma_s = 70 \pm 22 \text{ kgf/cm}^2$ then the value of the dynamic coefficient can be taken within the range of $K_d = 1.4 - 1.6$.

Thus, the peripheral speed of the hammer knife w_n , s^{-1} must not be less than the peripheral destructive speed w_{dest} , determined from formula (9) taking into account expression (10) and the distance from the drum axis to the working edge of the hammer knife.

$$w_n \geq w_{dest} = \sqrt{\frac{\sigma_{dest} K_d \ln \frac{a}{X_1}}{\rho_0}} / R, s^{-1} \quad (11)$$

where R is the distance from the drum axis to the working edge of the hammer knife, m.

Expression (11) practically does not contradict the well-known Melnikov-Plokhov expression for determining the critical rate of grain destruction.

In this case, in relation to the grain grinding process, the natural logarithm is used to describe the exponential growth of the number of destroyed parts of grains

and the decrease in the number of whole grains, taking into account the strength indicator obtained under dynamic loading conditions.

According to the average calculated value of the resistance to grain destruction by a hammer knife from equation (11), equal to 210 kg/cm², the main parameters of the force action on the cutting edges and chamfers of the knife were selected.

The analysis of the stress-strain state of a universal hammer knife was carried out in the KOMPAS-3D automated design system environment using the built-in strength analysis module ARM FEM.

The calculation algorithm consists of the following stages [1 2]: selection of material; assignment of fastenings; assignment of load; generation of finite element mesh; selection of calculation parameters; calculation; presentation of calculation results; analysis of calculation results.

Figure 2 shows a 3D model of a universal hammer knife with assigned fastenings and applied forces on the cutting edges and chamfers of the blades of flat and round plates.

A necessary component of any finite element problem is a finite element mesh. The primary purpose of a finite element mesh is to adequately approximate the geometry of the modeled object, taking into account all the geometric nuances important for the calculation.

Figure 1–3D model of a universal hammer knife.

The finite element model of the working element is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 2. Finite element model.

Mises stress; total linear displacement; yield strength safety factor; and strength safety factor.

Based on the results of the analysis, it was possible to establish the following parameter values:

- maximum equivalent stress according to von Mises 50.552811 MPa;
- maximum total linear displacement 0.022077 mm;
- minimum safety factor for fluidity 4.6486604;
- minimum safety factor 8.11033.

Conclusions. Microcracks present in the grain kernel act as stress concentrators. Crack development in the kernel occurs due to cuts made by the blade strikes. The crack grows at a rate greater than the hammer blade's penetration speed and leads to brittle fracture of the kernel, reducing the energy required for the grinding process.

When grain is crushed by impact with a blade, one can assume the existence of plastic deformation and its influence on brittle disintegration. In this case, the most suitable method is the rigid-plastic analysis of deformations of bodies under impact.

Under dynamic conditions, the resistance of the grain material to destruction and its critical destruction rate increase.

The determination of the value of the circumferential destructive speed (11) and the calculation of the energy of the grain grinding process and the design and technological parameters of grinders with a hammer knife should be carried out using the method of rigid-plastic analysis.

The peripheral speed of the hammers in existing agricultural crushers is insufficient to guarantee the destruction of all grains through a single free blow of a classic hammer, which justifies the possibility of using a hammer knife as the main working element.

An analysis of the stress-strain state of the hammer knife using the finite element method showed that the most vulnerable point is the screw connection at the junction between the first section of the flat plate and the second section of the round plate.

Therefore, when assembling a hammer knife, it is necessary to pay special attention to the strength characteristics of the clamping screw, and, if possible, to increase the reliability of the structure by using this product with increased strength.

References

1. Bryukhovetskiy A.N., Zakharov S. A. Construction of a model of a livestock facility using modern information and intelligence systems // *Bulletin of Vladimir Dahl Luhansk State University. Series Technical Sciences.* — 2025. — No. 1 (2). — P. 112–118.

2. Mezenov A. A., Grigorev N. N., Kashevarov N. I. Hammer grain crushers: classification and efficiency assessment methods. *Food production equipment and technology.* 2025. Vol. 55 No. 1. Pp. 214–225. <https://doi.org/10.21603/2074-9414-2025-1-2566>

3. Yarovoy M.N., Kornev A. S., Druzhinin R. A. Influence of the peripheral speed of hammers and the diameter of the working chamber on the effective power of a hammer crusher [Electronic resource] // *AgroEcoInfo: Electronic scientific and production journal.* — 2022 — No. 2 — Access mode: http://agroecoinfo.ru/STATYI/2022/2/st_235.pdf. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.51419/202122235>.

4. Modeling and justification of the geometric parameters of a circular knife of a universal grinding device Bryukhovetskiy A. N., Zakharov S. A., Chursin V. Yu. In the collection: *Innovative directions of development of technologies and technical means of agricultural mechanization. Proceedings of the international scientific and practical conference dedicated to the 100th anniversary of the Department of Agricultural Machinery of the Agroengineering Faculty of the Voronezh State Agrarian University named after Emperor Peter I. Ministry of Agriculture of the Russian Federation; Voronezh State Agrarian University named after Emperor Peter I.* 2015. pp. 62–67.

5. Voronin V.V., Akimenko A. V., Konoshin I. V. [et al.] Theoretical and experimental substantiation of the efficiency of using needle-shaped working elements in sieve and sieveless crushers // *Innovations in the agro-industrial complex: problems and prospects.* — 2019 — No. 4 (24). — P. 44–52.

6. Cherepkov A. V. Improvement of the grain grinding process with substantiation of the design and operating parameters of a hammer crusher: abstract of the dissertation of Cand. Sci. (Eng.): 05.20.01. — Voronezh. — 2016–152 p.

7. Trufanov V.V., Yarovoy M. N., Druzhinin R. A., Zolotarev A. M. Determination of the main indicators of the grain grinding process in an impact-centrifugal grinder // *Agro-industrial complex at the turn of the century: materials of the international scientific and practical conference.* — Part I. — Voronezh: FGBOU VO «Voronezh SAU». — 2015 — P. 182–186.

8. Thomas M, Hendriks WH, van der Poel AFB. Size distribution analysis of wheat, maize and soybeans and energy efficiency using different methods for coarse grinding. *Animal Feed Science and Technology.* 2018;240:11–21. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anifeedsci.2018.03.010>

9. Brodziak A., Król J., Nowaczek A. *Naturalne substancje inspiracje roślinnego negatywnie oddziałujące na health krów oraz jakość mleka. Żywnosc. Nauka. Technologia. Jakość. 2017;24(1):33–47. [Brodziak A, Król J, Nowaczek A. Natural substances of plant origin adversely affecting the health of cows and milk quality. Food. Science Technology. Quality. 2017; 24(1):33–47. (In Polish)] <https://doi.org/10.15193/zntj/2017/110/171>*
10. Vaculik P., Maloun J., Chládek L., Prikryl M. *Disintegration process in disc crushers. Research in Agricultural Engineering. 2013;59(3):98–104. <https://doi.org/10.17221/28/2012-RAE>*
11. Sabiev U.K., Soyunov A. S., Myalo V. V., Yatsunov A. N. *Theoretical description of the motion of a material particle in pan vibrating batchers for agricultural purposes. IOP Conf. Series: Earth and Environment. Sci. 2022;954:012067. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/954/1/012067>*
12. Ganin N. B. *Design and strength calculation in the KOMIAC-3D V13 system, 8th edition, revised and supplemented — M.: DMK Press, 2011. — 320 p.: ill.*

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INVESTIGATION OF DAMAGE TO HYDRAULIC ENGINEERING STRUCTURES IN THE STEPPE ZONE OF THE SOUTHERN URALS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF RECOMMENDATIONS FOR THEIR RECONSTRUCTION

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The aim of this study is to investigate the technical condition and systematize the most common damage to hydraulic structures in reservoirs in the steppe zone of the Southern Urals based on the results of visual inspections of hydraulic structures in the Bolshoy Yushatyr River basin. This will allow for the development of recommendations for their reconstruction. As a result of inspections of hydraulic structures (HS) at 82 reservoirs, the composition and types of HSs were determined and their technical conditions were analyzed using conventional criteria. The most common identified HS damages are systematized based on their impact on the operation of the hydraulic structures. It was found that 20% of the hydraulic structures are in unsatisfactory technical condition, and generalized repair recommendations have been developed for them.

Keywords: *reservoir; reservoir; channel pond; hydraulic structures; slopes; crest; pools; overgrowth; erosion; damage; technical condition criteria.*

Introduction. When operating hydraulic structures (HS) in the steppe zone of the Southern Urals, identifying and analyzing typical damage affecting their reliability and safety is particularly important. The region's unique natural and climatic conditions — sharp temperature fluctuations, uneven precipitation distribution, high evaporation, and pronounced weathering processes — create additional risk factors, accelerating the development of defects and complicating the operation of HS. Therefore, systematizing the most common types of damage and determining their causes is a necessary step in substantiating effective recommendations for the reconstruction of HS. This approach allows for targeted improvements in their durability, operational stability, and overall safety.

A review of literary sources revealed that a number of different problems currently exist related to the operation of HS. The technical condition of HS is constantly deteriorating, with some structures in a state of disrepair and unfit for operation. In most cases, this is due to the abandonment of structures, the lack of owners of operating services, and the lack of funding for emergency restoration and reconstruction work [1–2].

In the Bolshoy Yushatyr River basin, a typical steppe stream, the issue of maintaining the reliability of hydraulic structures and promptly detecting damage during operation is particularly pressing given their importance for agricultural water supply, irrigation, and flow regulation. It is also important to consider that a significant portion of hydraulic structures are operated without complete design documentation and proper technical supervision, which significantly increases the risk of emergency situations.

Most of the reservoirs in the Bolshoy Yushatyr River basin are small and large ponds. They are typically under the jurisdiction of municipalities, and the technical condition of hydraulic structures is the basis for making rational decisions on repair work at the municipal level with a large number of hydraulic structures. At the federal level, reliable information on the condition and safety of individual hydraulic structures (HS) and hydroelectric power plants as a whole is also needed. This information will allow for the allocation of limited resources to repairing the most hazardous HS [3–7].

Surveying HS of hydroelectric power plants in the steppe landscape zone requires consideration of specific environmental factors, including the intensive development of aquatic and coastal vegetation, soil filtration, erosion, and suffusion, as well as the specifics of the formation and distribution of water loads on structures in a sharply continental climate (spring-summer floods, low-water periods). All of this necessitates a survey of the technical condition of HS and their HS, and the identification of the most common damages.

The aim of this work is to study the technical condition and systematize the most common damages to HS of reservoirs in the steppe zone of the Southern Urals based on the results of visual surveys of HS in the Bolshoy Yushatyr River basin, which will allow for the development of recommendations for their reconstruction. To achieve this goal, the following tasks were completed:

- identifying the soil-morphometric and hydrological conditions of the Bolshoy Yushatyr River basin;
- establishing a list of water bodies in the Bolshoy Yushatyr River basin for visual inspection of their hydraulic structures;
- summarizing and systematizing the results of the visual inspection of the hydraulic structures of the water bodies in the Bolshoy Yushatyr River basin.

Materials and Methods. The Bolshoy Yushatyr River drainage basin is located in the steppe zone of the southern Republic of Bashkortostan and the northern Orenburg Region, in the northern part of Obshchy Syrt. The predominant terrain is rolling hills, heavily dissected by large ridges and valleys. The average elevation is 250–300 m. Islands of oak, linden, birch, and other deciduous forests occupy approximately 10% of the territory.

The predominant soils are common and southern chernozems; meadow soils are found in river valleys, and solonchaks are found on watersheds in the southern part. The complex, rugged topography of Obshchy Syrt, under conditions of insufficient and irregular moisture, promotes destructive erosion processes and increased soil carbonate content. Long-term plowing and water erosion have led to significant degradation of more than 44% of the southern chernozems [8]. The Bolshoy Yushatyr River is a left tributary of the Salmysh River. The river's mouth is located 55 km along the left bank of the Salmysh River. The river is 92 km long. The catchment area is 3.4 thousand square meters.

According to the State Water Register of Russia, the river belongs to the Ural Basin District, with water management section 12.01.00.007 (the Sakmara River from the confluence of the Bolshoy Ik River to its mouth). The river basin is the Ural Mountains (the Russian part of the basin). The object code in the State Water Register is 12010000712112200006831 [9].

The Bolshoy Yushatyr River has 17 tributaries, including 8 first-order tributaries, 7 second-order tributaries, and 2 third-order tributaries. There are 10 left tributaries of the river, 7 right tributaries. The longest tributary is the Kuyanysh River (71 km), the largest drainage area is the M. Kuyurgaz River drainage area (360 km²). The river lengths vary from 10.0 km to 71.0 km, and the drainage areas — from 30 km² to 666 km² [10].

The largest reservoirs in the basin are: Aksarovskoye (Yushatyrskoye) Reservoir on the B. Yushatyr River with a water surface area of 8,800 thousand m² and a volume of 49,000 thousand m³, Otradnoye Reservoir on the Kuyanysh River with a water surface area of 1,680 thousand m² and a volume of 9,850 thousand m³.

The reservoirs of the Bolshoy Yushatyr River basin are located in the Tyulgansky (20), Oktyabrsky (19), and Sharlyksky (5) districts of the Orenburg Region and in the Kuyurgazinsky District of the Republic of Bashkortostan (75).

Prior to the commencement of fieldwork for a visual inspection of the reservoir's hydraulic structures, a survey route was developed. Upon arrival at the survey area, the pre-planned route was adjusted to take into account local features, field and dirt roads, the presence of bridges and fords, weather conditions, etc.

The visual surveys included: inspection of the hydraulic structures and their hydraulic structures with the preparation of survey reports; establishing the hydraulic connection of the reservoir with other water bodies; photographing the

structural elements of the hydraulic structures and the general appearance of the reservoir; and recording the coordinates of the hydraulic structures and reservoirs using a GPS navigator.

During the inspection of the hydraulic structures and their hydraulic structures, any damage was recorded in the survey reports. The survey reports included information on the reservoir's location in free format, the hydroelectric complex's geographic coordinates, survey dates, information on the hydraulic structures and hydraulic connections to other surface water bodies, photographs of the reservoirs, hydroelectric complexes, and their hydraulic structures, the types of structural components of the hydraulic structures, and their technical conditions. Eighty-two survey reports for the hydroelectric complexes were prepared.

Hydraulic connections were established visually, while being verified against Yandex Maps (hybrid type). The presence or absence of hydraulic connections was recorded in survey reports. Permanent hydraulic connections were present in 67% of surveyed water bodies, partial (during spring and summer floods) in 8%, and absent in 25% of surveyed water bodies.

Results and discussion. A comprehensive analysis was conducted based on the compiled survey reports:

a) The types of water bodies and the composition of the hydraulic structures of the hydroelectric power plants were determined:

— Of the surveyed water bodies, 72% are channel ponds, 11% are reservoirs, 9% are filling ponds, and 7% are flooded quarries;

— 84% of the hydroelectric power plants have dams, 87% have spillways, 28% have outlets, 23% have ice protection structures, and 7% have emergency canals;

b) The main design features of the hydraulic structures (spillway, outlet, ice protection) and dam structural elements (crest, upstream and downstream slopes) of the hydroelectric power plants were identified:

— All dams, except one, are earthfill dams, one is a rock-and-earth dam (location No. 46 — Quarry on the Sandin River);

— The crest of 24% of the dams is impassable, while that of 76% is passable, 19% of which are occupied by a dirt road. Crest materials: soil (67%), crushed stone (11%), asphalt, sand and gravel mix, and slag (22%);

— The upstream slope of 77% of the dams is reinforced with grass seeding, while that of 6% is reinforced with rock fill and reinforced concrete slabs. In isolated cases, shoring with tires, concrete blocks, and slag backfill is used. In 10% of cases, there was no shoring;

— Downstream slope shoring in 87% of dams was achieved by grass seeding, in 6% by riprap and crushed stone, and in 7% of cases by no shoring at all;

— 87% of hydraulic structures have spillways: bucket-type (31%), pipe-type (horizontal, vertical, overflow) (26%), bucketless (24%), shaft and siphon-type

(7%), bell-shaped wall, open flume, stopcock (7%), and others (5%). Downstream energy absorption is provided by pipes (77%), stilling walls, wells, flumes with spillways, and cantilevers (23%);

— 28% of hydraulic structures have tubular outlets, while the rest lack them or are not visible. They are primarily used for water discharge and technical needs; — 23% of hydraulic structures have ice protection devices, primarily in the form of piles (reinforced concrete or metal) and metal pipes with guards, while the rest lack them;

c) The technical condition of hydraulic structures (spillways, outlets, ice protection, and, separately, dams based on their structural elements: crest, upstream and downstream slopes) of hydraulic structures was determined. Since the surveys were only visual, conditional criteria were developed to assess their technical condition:

— Normal (structure or element is functional, no visible damage to the structure);

— Satisfactory (structure or element is functional, but there is damage that does not affect its operation);

— Unsatisfactory (structure or element is not functional, there is damage that affects its operation).

The developed criteria were used to determine the number of hydraulic structures and dam structural elements. The analysis showed that, on average, in terms of structural elements of the dams, most dams are in satisfactory condition (68%), while 23% are in unsatisfactory condition. The greatest damage affecting dam operation is observed along the dam crest (30%).

On average, for the hydraulic structures, most hydraulic facilities are in satisfactory condition (71%), while 20% are in unsatisfactory condition. The greatest damage affecting the operation of the hydraulic structures was found in dams (an average of 23%).

d) The most common damage to the structural elements of dams and hydraulic structures of hydraulic structures was identified.

Of all the hydraulic structures in the Bolshoy Yushatyr River basin, four have all hydraulic structures in the “normal” category: the Otradnoye Reservoir on the Kuyanysh River (according to the operation service), the Yushatyr Reservoir on the B. Yushatyr River (according to the operation service), and the pond on the river. Uray (based on survey results), pond on the Kutuy River (based on survey results). Various damages were detected at the remaining hydraulic structures, including the most common ones.

The most common damage that does not affect the operation of hydraulic structures is overgrowth by grass, shrubs, trees, and reeds. The most common damage that does affect the operation of the structure is: partial or complete erosion of the dam crest and slopes, dam crest breaches, and slope damage by livestock; overgrowth of the spillway and outlet with grass, shrubs, and trees significantly affecting

the transit flow of water; destruction of the spillway section in the downstream (erosion funnel, collapsed outlet channel, collapsed outlet head, severe erosion near the pipe); destruction of the spillway section on the upstream side (gate inoperable, trees and debris piled at the inlet, non-functioning stopcocks); erosion of soil and rock fill at the outlet of the pipe outlet; damage to the protective ice protection fencing. Many ponds are abandoned, although they are formally under the jurisdiction of local municipalities. Some reservoirs are leased to local entrepreneurs and used for fish farming, but according to their contracts, they are not responsible for the technical condition of the hydraulic structures. Almost all hydraulic structures, with the exception of large reservoirs, lack operational services and do not conduct visual inspections, much less scheduled comprehensive monitoring of the technical condition of the hydraulic structures.

Conclusions. Using a survey of 82 hydraulic structures in the Bolshoy Yushaty River basin, we were able to determine their overall condition and identify the most problematic structures. The use of conditional assessment criteria allowed us to classify the hydraulic structures into three categories—“normal,” “satisfactory,” and “unsatisfactory,” enabling us to plan repairs and prioritize reconstruction.

It was determined that approximately 20% of the structures are in unsatisfactory condition and require urgent repairs, with the main damage concentrated on the dam crest (30%) and its upstream slope (23%). Systematization of the most common defects affecting the operation of hydraulic structures allows us to compile a list of necessary repair measures and develop standard solutions with estimated costs.

Studies of damage to hydraulic structures in the steppe zone of the Southern Urals have demonstrated the importance of developing recommendations for reconstructing dam crests, slopes, and culvert components, along with estimated cost estimates, to ensure effective financial planning and maintain hydraulic structures in proper technical condition.

REFERENCES

1. *Shirobokova O. E. Surveys of the technical condition of hydraulic structures in the Bryansk region / O. E. Shirobokova // Problems of energy supply, automation, informatization and nature management in the agro-industrial complex: Collection of materials of the international scientific and technical conference, Bryansk, May 16–17, 2024. Bryansk: BGAU, 2024. Pp. 161–164. — EDN HEFGIH.*

2. *Mikhailov E. D. Surveys and Problems of Operation of Hydraulic Structures of Water Management / E. D. Mikhailov // Scientific Journal of the Russian Research Institute of Land Reclamation Problems. 2011. No. 4 (4). P. 12. — EDN OKJFBP.*

3. Gritsan V. V. *Technical condition of the surveyed hydraulic structures in the Moscow region and classification features of their reservoirs // Nature management. 2021, No. 3, pp. 69–79. <https://doi.org/10.26897/1997-6011-2021-3-69-79>*

4. Volkov, V. I. *Analysis of the condition of hydraulic structures in the Chekhov district of the Moscow region / V. I. Volkov, G. M. Kaganov, P. V. Belousov // Nature management. 2010. No. 5, pp. 30–36. RSAU-MTAA CSL Local Network*

5. Chernykh, O. N. *Safety problems of the lower pools of Moscow ponds / O. N. Chernykh, V. I. Volkov // Nature management. 2017. No. 1, pp. 47–54. EDN: YRBSRH*

6. *State Water Register: [archived October 15, 2013] / Ministry of Natural Resources of the Russian Federation. 2009. March 29.*

7. Khazipova A., Chafizov A., Komissarov A., Mustafin R., Zubairov R. *Choice of Melioration Facies Regimes Using Catenary-facies Models of Watersheds of the Forest-steppe Zone of the Republic of Bashkortostan / Asian Journal of Water, Environment and Pollution, vol. 17, no. 1, pp. 19–26, 2020.*

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FEATURES OF PROCESSING COMPLEX THERMOPLASTICS FROM MULTILAYER STRUCTURES

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The article discusses the features of processing complex thermoplastics consisting of multilayer structures. The main problems of processing multilayer materials, as well as their composition, are discussed. The features of the destruction of multilayer products, methods and methods of their grinding are analyzed. The importance of separation technologies and restoration of material properties for effective reuse is emphasized. The article also discusses approaches and the most effective equipment used for processing multilayer structures.

Keywords: *complex thermoplastics, polymer utilization, multilayer structures, destruction of layered products.*

The use of complex thermoplastics is actively growing in various industries, from packaging to complex products. However, a large amount of polymer waste creates environmental problems, since most plastic products end up in landfills or in natural reservoirs, which negatively affects the environment. Approximately 2 million tons of polymer waste are disposed of annually in Russia, while only about 10–15% of it is recycled. The remaining waste is usually sent for burial or incineration, which increases the burden on the environment and contributes to the loss of resources. Polymer recycling is an important step in reducing the environmental footprint, allowing the reuse of materials, reducing waste and reducing the cost of producing new plastics.[1]

The processing of complex thermoplastics from multilayer structures is one of the most urgent and at the same time technically challenging tasks in modern mechanical engineering, the chemical industry and the field of environmental safety.

Multilayer materials are composites in which layers of various thermoplastics are interconnected to achieve certain performance characteristics, such as

increased strength, barrier properties, or environmental resistance. Multilayer films are one of the most striking examples of complex thermoplastics.

These materials consist of several layers of polymer or polymer composite materials combined into a single structure to achieve the required performance characteristics. Due to their versatility and versatility, such films are widely used in packaging, electronics, construction and other industries. This material usually consists of the following components:

1. Polyolefins are the most common base materials due to their strength, flexibility, and accessibility. For example, the bottom layer is often made of polyethylene, which provides barrier properties and protection from moisture.

2. Barrier layers are made of materials such as polyamide, polychloride fluoroethylene, or special metallized films that prevent the penetration of gases, oxygen, odors, and moisture.

3. Protective and decorative layers — made of PVC or other polymers, which give the film an aesthetic appearance and resistance to mechanical damage.

4. Adaptive and functional layers — include layers with UV resistance, heat-resistant or electrically conductive components.

A feature of such structures is the presence of interlayer bonds, sometimes using adhesives, lignin or polymer binders. These compounds make the mechanical separation of complex multilayer materials difficult, and processing has problems separating individual components without degrading them (Fig. 1) [2].

Fig. 1. Granulate obtained during the recycling of polymer waste [2]

Powerful, specially adapted machines and tools are used for crushing and processing complex thermoplastics, especially multilayer films.

The most effective technological method today is mechanical processing — this is the most common approach, including:

1. pre-crushing of waste to a fraction of 5–20 mm;
2. air or water separation for separation of heavy inclusions (metal, minerals);
3. extrusion with compatibilizers, additives that improve adhesion between incompatible polymers (for example, maleated polyethylene for PE/PP mixtures).

The main purpose of grinding is to effectively break down the structure of a material and prepare it for further processing or disposal, without preserving

the original integrity of multi-layered systems. This can be achieved using mills and granulators, which effectively convert leftovers into fine granules or powder, making them suitable for further processing or disposal.

Fig. 2. The scheme a knife mill used for processing thermoplastics:
 1 — body; 2 — drive shaft; 3 — lid; 4, 12 — cheeks; 5 — grid; 6,8— fixing screws; 7 — fixed knife; 9 — hopper; 10 — movable knife; 11 — rotor

Other types of mills can also be used, depending on the type of material being processed and the desired outcome:

1. Disc shredders use toothed discs with sharp edges, rotating at high speed, and are designed for pre-machining multilayer films and hard dense plastics. The grinding level can be adjusted by changing the speed of the discs and the distance between them, which allows for the production of both large and small particles [3]. These devices are well suited for processing materials with a dense structure and they do not require prior preparation for processing.

2. Knife shredders based (Fig. 2) on the centrifugal motion of the rotor with knives create impact and grinding action and are ideal for fast and uniform shredding of a variety of plastic materials such as PE, PP, PVC, as well as plastic waste from packaging and other easily recyclable materials. They are effective when fast grinding is required with different structures and densities.

3. Hammer grinders (Fig. 3) use pivotally suspended steel hammers that collide with the material and grooved side plates, facilitating crushing on the fly under strong impact. They are often used to break down hard, complex plastics, such as multilayer films, reinforced and composite materials, and to grind dense structures and reinforcements into ultra-fine particles.

Thus, for multilayer films and dense hard plastics, it is most effective to use disc or hammer shredders, which provide simultaneous preparation and shredding of even the heaviest structures. Light and medium-sized plastic waste is better crushed by knife machines due to fast and uniform grinding [4]. For complex, multi-layered materials, hammer devices that can destroy even the heaviest structures will be the best choice. When processing various types of waste, it is possible to use combined solutions to ensure optimal grinding levels and process efficiency.

Fig. 3. Diagram of a hammer mill used for processing thermoplastics:
1 — complete mill body; 2 — rotor in boron; 3 — thrust bearing; 4 — support bearing; 5 — drive; 6 — coupling; 7 — separator

The mechanical method of processing multilayer thermoplastics demonstrates high economic efficiency due to minimal capital expenditures on equipment — basic units such as crushers and mills are significantly cheaper than the equipment required for chemical or combined processing methods of multilayer thermoplastics.

In addition, mechanical processing provides significant energy savings, with energy consumption being 3–5 times lower than during primary polymerization.

An important advantage is the scalability of the solution — the method can be successfully implemented in small and medium-sized enterprises without requiring the creation of complex supporting infrastructure. Of particular value is the technology's ability to preserve the molecular weight of the polymer: unlike chemical degradation, mechanical processing minimizes the degradation of molecular chains, which is critical for maintaining the strength characteristics of the processed material [5]. The flexibility of using recycled materials also deserves attention — the pellets obtained as a result of processing are successfully used in compounds for the production of non-food packaging, building materials and various technical products.

From an environmental point of view, this method contributes to a noticeable reduction in the negative impact on the environment: the volume of waste sent to landfill is reduced, as well as CO₂ emissions are reduced — according to data from the life cycle analysis (LCA), they are 40–60% lower compared to the production of primary polymer.

The specificity of multilayer thermoplastics, characterized by a complex composite structure, necessitates the use of specialized technological solutions at the stage of primary grinding. Effective processing of complex polymer materials requires the use of equipment that not only crushes the material, but also controls the breaking of laminar bonds and fiber inclusions to produce a homogeneous raw material. Therefore, the optimization of methods and the selection of adequate equipment for crushing complex composites is a fundamental task in the processing chain. Solving this problem allows not only to increase the economic efficiency of processing, but also to significantly expand the raw material base of secondary polymers, which corresponds to the strategic goals of developing resource-saving closed-cycle technologies.

List of literature

1. Kryzhanovsky V. K., Burlov V. V., Panimatchenko A. D., Kryzhanovskaya Yu. V. *Technical properties of polymer materials*. St. Petersburg: Profession, 2003. 248 p. 143–145.
2. Kuleznev V. N., Shershnev V. A. *Chemistry and physics of polymers*. Moscow: KolosS, 2007. 320 p. 211–214.
3. Morozov I. A. *Technological equipment for processing thermoplastics // Modern technologies*. 2020. No. 1. pp. 22–28.
4. Osovskaya I. I., Novikova A. A. *Thermoplastics. The latest advances in polymer technology and processing. Cases and tests: a textbook /SPB.* — 2019–134 p. 21–22.
5. Shevchenko N. D. *Investments in plastics processing: economics and opportunities // The economics of recycling.* — 2022. — No. 4. — pp. 36–41.

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ANALYSIS OF METHODS FOR STRENGTHENING WORKING ROLLS TO INCREASE THEIR RESOURCE IN THE PRODUCTION OF DAMPING BANDS

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The article discusses the complex problem of increasing the hardness and strength of metal parts in mechanical engineering, as a critical factor in ensuring the reliability and durability of manufactured products, using the example of working rollers in the production of damper belts. The article analyzes traditional and modern methods of hardening and identifies their features and limitations in various production environments. Each hardening method is examined in detail, including key technological parameters such as temperature regimes, time characteristics, depth of the hardened layer, and quantitative measures of increased hardness and fatigue strength. It has been established that the choice of a rational method depends on a combination of factors: the composition of the part material, geometric characteristics, required mechanical properties, production capabilities, and economic feasibility. The presented review of hardening methods allows us to determine the most effective technological approach for solving specific production tasks related to improving the reliability and wear resistance of parts based on objective data.

Keywords: *part hardening, hardness, strength, annealing, normalization, hardening, tempering, cementation, ball rolling, surface layer, martensite, austenite, working rollers, damping belts.*

Part hardening is one of the key processes in mechanical engineering, aimed at increasing the hardness, strength, and wear resistance of the surface and bulk layers of metal products. In the context of constantly growing requirements for the reliability and durability of mechanisms and equipment, the use of modern hardening methods becomes a necessary condition for creating competitive products [1]. Hardening is a process that uses various physical, chemical, and mechanical methods to enhance the mechanical properties of metal, such as hardness,

resistance to abrasive wear, fatigue strength, and more. The essence of the process is to change the crystal structure of the metal and form hardened layers with altered physical and mechanical characteristics.

The problem of hardening becomes relevant in the production of damper rings made from a damper tape (Fig. 1) [2]. The working rollers used to form the profile of the tape are subjected to intensive abrasive wear and contact loads, which leads to their rapid failure and a decrease in productivity. This requires careful analysis and selection of the most effective method of hardening the working rollers, which can significantly extend the service life of the tool and improve the reliability of the produced damper rings. This involves the development of a combined approach or the creation of a fundamentally new method for increasing the hardness and durability of the working tools.

Fig. 1. Types of damping tapes

There are many methods for hardening parts, each with its own characteristics, advantages, and limitations. These methods can be broadly categorized into several main groups: thermal, mechanical, chemical-thermal, thermomechanical, and modern high-tech methods such as electrospark and laser hardening. The choice of the most suitable hardening method depends on factors such as the material of the part, the desired depth of the hardened layer, the desired hardness level, the geometry of the part, the manufacturing capabilities of the facility, and economic considerations [3, 4].

The thermal method (Fig. 2) includes a set of operations aimed at changing the microstructure and improving the strength characteristics of products. The main stages of the process include annealing, normalizing treatment, hardening, and relaxation tempering. The combined use of these operations provides a comprehensive improvement in the performance parameters of metal parts [3].

Annealing is a process that involves heating the product to a temperature range of 770–900 °C. The product is held in the furnace for 1–4 hours, and then cooled simultaneously with the furnace. This process transforms the large-crystalline structure into a fine-crystalline form. The main purpose of annealing is to eliminate residual stresses that may have been caused by casting, forging, stamping, rolling, welding, or straightening operations [5, 6].

Fig. 2. Thermal method of part hardening

Normalization is a technique that involves heating the product to an annealing temperature and holding it for 1–2 hours, followed by natural cooling in air to room temperature. This process is used to improve the crystal structure and enhance the mechanical properties of the material.

Tempering is carried out at temperatures of 750–900 °C and is used for steel alloys containing at least 0.5% carbon. For lower carbon content, the tempering effect is insignificant. This operation gives the material high hardness and strength characteristics [6].

Vacation is a secondary heating of the tempered product in the temperature range of 150–600 °C. The duration of the tempering process varies from 5–10 minutes to 15 hours, depending on the desired final parameters. After aging, cooling is performed. This step helps to reduce stress during hardening, changes the crystal structure, and increases the material's ductility.

Induction hardening with high-frequency currents is a local method of surface hardening.

When using high-frequency electromagnetic effects, the part is placed in an inductor whose geometry corresponds to the profile of the hardened area. The inductor creates an alternating magnetic field by passing an alternating electric current with a frequency of 2500–5000 Hz. The surface is heated to the solidification temperature (750–900 °C) for 2–10 seconds, then the power is turned off and a cooling liquid is applied. For example, the depth of the solidification zone on crankshafts is 4–7 millimeters [7].

Quenching in electrolytes. The technology is carried out by passing a direct electric current with a voltage of 220 V through the product, which serves as a cathode immersed in a salt solution (sodium carbonate). The material is heated

to 250–450 °C. This approach allows to increase the resistance to mechanical wear by 2–5 times and more.

Cold treatment — the technology consists in cooling parts to temperatures –80 °C and below, followed by heating to room temperature. Under such temperature influence, additional phase transformations of residual austenite into hard martensite occur, which leads to an increase in the hardness and wear resistance of parts. To reduce internal stresses after cold treatment, parts are subjected to hardening. Immediately after hardening, parts are treated with cold. Liquid nitrogen is used as a refrigerant.

Combined methods of hardening [7].

Thermomechanical processing. This approach combines two complementary operations: deforming the material in combination with subsequent heat treatment, which provides a synergistic effect in improving the mechanical properties of the product. Thermochemical (Fig. 3, a) — this method includes: cementation (carbonization); cyaniding (carbon and nitrogen saturation); nitriding (nitrogen saturation); alitizing (aluminum saturation); siliciding (silicon saturation); boriding (boron saturation); oxidation (blackening), etc.

Fig. 3. Thermomechanical method of part hardening (a); metal cementation (b)

Cementing (Fig. 3, b). The process involves an artificial increase in the carbon concentration in the surface zone of low-carbon steel alloys (initial content of 0.1–0.3%). The diffusion depth is 1–3 millimeters, while the inner layers retain a low carbon content. After achieving a carbon saturation level of 0.7–1.1%, the part is subjected to hardening [7, 8].

Cyaniding. The technology is based on the simultaneous saturation of the surface zone with carbon and nitrogen at 820–870 °C by exposure to molten salt compositions with cyanide components. The depth of diffusion penetration is about 0.25 millimeters, and the achieved hardness is 640–780 Brinell units.

Nitriding (Fig. 4) is carried out by saturating the surface layer with nitrogen at temperatures ranging from 480 °C to 650 °C. Aluminizing is a method that involves the diffusion of aluminum into the surface layers of steel material. Siliconizing is performed at temperatures ranging from 1100 °C to 1200 °C to enhance corrosion resistance. Boriding is a process that involves the saturation of steel with boron to increase hardness and wear resistance.

Fig. 4. Nitriding of parts

Oxidation is the process of saturation of the surface with oxygen (chemical or thermal) to prevent corrosion damage. It is carried out in baths with solutions of sodium hydroxide, sodium nitrate and nitrite-nitrate salt peter at a temperature of 130–145 °C for 1–2 hours. A protective layer of black oxide 1–2.5 microns thick is formed on the surface [7].

Thermodiffusion hardening. The methodology is based on the use of active energy compositions in the form of paste-like materials that are applied to the surface and ignited. When the paste burns, the part is heated to 600–800 °C, and the alloying elements from the paste composition diffuse into the upper layers of the metal. After 2–3 minutes, the charred part is immersed in water for cooling. The energy base of the composition includes mixtures of oxygen-containing substances and metal powders (aluminum, magnesium, calcium, and other metals).

Mechanical surface hardening methods (Fig. 5) involve the purposeful disruption of the crystalline order of a metal structure through mechanical impact.

The physical mechanism of mechanical surface hardening is based on the fact that, under the influence of pressure from a solid metal tool, microscopic protrusions on the processed surface undergo plastic deformation, the micro-roughness of the surface is reduced, and the surface layer of the metal is hardened. The main mechanical methods include: rolling with a ball or roller; broaching; shot blasting; diamond hardening.

Rolling with a ball or roller. Lathe equipment is used for processing cylindrical surfaces, and planing machines are used for processing flat surfaces. Tool elements are made of high-strength tool alloys. This treatment increases hardness by 40–50% and fatigue strength by 80–100% [8].

Figure 5. Schemes of types of mechanical hardening of parts: running-in of surfaces (a, b); rolling out surfaces (c, d)

Broaching is used to improve the accuracy and quality of internal holes. The process involves passing a special calibration ring or spherical element through the hole in the product. In the case of shot blasting, steel shot is used, which provides better results compared to cast iron alternatives. The resulting hardened layer reaches a thickness of 1.5 mm, increasing the hardness by 20–60% and the fatigue strength by 40–90%. Diamond polishing is performed using a diamond tool with a rounded working surface geometry. The tool, fixed in the holder with a spring tension, is pressed against the surface to harden it.

Electrophysical methods of modern hardening [8].

The electrospark method is based on the pulsed action of a directed high-intensity electric discharge. An electric spark occurs between a hard-alloy electrode (for example, made of stellite material) and the workpiece under the influence of a pulsed electric current. The material from the anode electrode is transferred to the cathode part, resulting in surface hardening.

Electromechanical hardening is used to form a hardened layer up to 0.2–0.3 mm thick, which increases the wear resistance by up to 11 times and the fatigue strength by 2–6 times. The process involves applying an electric current of 350–1300 A at a voltage of 2–6 V to the area where the tool contacts the parts. The tool is electrically isolated from the machine equipment. Due to the small size of the contact surface, there is significant electrical resistance, which generates thermal

energy that heats the contact surface to the hardening temperature in a fraction of a second. The subsequent rapid dissipation of heat into the depth of the part ensures cooling of the surface layer. As a result, a combined effect of surface hardening to a depth of 0.2–0.3 mm and simultaneous mechanical embrittlement is achieved, significantly increasing the wear resistance and fatigue strength.

Laser hardening (Fig. 6) is a method that uses laser systems (optical quantum generators) with an output power of 0.8–5 kW of electromagnetic radiation. When this radiation is focused on the surface being treated, it concentrates energy with an extremely high density.

Fig. 6. Laser hardening of parts

Laser radiation when exposed to a metal surface is partially reflected, and the remaining part of the energy flow penetrates to a depth up to 10^6 - 10^7 m. The high intensity of laser radiation allows you to achieve extremely high temperatures on the processed surface in fractions of a second. initiation of local curing of a thin layer. This initiates the local hardening of a thin near-surface layer of metal, which provides high technical characteristics of the processed areas [9].

Conclusions.

1. Based on the analysis of traditional and high-tech methods of hardening, it has been established that the most promising approaches to hardening of working rollers are approaches based on local high-energy surface treatment, which provide the formation of hardened layers of increased hardness with minimal thermal deformations.

2. The expediency of developing new specialized technological schemes combining elements of thermal, mechanical and high-tech processing specifically for working rolls has been established. This opens up the prospect of creating innovative solutions that allow to maximize the resource and reliability of both the rollers themselves and the damper belts made with their help.

Literature

1. Natapov B. S. *Heat treatment of metals: textbook. allowance* / B. S. Natapov. M.: Mechanical Engineering, 1980. 320 p.
2. Lozovaya S. Y. *Increasing the wear resistance of the guide rollers of the installation for the manufacture of a damper belt* / S. Y. Lozovaya, A. N. Afonin, M. S. Ry-sikov *Modern High-Tech Technologies*. — 2023. — No. 11. — Pp. 45–51; URL: <https://top-technologies.ru/ru/article/view?id=39819> (accessed on 07.12.2023), special. 02.05.05. VAK, K2.
3. Lyakhovich L. S. *Chemical and thermal treatment of metals and alloys: hand-book* / L. S. Lyakhovich. M.: Metallurgy, 1981. 512 p.
4. Shmykov A. A. *Handbook of Thermist* / A. A. Shmykov. M.: Mechanical Engi-neering, 1981. 456 p.
5. Glushchenkov V. A. *Hardening of Metals in Pressure Treatment: Electronic Resource. Textbook.* / V. A. Glushchenkov. Samara: Samara State Aerospace Uni-versity, 2015. 150 p.
6. Korostelev V. F. *Surface and volume hardening of alloys: a monograph* / V. F. Korostelev. Moscow: Infra-Engineering, 2021. 160 p.
7. *The choice of materials and methods of hardening machine parts: textbook. manual* / A. V. Yeltsov [et al.]. Tambov: TSTU, 2013. 120 p.
8. Naizabekov A. *Technologies of physico-mechanical hardening of metals and alloys: a monograph* / A. Naizabekov. Almaty: KazNITU, 2019. 250 p.
9. GOST 33439–2015. *Metal products made of ferrous metals and alloys based on iron-nickel and nickel. Terms and definitions for heat treatment.* Moscow: Stan-dartinform, 2016. 28 p.

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COMPARISON OF THE ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF PROCESSING DIFFERENT TYPES OF THERMOPLASTICS

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This article examines the analysis of the economic efficiency of processing various types of thermoplastics, which is a key task for the development of a circular economy and rational management of polymer waste. In the context of growing environmental regulation and economic instability, investors and operating enterprises need clear, quantifiably sound data to make decisions about choosing the most profitable raw material niches and optimizing technological processes. Existing research often focuses on the technical aspects of recycling, ignoring comparative economic analysis, which directly determines the investment attractiveness and sustainability of a recycling business. The article proposes a practical model for comparing the main commercially significant streams of secondary thermoplastics: polyethylene terephthalate, polyethylene, and polypropylene. The results of the work make it possible not only to rank areas by profitability, but also to identify shortcomings in the cost structure, which helps to reduce the cost of the final product and increase the competitiveness of domestic processors against the background of imports of primary raw materials.

Keywords: *plastic recycling, economic efficiency, profitability, comparative analysis, thermoplastics, polyethylene, polypropylene, cost of processing, polymer waste.*

The main purpose of the comparative analysis is to determine which of the mass — produced types of recycled thermoplastics is the most economically attractive for a potential investor or an operating enterprise under standard market conditions. In this paper, the most common method is considered, which includes the stages of sorting, crushing, washing, agglomeration or extrusion and granulation.

For the sake of clarity of comparison, three key material flows representing different market segments were selected.:

1. Polyethylene terephthalate (Fig. 1): represents an organized collection market with relatively clear logistics and high requirements for the purity of raw materials, has a number of advantages that make this material widely used for the production of packaging, textiles, fibers, technical parts and household products [1].

Fig. 1. Polyethylene terephthalate products (bottles, containers, cans)

2. Polyethylene (Fig. 2): This is a difficult stream to process due to its low bulk density and the presence of complex adhesive contaminants. It is used for the production of various products in various fields: packaging, household appliances, medicine and automotive industry. The material is used due to its properties: lightness, chemical resistance, and dielectric properties.

Fig. 2. Polyethylene products (films, bags, wrappers)

3. Polypropylene: represents a mixed stream with a wide raw material base, including packaging, automotive components and household products, it also has high mechanical properties, chemical resistance, thermal stability, and environmental friendliness [2].

In order for the comparison to be the most objective, the analysis is based on a simplified but representative model for calculating the cost of one kilogram of commodity regranulate [3]. Three fundamental cost items common to any production were identified:

1. Raw materials (variable costs): a key item that determines up to ninety percent of the cost. The average market prices for secondary raw materials — flex, agglomerate or crushed — in the first quarter of 2024 were used for the calculation. Prices are taken from the open data of the largest commodity exchanges and aggregators of raw materials.

2. Electricity (variable and conditionally fixed costs): the second most important article reflecting the energy intensity of the process. The specific energy consumption is assumed to be zero point five kilowatt-hours per kilogram of finished products. This value is the average value for a modern line that includes a shredder, a sink, an agglomerator and an extruder granulator. The tariff is set at 6p/kW, which corresponds to the average industrial tariff in a number of regions of the Russian Federation.[4]

3. Depreciation of equipment (fixed costs): an article that allows you to take into account capital investments. The notional cost of a fully finished production process line with a capacity of 500 kg/hour is estimated at 12 million rubles. The depreciation period is set at five years (60 months), which is the standard period for technological equipment in this industry.

Assumptions were made to focus on profitability and ensure comparability:

1. Line capacity: adopted uniform for all types of polymers — 500 kg/h. This is a standard capacity for small and medium-sized enterprises, which allows them to achieve payback in a reasonable time. Working hours: twenty-two working days per month for eight hours, which gives a monthly processing volume of eighty-eight tons.

2. Ignoring other operating costs: the model does not take into account wages, rental of space, the cost of water, detergents, logistics and administrative costs. This is done intentionally to highlight the impact of fundamentally different raw material costs and to show the basic marginality of each area. In practice, these costs can range from ten to twenty percent of the cost and are distributed relatively evenly between different polymers.

3. Raw material quality and product yield: it is accepted that the input raw materials meet the standard contamination requirements, and technological losses such as rejection or screening are minimal. In reality, for polyethylene, especially films, the yield of the finished product may be fifteen to twenty-five percent lower

due to the content of heavy impurities and unsorted inclusions, which is a hidden but critical factor in reducing profitability [5].

4. Price stability: The calculation uses a static snapshot of market prices for a specific period. In dynamics, prices for raw materials and products correlate, but at different rates, which creates operational risks for profitability stability.

The final indicator for comparison.

Gross profit margin is selected as an integral indicator of efficiency, calculated using the following formula: Profitability = Gross profit / Cost × 100 %.

This indicator clearly demonstrates what percentage of revenue from sales is profit before deducting management and business expenses, and allows you to directly compare the attractiveness of different business areas.

Thus, the proposed model is effectively suitable for comparative analysis, minimizing the influence of particular conditions and highlighting the fundamental economic differences between the processing streams of polyethylene terephthalate, polyethylene and polypropylene. The results obtained allow us to draw the first conclusions about the potential profitability that can be used when developing a full-fledged business plan, taking into account all specific factors.

To simplify the model used and to ensure the purity of the comparison of basic items, only depreciation is conditionally attributed to fixed costs (Tab. 1):

— Monthly depreciation charges: 12,000,000 rubles / 60 months = 200,000 rubles/month.

— Depreciation per 1 kg of products: 200,000 rubles / 88,000 kg = 2,27 rubles/kg.

— Electricity costs per 1 kg: 0,5 kWh / kg /kg × 6 rubles/kW·h = 3,0 rubles/kg.

— Average market prices for secondary raw materials (flex/crushed) are used.

Table 1. Comparative cost of the product and the resulting regranulate

Product type	Product cost, RUB/kg	Regranulate cost, RUB/kg
PET (transparent bottle)	35–40	65–75
PE (LDPE/LLDPE film)	18–25	45–55
PP (casting/extrusion waste)	30–35	60–70

The average values are used for the calculation (Tab. 2.): PET (raw material 37,5, product 70), PE (raw material 21,5, product 50), PP (raw material 32,5, product 65).

Based on the developed financial and economic model, a comparative analysis of the profitability of processing the main types of thermoplastics were carried out. Calculations have shown that:

Table 2. The total profitability of various types of thermoplastics

Indicator	PET (bottle)	PE (film)	PP (waste)
Product, RUB/kg	37,5	21,5	32,5
Electricity, RUB/kg	3	3	3
Depreciation, RUB/kg	2,27	2,27	2,27
Total cost, RUB/kg	42,77	26,77	37,77
Cost of regranulate, rub/kg	70	50	65
Gross profit, RUB/kg	27,23	23,23	27,23
Profitability, %	63,7%	86,8%	72,1%

— recycling of polyethylene film demonstrates the highest potential profitability of 86.8, but this indicator is the most sensitive to the actual cost of sink;

— the processing of polyethylene terephthalate 63.7% and polypropylene 72.1% is characterized by more stable and high rates, and the cost in these areas is 85–90% determined by the cost of raw materials.

The key economic factor for all industries is the difference between the price of commercial granulate and the purchase price of sorted raw materials. Thus, the results of this work not only structure knowledge about thermoplastic recycling equipment, but also provide a practical tool for consciously choosing raw material specialization and optimizing costs. The obtained data form a solid basis for further research, particularly for detailed mathematical modeling of key equipment components during the processing of specific types of polymer waste.

List of literature

1. Kryzhanovsky, V. K. *Technology of processing plastics and elastomers: a textbook for universities* / V. K. Kryzhanovsky, V. V. Burlov, A. D. Panimatchenko. — Saint Petersburg: Profession, 2021. — 416 p. — ISBN 978-5-91885-268-9. p. 52.

2. Schwartz, A. G. *Polymer extrusion* / A. G. Schwartz, F. R. Schwartz. — 3rd ed., reprint. St. Petersburg: Profession, 2020. 496 p. ISBN 978-5-91885-452-2. pp. 138.

3. *Polymer waste and problems of their recycling: a monograph* / edited by A. A. Popov. — Moscow: Infra-Engineering, 2022. — 188 p. — ISBN 978-5-9729-0934-3. P. 44.

4. *Secondary polymer market in Russia 2023: research and forecast until 2026: analytical report*. Moscow: ROI, 2023. 145 p. 26.

5. *Fundamentals of designing equipment for polymer processing: a textbook* / B. V. Braginsky [et al.]; edited by B. V. Braginsky. — Saint Petersburg: TSOP "Profession", 2019. — 288 p. — ISBN 978-5-91885-218-4. P. 12.

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ASSESSMENT OF OVERHEAD LINE CONDUCTORS AND GROUND WIRES TECHNICAL CONDITION ACCORDING TO MAGNETIC FLAW DETECTION DATA

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Abstract. *This paper discusses the practice of monitoring the technical condition of overhead power transmission line equipment (current-carrying conductors, ground wires, and tower guys) using non-destructive testing tools such as magnetic flaw detection. The results of monitoring the current condition of conductors and ground wires on 35–220 kV overhead power lines in the networks of PJSC "Rosseti" branches are illustrated. Calculated estimates of the residual load-bearing capacity of the inspected objects based on magnetic flaw detection data are presented. A conclusion is drawn regarding the effectiveness of magnetic flaw detection for assessing the current condition and remaining service life of conductors, ground wires, and tower guys.*

Keywords: *overhead power lines, technical condition, monitoring, bimetallic conductors, ground wires, magnetic flaw detection, cross-section loss, local defects, load-bearing capacity, residual service life.*

Introduction The safe operation of overhead power lines depends on many factors, including the strength of line equipment components (current-carrying conductors, ground wires, and support guy wires). Therefore, worn or defective conductors, ground wires, and support guy wires must be replaced promptly. The technical condition (TC) assessment of overhead power line conductors, ground wires, and support guy wires is based on a comparison of the identified defects with the rejection standards specified in regulatory and technical documents [1–3].

During operation, conductors and ground wires are subject to corrosion, friction, and fatigue wear. Lightning strikes expose sections of conductors/cables to high temperatures, which leads to a loss of their load-bearing capacity (strength)

due to changes in the metal structure. If timely measures are not taken, all of these factors, due to increased wind loads or the formation of ice, can lead to conductor or cable breakage. When monitoring the TC of bimetallic conductors (type ASCR) and steel ground wires, both visual inspection and non-destructive testing (NDT) are used. Obviously, visual measurement control (VMC) of conductors/ground wires only detects surface defects. The degree of frictional wear or corrosion of the internal wires of the steel core of the conductor cannot be detected using VMC. However, these defects lead to a loss of metal area (LMA), a key characteristic determining its strength. The loss of metal area (LMA) and the number of wire breaks (NB) over a given length of conductor or conductor are used in domestic and international regulatory documents as basic rejection criteria.

Below is a description of the technology for monitoring the TC of steel ground wires and steel cores of bimetallic conductors (type ASCR, etc., GOST 839–2019) using magnetic flaw detection. Examples of diagnostic data and the results of a calculated assessment of the residual bearing capacity of inspected objects on overhead power lines of branches of PJSC “Rosseti” Centre and PJSC “Rosseti” Centre and Volga Region are provided. These materials were used in the development of reconstruction and repair projects for the inspected overhead power lines.

Equipment for magnetic flaw detection of overhead power line conductors and ground wires. Over the past 20–30 years, the operating departments of domestic and foreign grid companies have begun to use NDT tools — magnetic flaw detectors based on the MFL (Magnetic Flux Leakage) method — to diagnose the TC of steel ground wires and cables (GOST 3062–80, GOST 3063–80, etc.) of overhead power line support guys, as well as the steel cores of bare wires (GOST 839–2019) [4–9]. Although the design, basic characteristics, and even the purpose of magnetic flaw detectors have changed significantly in recent years, their operating principle remains the same. Magnetic flux is generated along the object being tested by an electromagnet or permanent magnet and brings the ferromagnetic material to a state close to magnetic saturation. Under these conditions, the magnetic flux is directly proportional to the cross-sectional area of the material. By measuring the change in magnetic flux along the tested object with magnetically sensitive sensors (Hall sensors) due to a decrease in the cross-sectional area of the ground wire or bimetallic wire core (type ASCR), the LMA can be determined as a percentage of the nominal cross-sectional area of the steel. If a ground wire or steel core breaks, part of the magnetic flux is released into the surrounding medium. When the section containing the broken wire moves near the magnetically sensitive sensor, an electrical pulse is generated at the sensor’s output. This method can detect breaks not only on the surface but also within the tested object.

When monitoring TC, conductors, ground wires, and guy wires of overhead transmission line supports must be simultaneously inspected for distributed defects

(LMA due to fretting-corrosion wear) and LDs (such as number of wire breaks, traces of thermal impact, etc.). The flaw detectors used must meet certain requirements. Their kit must consist of a measuring unit (MG - a magnetic head with a replaceable set of sensors) and an electronic unit (EU) for collecting, processing, and storing diagnostic information. The design and overall dimensions and weight of the flaw detector must ensure easy installation/dismantling on the conductor/ground wire being inspected (the weight of the kit, depending on the MG size, ranges from 3 to 15 kg). To localize the signals from the measuring sensors, the flaw detector must be equipped with a distance counter, allowing the position of the signals on the defectograms to be determined relative to a fixed point on the monitored object. The flaw detector design must enable the inspection of overhead line conductors and ground wires with diameters ranging from 6 to 42 mm. Flaw detection must be supported at various line speeds (0 to 4 m/s). Real-time flaw detection, with data storage and subsequent processing, is required, as well as the operability of the flaw detector electronics even under induced voltage conditions on the overhead line. Metrological characteristics must meet the following requirements*:

- Error in measuring the grounding wire within the wire/grounding wire diameter range of 6 to 12 mm: no more than 2%, and within the diameter range of 12 to 64 mm: 0.5%;
- Wire breakage sensitivity threshold: 0.5%;
- IP54 or IP66 rating.

Note: Domestic magnetic flaw detectors for steel cables INTROS meet the above requirements. (www.intron.ru).

Magnetic flaw detection technology for overhead power transmission lines (OHL) conductors and ground wires. Monitoring of conductors and ground wires can be performed without grounding them, but with the OPL de-energized, which improves the safety of equipment installation/dismantling at the facility being inspected. Magnetic flaw detection should be preceded by visual inspection of the conductors/ground wires, which can be performed using a UAV or a wheeled device equipped with a video recording and data transmission system (FPV — First Person View [9]) moving over the facility being inspected. It is also necessary to ensure that there are no obstacles to the movement of the OHL over the facility being inspected (protruding ends of broken outer wires, localized increases in the diameter of the conductor/ground wire, etc.). Such obstacles must be removed. Otherwise, the relevant areas are excluded from the flaw detection process, as are areas inaccessible to inspection due to design limitations.

Installation and removal of diagnostic equipment (the MG and EB flaw detector, as well as the FPV and data transmission systems) at the height of the wire/ground wire suspension are performed using auxiliary equipment (a lift, installation trolley, etc.).

To record defectograms via the LMA and LD channels, the flaw detector's measuring head must be moved along the accessible section of the wire/ground wire (pulled over with a nylon rope or using an autonomous, remotely controlled, self-propelled device).

Fig. 1. Moving the measuring head along the wire:
 a) using a nylon rope; b) using an autonomous self-propelled device

Assessment of technical condition of ground wires and overhead power line conductors based on magnetic flaw detection results. Classification of technical condition of conductors/ground wires based on magnetic flaw detection data is performed in accordance with the following regulatory documents: RD 34.20.504–94 “Standard instruction for operation of overhead power transmission lines with voltage of 35–800 kV” and RD “Instruction for determination of technical condition of combined conductors, ground wires and guys of overhead power line supports by non-destructive testing methods using magnetic flaw detection” (approved by JSC “STC of Electric Power Industry”). These instructions list the categories of technical condition, provide standards for rejection of conductors/ground wires, and give recommendations on the frequency of magnetic flaw detection. In accordance with the category of technical condition of conductors/ground wires of overhead power lines, the following periods for subsequent diagnostics are recommended: “Operating” (LMA up to 11 %) — after 6 years; “Limitedly serviceable” (LMA from 11 % to 20 %) — after 3 years. If the TC is classified as “Inoperative (emergency)” (LMA greater than 20% or the number of ground wire or core breaks exceeds the rejection standards), then a decision on repair and restoration measures should be made immediately.

Assessment of the bearing capacity of ground wires and overhead power line conductors based on magnetic non-destructive testing (NDT). Assessing the strength degradation of conductors/ground wires is a component of the qualification of their TC. The information obtained during NDT monitoring alone does not

allow one to judge the degree of change in the strength of the monitored objects. However, diagnostic parameters (LMA and/or the number of LD over a given length) can be used as input data when calculating the estimated bearing capacity of conductors/ground wires based on an appropriate mechanical model using methods of materials and structures mechanics. This approach to using magnetic non-destructive testing results allows us to determine strength indicators that can be used to draw informed conclusions about the TC of the diagnosed objects.

From an engineering perspective, TC degradation associated with the loss of the conductor/ground wire's load-bearing capacity is naturally interpreted as a reduction in the safety factor due to the accumulation of operational defects compared to the initial state. The safety factor can serve as an informative parameter when qualifying the conductor/ground wire's load-bearing capacity during its current service life. When the safety factor becomes close to the standard value, it becomes necessary to take appropriate measures to ensure the safe operation of the overhead power line.

The methodology and sequence for strength calculations for ground wires (steel cables) are given in [11]. The safety factor is determined by the ratio:

$$n = \frac{\sigma_{\epsilon}}{\max \sigma_{\text{экс}}}, \quad (1)$$

where $\sigma_{\text{б}}$ — tensile strength of the wire material, $\sigma_{\text{экс}}$ — equivalent stress according to the corresponding strength criterion [12] in the most stressed wire.

Relative parameters of strength loss $R_{\text{ПЦ}}$ and $R_{\text{ЛД}}$, associated with two types of defects — LMA and LD, are introduced as

$$R_{\text{ПЦ}} = 1 - \frac{n_{\text{ПЦ}}}{n_0}, \quad R_{\text{ЛД}} = 1 - \frac{n_{\text{ЛД}}}{n_0}. \quad (2)$$

Here $n_{\text{ПЦ}}$ and $n_{\text{ЛД}}$ — safety factors for a rope with defects of the LMA and LD types, respectively, n_0 — safety factor of a new rope in the delivery condition (theoretically, without defects). Parameters $R_{\text{ПЦ}}$ and $R_{\text{ЛД}}$ are determined independently according to the hypothesis of damage accumulation in structural mechanics. The resulting loss of strength R in cross section is determined by superposition

$$n = n_0 (1 - \max R). \quad (6)$$

The safety factor of the wire and/or ground wire is determined by the expression

$$n = n_0 (1 - \max R), \quad (7)$$

where $\max R$ — Maximum loss of strength in the diagnosed area. The safety factor must remain above the minimum permissible standard value throughout the entire service life. n_* , i.e. $n \geq n_*$. Otherwise, the ground wire must be replaced.

The strength calculation of bimetallic wires is performed according to the same scheme as for ground wires, with the stress state parameters assessed using methods adopted for combined structures [13]. Current values of strength indicators n or R can be used to evaluate the load-bearing capacity of wires with accumulated defects.

Figure 2 shows examples of calculated nomograms for the relative loss of strength for a range of bimetallic bare wires (type ASCR GOST 839–2019) depending on the loss of cross-section of the steel core. These nomograms allow for a rapid assessment of the reduction in the wire’s load-bearing capacity based on diagnostic data.

Fig. 2. Nomograms of the relative loss of strength of steel-aluminum composites depending on the loss of cross-sectional area of the steel core

a)

b)

Fig. 3. Defectograms of the LMA (a) and LD (b) of the core of the BS 185/43 steel-bronze wire

The results of calculating the residual strength of a section of BS 185/43 conductor operated at the crossing of the 35 kV Ladozhskaya-3 overhead line across the Neva River are presented in [10] (see Figs. 6–7). The defectograms for the LMA and LD channels of a section of BS 185/43 conductor at the crossing of the 35 kV Ladozhskaya-3 overhead line across the Neva River, obtained with an INTROS (MG 20–40) flaw detector, are shown in Fig. 3. The defectogram (Fig. 3a) shows that the maximum PS in this section is 18%, and the peaks in the LD defectogram (Fig. 3b) indicate the presence of wire breaks.

The distribution of the strength index n along the section of the wire with diagnosed defects, obtained by calculation, is shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Distribution of the strength index in a section of BS 185/43 conductor

The red dot at $l^* = 10.1$ m corresponds to the minimum value of $n = 3.57$. This minimum can be considered the actual safety factor n for the conductor in the section under consideration. The obtained estimates are consistent with the provisions of the Electrical Installation Code (PUE-7) [1], where strength requirements are formulated in terms of “permissible stresses.” Specifically, stresses in the conductor must not exceed the permissible value, which is determined depending on the type and brand of conductor, as well as the typical operating conditions.

We note some problems and specific features of the residual strength assessment of conductors/grounding cables with identified operational defects. This assessment must be conducted taking into account changes in the strength characteristics of the corresponding structural materials during long-term operation. Unfortunately, reliable and systematic data regarding the long-term strength of bimetallic conductors (type ASCR, etc.) is extremely limited.

Calculation results show that the loss of strength in bimetallic conductors is less than the core’s SS due to the fact that part of the load is supported by the layered wires. Calculating a conductor/ground wire using the spiral cable model [12], unlike the “rod approximation” [13], takes into account the uneven distribution of stresses across the cross-section caused by the stretching, bending, and torsion of the wires. This yields a greater loss of strength than the calculation based on ultimate loads in the “rod approximation.” For the same reason, the loss of strength in ground wires is higher as a percentage than the corresponding SS for the metal. The more complex the core design, the greater the difference in the safety factors for new and defective conductors under comparable loads.

Results of diagnostics of the technical condition of overhead power line conductors and ground wires using magnetic flaw detection. Below, using the example of monitoring conductors and ground wires performed by specialists from the INTRON PLUS laboratory as part of comprehensive inspections of 35–110 kV overhead power lines at Rosseti Centre’s electric grid enterprises (see Table 1), we illustrate the effectiveness of using magnetic flaw detection in assessing the operational readiness of lines with a long service life (45–50 years or more).

Wires and ground wires were inspected at 10 branches of PJSC Rosseti Centre on 18 35–110 kV overhead lines. At Belgorodenergo, the conductor TC was classified as “Operable” on all inspected overhead lines, which had a service life of 35 to 48 years. The next magnetic NDT inspection is recommended to be performed in 6 years. A similar situation was observed on the 35 kV Vetma-Kasilovskaya overhead line (commissioned in 1986, Bryanskenergo), the 110 kV Dolgorukovo overhead line (commissioned in 1982, Lipetskenegero), and the 110 kV Talashkino-Golyнки No. 2 overhead line (commissioned in 1974, Smolenskenergo).

Table 1. Names and characteristics of inspected overhead power lines at Rosseti Centre's branches

«Belgorodenergo»			
№	Characteristics of objects	Overhead Power Line under Diagnostics / Year of Commissioning / Technical Condition	Reason for control
1	2	3	4
1	Name of overhead power line/ Year of commissioning:	110 kV overhead power line “Frunzenskaya-Belgorodskaya CHPP” / 1986 / TC: «Operable»	Crossing a road, populated area
	Overhead power line section/ Length of section	Spans 143–144, 153–154, 152–153 / 0.565 km	
	Type of wires/ground wire	AC-150/24 (LMA 2.9–5.4%) / S-50 (Not monitored)	
1	2	3	4
2	Overhead Line Name/Year of Commissioning:	110 kV Gubkin-Tyagovaya Over- head Line / 1975/ TC: «Rabotic»	Marshy area
	Overhead Line Section/Length	Span 74–75 / 0.184 km	
	Type of Wires/Ground Wire	AS-185/29 (LMA 7.7–9.1%) / S-50 (Not monitored)	
3	Overhead Line Name/Year of Commissioning:	110 kV Stary Oskol — Pushkar- naya Overhead Line / 1977 / TC: «Rabotic»	River crossing
	Overhead Line Section/Length	Span 26–27 / 0.238 km	
	Type of Wires/Ground Wire	AS-185/29 (LMA 9.0–9.8%) / S-50 (Not monitored)	
4	Overhead Line Name/Year of Commissioning:	110 kV Stary Oskol — Tsentral- naya 1 Overhead Line / 1977 / TC: «Rabotic»	Pollied area
	Overhead Line Section/Length	Span 160–161 / 0.075 km	
	Type of Wires/Ground Wire	AS-185/29 (LMA 6.8–8.0%) / C-50 (Not controlled)	
«Bryanskenergo»			
6	Name of overhead power line/ Year of commissioning:	35 kV Vetma-Kasilovskaya Over- head Line / 1986 / TC: «Operable»	Crossing a road, populated area
	Overhead power line section/ Length of section	Spans 9–13 / 0.540 km	
	Type of wires/ground wire	AC-70/11 (LMA 4.8–6.7%)/PS-35 (Not monitored)	

«Voronezhenergo»			
7	Name of overhead power line/ Year of commissioning:	110 kV Double-Circuit Overhead Line «Yuzhnaya — DSK No. 9» / 1966 / TC: «Limited Serviceability»	Populated area
	Overhead power line section/ Length of section	Spans 56–59; 61–63 / 0.624 km; 0.626 km	
	Type of wires/ground wire	AC-185/29 (LMA 16.3–19.8%) / S-50 (Not Monitored)	
«Kostromaenergo»			
8	Name of overhead power line/ Year of commissioning:	110 kV Borok-Galich Overhead Line / 1963 / TC: «Inoperative»	Populated area, accident rate
	Overhead power line section/ Length of section	Spans 223–225 / 0.455 km	
	Type of wires/ground wire	AC-129/19 (LMA 20.2–21.3%) / S-50 (PS 18.2–19.0%)	
«Lipetskenergo»			
1	Name of overhead power line/ Year of commissioning:	110 kV Dolgorukovo Overhead Line / 1982 / TC: «Operable»	Accidents, crossing roads and railways
	Overhead power line section/ Length of section	Spans 38–39, 177–178 / 0.447 km	
	Type of wires/ground wire	AC-150/24 / S-50	
2	Name of overhead power line/ Year of commissioning:	35 kV No. 5 Overhead Line / 1956 / TC: «Inoperative»	Accident rate
	Overhead power line section/ Length of section	Spans 44–46 / 0.279 km	
	Type of wires/ground wire	AC-70/11 (PS 19.9–21.2%) / (Absent from the overhead line)	
3	Name of overhead power line/ Year of commissioning:	35 kV Krasnaya Palna Overhead Line / 1966/TC: «Limited Operation»	Accident rate
	Overhead power line section/ Length of section	Spans 72–74 / 0.209 km	
	Type of wires/ground wire	AC-50/8 (LMA 15.6–17.4%) / (Absent from the overhead line)	
«Orelenegero»			
1	Name of overhead power line/ Year of commissioning:	110 kV Livny-Cherkasskaya Overhead Line, 1 Circuit / 1972 / TC: «Limited Operational Capacity»	Populated area
	Overhead power line section/ Length of section	Spans 17/17–19/19 / 0.415 km	
	Type of wires/ground wire	AC-120/19 (LMA 11.0–12.8%) / C50 (Not Monitored)	

Smolenskenergo			
1	Name of overhead power line/ Year of commissioning:	110 kV Talashkino — Golyнки No. 2 Overhead Line / 1974 / TC: «Operable»	Intersection with 330 kV overhead power line
	Overhead power line section/ Length of section	Spans 5–8А / 0.716 km	
	Type of wires/ground wire	AC-150/24 (PS 7.8–9.6%) / TK50 (LMA 3.7–5.5%)	
Tambovenergo			
1	Name of overhead power line/ Year of commissioning:	110 kV Michurinskaya- Pervomayskaya Overhead Line / 1963 / TC: «Limited Operational Capacity» «Operable»	Accident rate
	Overhead power line section/ Length of section	Spans 37/37–41/41 / 0.789 km	
	Type of wires/ground wire	AC-185/24 (LMA 15.1–19.4%)/ C50 (Not tested)	
«Tverenergo»			
1	Name of overhead power line/ Year of commissioning:	110 kV Krasny Kholm — Kesma Overhead Line / 1970 / TC: «Lim- ited Serviceability»	Accident rate
	Overhead power line section/ Length of section	Spans 162–165 / 0.610 km	
	Type of wires/ground wire	AC-95/16 (PS 10.9–15.2%) / TK-50 (PS 6.3–9.8%)	
1	2	3	4
	Name of overhead power line/ Year of commissioning:	110 kV Porechye-Sandovo Over- head Line / 1964 / TC: «Inoperative»	Accident rate
	Overhead power line section/ Length of section	Spans 180–183 / 0.413 km	
	Type of wires/ground wire	AC-120/19 (PS 16.7–19.7%) / S-50 (PS 13.4–16.7%)	
«Yarenergo»			
1	Name of overhead power line/ Year of commissioning:	110 kV Putyatinskaya Double- Circuit Overhead Line / 1962 / TC: «Limited Serviceability»	Cross- ing the railway
	Overhead power line section/ Length of section	Spans 33–34, 42–43 / 0.482 km	
	Type of wires/ground wire	AS-240/39 (LMA 11.0–12.8%)/ S-50 (Not controlled)	

In a number of cases, significant operational defects were identified in the ground wires and conductor cores. For example, on the 110 kV Yuzhnaya — DSK No. 9 overhead power line (commissioned in 1966, Voronezhenergo), the ground wire cores were classified as “Limitedly Serviceable” (wire core resistance was no more than 20%, and the relative loss of load-bearing capacity was up to 17%). The next magnetic NDT was recommended for three years. A similar situation occurred on the 35 kV Krasnaya Palna overhead line (commissioned in 1966, Lipetskenergo), on the 110 kV Livny-Cherkasskaya overhead line (commissioned in 1972, Orelenergo), and on other lines (see Table 1).

At the same time, the diagnostics of the conductor core resistance on the inspected overhead lines using magnetic non-destructive testing yielded more alarming results. Thus, the data from the defectoscopy of conductors on the 35 kV No. 5 overhead line (commissioned in 1956, Lipetskenergo) and the 110 kV Borok-Galich overhead line (commissioned in 1963, Kostromaenergo) showed that their conductor core resistance should be classified as “Inoperative” (conductor core resistance is more than 20%, and the relative loss bearing capacity — more than 17%). Along with the phase conductors, flaw detection of ground wires was also carried out on some of the monitored overhead lines (see Table 1). The condition of the ground wires on the 110 kV Talashkino — Golyнки No. 2 overhead line (PAO Smolenskenergo) and the 110 kV Krasny Kholm — Kesma overhead line (commissioned in 1970, PAO Tverenergo) was classified as “Operable”, on the 110 kV Borok-Galich overhead line — as “Limitedly operable”, and on the 110 kV Porechye-Sandovo overhead line (commissioned in 1964, Tverenergo) — as “Inoperable”. Below, as an example, the data of flaw detection of the ground wire on the 110 kV Porechye-Sandovo overhead line are provided (with branches at PS Akhmatovo, PS Topalki) in the span between supports No. 179 and No. 180. Fig. 5 shows the defectograms of the LMA and LD, recorded by the INTROS flaw detector (MG 6–24). Table 2 shows the parameters of the ground wire, the inspected section, and reflects the results of the office analysis of the defectograms of the LMA and LD using the Wintros program.

Table 2. Results of diagnostics of the ground wire of the 110 kV Porechye-Sandovo overhead power line

Ground wire type	Ground wire inspection section and its length	Description of the detected defects. Their parameters	Technical condition
Lightning cable S-50, diameter $d=9.1$ mm.	The initial inspection point, “0 m,” is located at support No. 180. The section length is 218.5 m.	Maximum loss of cross-section of the ground wire — PS = 16.4% at the 37.2 m mark. Wire breakage with a divergence of (36.2–37.2) m.	TC “Inoperative.» The grounding cable must be replaced.

a)

b)

Fig. 5. Defectograms of the LMA (a) and LD (b) of ground wire section on the 110 kV “Porechye-Sandovo” overhead line.

Conclusions

1. Magnetic flux detection is an effective method for non-destructive testing and diagnostics of the technical condition of overhead line equipment — bimetallic bare conductors (type ASCR, etc.), steel ground wires, and support guy wires. At Rosseti PJSC branches, this NDT method is increasingly being used in comprehensive inspections of 35–220 kV overhead lines, conducted to determine the operational readiness of line equipment.

2. The results of diagnostics and monitoring of ground wires and ground wires using magnetic flux detection, in some cases, indicate limited or inoperable (pre-emergency) conditions of the tested equipment, while in others, they help extend the safe operating life. This saves significant financial costs on repair and restoration work or replacement of overhead line equipment.

3. From an engineering perspective, the residual strength factor, a parameter characterizing the condition of an overhead line conductor/grounding wire calculated using flux detection data, can serve as an additional argument when making appropriate decisions by operating personnel. Periodic monitoring of the TC using magnetic flux detection technology allows for assessing the rate of degradation of the technical condition of conductors/grounding wires and,

based on this, developing methods for quantitatively assessing their remaining service life.

The register of regulatory and technical documents in the field of technical regulation of PJSC Rosseti does not currently contain any guidelines regarding methods for using magnetic flaw detection to determine the technical condition of the monitored object. The need to conduct diagnostics of current-carrying bi-metallic wires, steel ground wires, and support guy wires using magnetic flaw detection should be reflected in the relevant standards of PJSC Rosseti, regulating the procedure for performing and sequencing control and diagnostic work, as well as in the technical specifications for the performance of work on monitoring the TC of the lines in operation.

References

1. *Electrical Installation Rules. 7th edition. Stereotype reprint // St. Petersburg: DEAN Publishing House, 2008. — 704 p.*

2. RD 34.20.504–94 “*Standard Operating Instructions for 35–800 kV Overhead Power Lines*” // Moscow: NC ENAS Publishing House, 2006. — 200 p.

3. Appendix 3 to the Order of RAO UES of Russia and OAO FGC UES dated 17.12.2002 No. 706/100 — “*Methodological Guidelines for Assessing the Technical Condition of Main Electric Grid Facilities of JSC-Energo and the Infrastructure Ensuring Their Repair and Operational Maintenance*”.

4. *Non-destructive Testing: Handbook: In 8 volumes // Under the general editorship of V. V. Klyueva. Vol. 6: Book 1: V. V. Klyuev, V. F. Muzhitsky, E. S. Gorkunov, V. E. Shcherbinin. Magnetic Testing Methods. 2nd ed., corrected. Moscow: Mashinostroenie, 2006. — 832 p.*

5. RD-03–348–00 *Guidelines for Magnetic Flaw Testing of Steel Ropes. Basic Provisions // Moscow: Gostekhnadzor, 2000. — 18 p.*

6. Belitsky S. V., Kasimov G. A., Sukhorukov V. V. *Steel Rope Flaw Detector IN-TROS // In the World of NK, 2006, No. 2. pp. 13–18.*

7. V. Sukhorukov, D. Slesarev, A. Vorontsov. *Electromagnetic inspection and diagnostics of steel ropes: technology, effectiveness and problems. Materials Evaluation (ME), American Society of Nondestructive Testing. Vol. 72, N8, August 2014, pp.1019–1027.*

8. V. Volokhovskiy, A. Vorontsov, D. Sukhorukov, B. Mekhanoshin, V. Shkaptsov. «*Assessment of OHL Availability and Residual Life-Time by Using Non Destructive Instrumental Control for Conductors, Steel Wires and Guys*». (CIGRE Session 2010, B2–309) <http://www.cigre.org/gb/Events/session.asp>

9. V. Y. Volokhovskiy, A. N. Vorontsov, V. V. Sukhorukov, V. V. Tsukanov, V. A. Shkaptsov, M. S. Artem'ev, V. V. Chernetsov. *Condition assessment of conductors and ground wires of overhead lines using non-destructive testing based on magnetic flux measurements* // *Cigre Science and Engineering*, 2016, No 6. P. 46–54.

10. Volokhovskiy V. Yu., Vorontsov A. N., Sukhorukov D. V., Rudyak A. R. *Magnetic flaw detection — an effective tool for monitoring the technical condition of wires and ground wires of overhead power lines* // *Electric Stations*, 2019, No. 12. pp. 28–37.

11. Vorontsov A. N., Volokhovskiy V. Yu. *Mechanical model for assessing the strength and service life of steel ropes of lifting machines and according to diagnostic data. Handbook. Engineering journal* // *Moscow: Publishing house SPECTRUM*, No. 10 (187), 2012. pp. 37–47.

12. Sorensen S. V., Kogaev V. P., Shneiderovich R. M. *Bearing capacity and strength calculations of machine parts* // *Moscow: Mechanical Engineering*, 1975.— 448 p.

13. Kesselman L. M. *Fundamentals of Mechanics of Overhead Power Lines* // *Moscow: Energoatomizdat*, 1992.— 354 p.

14. Glushko M. F. *Steel Hoisting Ropes* // *Odessa: Astroprint*, 2013.— 336 p.

CURRENT ISSUES OF FIRE SAFETY OF ELECTRICAL EQUIPMENT

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Abstract. *This article examines current issues related to fire safety in electrical equipment. Statistical data analysis reveals a steady increase in the number of electrical fires, demonstrating the ineffectiveness of existing approaches to monitoring and prevention. Key emergency modes (short circuit, overload, high contact resistance, sparking, arcing, and overvoltage) are classified and analyzed, revealing their interrelationships and the cumulative effect leading to fires. Particular attention is paid to the role of cable insulation degradation as the primary initiating factor. The paper presents a critical review of traditional and modern insulation diagnostic methods, assessing their capabilities and limitations. It also substantiates the need to shift from reactive measures to predictive fire risk management based on integrated monitoring systems and equipment residual life assessment, enabling the implementation of a predictive maintenance strategy.*

Keywords: *fire safety, electrical equipment, emergency modes, insulation degradation.*

Introduction

Electrical equipment is an integral element of the infrastructure of any industrial enterprise or civil facility. However, its operation is associated with a high risk of emergency conditions that can lead to fires. According to statistics, electrical equipment accounts for approximately 30% of fires [1]. Violations of electrical equipment installation and operation regulations are the direct cause of over 64,000 fires per year. This indicates a systemic problem leading to human deaths (approximately 2,300 per year) and significant property damage (almost 11 billion rubles annually). It is important to note that the problem is not stabilizing, but worsening. There has been a steady increase in the number of such fires: from 59,783 in 2022 to 64,795 in 2024. This demonstrates that existing approaches to monitoring and prevention are insufficiently effective and require fundamentally new solutions. The vast majority of fires (57,374 incidents) involve cables and wires. This clearly indicates that the

insulation condition of cable and wire products is the primary fire hazard factor, and its diagnosis and prediction should be the primary focus.

It is also important to note the statistics on electrical injuries to workers. An analysis of the causes of electrical injuries in the Russian Federation shows that 40–45% of electrical injuries are related to improper equipment operation, leading to reduced insulation resistance and the appearance of voltage on non-current-carrying parts. A significant number of electrical injuries (25–30%) are caused by poor workplace organization and failure to comply with job descriptions and occupational safety requirements. 30–35% of electrical injuries are due to poor equipment design and installation: the presence of exposed live parts, insufficient clearance between live parts and metal equipment structures, the absence of alarms and interlocks, etc. [2]. Ultimately, it can be concluded that, according to statistics, the number of fires caused by electrical faults is steadily increasing, making the issue of fire risk management urgent. The goal is to systematize fire causes, critically evaluate existing diagnostic and control methods, and substantiate directions for developing predictive measures.

Classification and analysis of the causes of electrical fires

Fire safety at various facilities, including residential and public buildings, is largely determined by the condition of the electrical equipment and installations. As noted above, the proportion of fires caused by faults in electrical systems reaches 30%, due to the wide range of emergency conditions and the complexity of their interactions. Key causes of electrical fires include short circuits, electrical circuit overloads, high contact resistance, sparking, arcing, and overvoltage. These phenomena are not isolated; they form a complex cause-and-effect network, where one emergency condition can initiate or aggravate another, greatly increasing the overall fire risk [3].

Short circuits are the most common and dangerous cause. They occur when conductors with different potentials come into direct contact through broken, charred, or mechanically damaged insulation. The fire hazard mechanism involves a sudden increase in current, which, according to the Joule-Lenz law, leads to the release of a huge amount of heat in a short time. This causes the melting of the conductive conductors, intense combustion, and spattering of the insulation, releasing flammable gases. The temperature in the short-circuit zone can reach several thousand degrees, and the ejected hot metal and polymer particles serve as powerful ignition sources for surrounding flammable materials.

Electrical circuit overload is a condition in which the current in the circuit continuously exceeds the rated value for which the wires and equipment are designed. It occurs when multiple high-power consumers are connected simultaneously to a single line, when conductors with insufficient cross-section are used, or when electric motors are mechanically overloaded. The fire hazard from overload is cumulative:

prolonged heating of the wires leads to thermal aging of the insulation — loss of elasticity, charring, and a reduction in dielectric strength. According to the “eight-degree” rule of thumb, an 8 °C increase in temperature reduces the service life of insulation by half. Ultimately, degraded insulation loses its properties, creating the conditions for a short circuit.

High contact resistance (poor contact) occurs at connection points due to oxidation, looseness, or mechanical damage. According to the Joule-Lenz law, the heat generated in a contact is proportional to its resistance. Even with normal current, high resistance leads to localized overheating of the contact pair, which causes further oxidation and an increase in resistance — a self-accelerating process. The temperature at the point of poor contact can reach hundreds of degrees, causing charring of the insulation, melting of the metal, and, as a result, sparking or arcing. Thus, high contact resistance serves as a direct ignition source and is often the cause of subsequent short circuits.

Sparking (arcing) is a short-term electrical discharge in a gaseous medium (air), accompanied by the release of light and heat. It occurs when a circuit breaks under load, a contact failure occurs in switches, or when small air gaps between conductors are disrupted. Although the energy of a single spark may be small, its temperature reaches 1500–2000 °C, which is sufficient to ignite flammable gases, dust, or flammable liquids. Sparking often accompanies other emergency situations: for example, a vibrating wire with damaged insulation can create intermittent sparks, while a broken conductor in a live cable leads to a sustained spark discharge.

An electric arc is a sustained plasma discharge with high current density and extremely high temperature (3000–4000 °C and higher). In electrical installations, arcs occur due to short circuits, circuit breaks under heavy load, or insulation breakdown. Its danger lies in the combined thermal effects: direct contact with flammable material, powerful thermal radiation, and splashing molten metal. An electric arc has tremendous destructive power and ignites most flammable materials almost instantly. Arcing is often the culmination of a fault condition initiated by overload, poor contact, or overvoltage.

An electrical network overvoltage is a short-term, significant increase in operating voltage caused by atmospheric discharges (direct lightning strikes or induced surges), switching processes, or the transfer of high voltage into a low-voltage network. The danger of overvoltage lies in the occurrence of brief but powerful surge currents, which can cause breakdown of insulation not designed for such conditions. This paves the way for subsequent short circuits, sparking, or arcing. Furthermore, overvoltage accelerates the aging process of the insulation, reducing its service life and increasing the likelihood of future failure.

The interrelationship between emergency modes and their cumulative effect poses the greatest danger. A typical fire scenario may look like this:

overvoltage — localized insulation breakdown — increased leakage current and overheating (overload of the localized section) — thermal degradation and charring of the insulation — decreased resistance between the conductors (high contact resistance at the breakdown point) — sustained sparking — arcing — short circuit with massive energy release. Thus, an initially less dangerous phenomenon triggers a chain reaction leading to catastrophic failure.

Analysis shows that the main causes of electrical fires are not only dangerous in themselves but are also closely interrelated, forming cascading processes with a synergistic effect. The most vulnerable link, initiating most emergency sequences, is the insulation of cable and wire products. Its gradual degradation under the influence of operational factors creates the conditions for the transition from one emergency mode to another, more dangerous one. Therefore, effective fire prevention requires a shift from responding to short circuits or arcs that have already occurred to predictive diagnostics of early stages of degradation — monitoring parameters indicating overload, contact deterioration, or insulation aging. The development of comprehensive monitoring systems that take into account the interrelationships between all of these factors is a key area for ensuring fire safety in electrical installations.

Analysis of existing methods for assessing the state of insulation

Ensuring fire safety in electrical installations directly depends on the ability to promptly and accurately assess the technical condition of their key components. As described above, cable insulation degradation and increased contact resistance in contact connections are among the main causes of fault conditions leading to fire. Modern diagnostics aim to move beyond simply diagnosing faults and move toward predicting the remaining life of equipment and predictive maintenance. Below is an analysis of existing methods, their potential, and limitations.

Traditional approaches to insulation monitoring are often based on measuring basic parameters such as insulation resistance and dielectric loss tangent. These methods, regulated by regulatory documents, are widely available and relatively simple to implement. However, they are essentially indirect indicators of aging, recording changes that have already occurred (moisture, contamination, thermal degradation), but do not allow for a highly accurate prediction of how long the insulation will last before breakdown. Their main drawback is their reactive rather than predictive nature. In response to this problem, more complex non-destructive methods are being developed, which can be divided into several areas: predictive models based on parameter dynamics; methods adapted to combined effects; online monitoring methods in operating networks; and advanced relaxation spectroscopy.

Modern methods for assessing the condition of insulation are evolving from simple factual statements to comprehensive diagnostics and forecasting. A key area is

the development of predictive models based on the analysis of diagnostic parameter dynamics over time. For example, the active insulation resistance is used as a fundamental indicator. After measuring and normalizing the values to standard conditions (standardized length, standardized temperature), they are compared with a critical threshold. Shablovsky Ya. O. et al. [4] created a mathematical model describing the exponential nature of resistance degradation, which allows not only to assess current wear but also to calculate the remaining service life, classifying the aging mode as normal, accelerated, or delayed. This approach lays the foundation for moving from planned maintenance to a strategy based on the actual condition of the equipment.

To assess the durability of insulation in real-world, often aggressive, conditions, methods adapted to combined impacts are being developed. Particular attention is being paid to aging processes under increased pollution and humidity (for example, in coastal zones or industrial atmospheres). Accelerated testing setups simulating the effects of salt fog are being created in laboratory conditions. In the research of Yu. V. Solovyov, A. I. Tadjibaev, and A. N. Nazarychev [5], monitoring surface leakage currents becomes a key diagnostic feature, directly correlating with the intensity of surface tracking erosion — one of the main breakdown mechanisms of protected conductors.

Online monitoring methods that do not require equipment shutdown are of practical interest for operation. One such approach uses the analysis of zero-sequence currents that arise in the network when insulation deteriorates. To improve reliability and eliminate false signals from unbalanced loads, it is proposed to place measuring kits at both ends of the line. In their article [6], V. I. Biryulin, D. V. Kudelina, and O. M. Larin assess the insulation condition based on the difference in the active components of these currents: in a healthy line, the difference is close to zero, while its increase indicates a defect with a possible localized area. However, this method is most effective for detecting localized damage on short lines and may not detect uniform aging of the insulation along its entire length.

Relaxation spectroscopy provides the most in-depth analysis of structural changes in polymer insulation (polyethylene, cross-linked polyethylene). It is based on the study of the temperature-frequency dependences of the dielectric loss tangent. During aging, the maximum dielectric loss tangent in the α -relaxation region, associated with the mobility of macromolecular segments, shifts toward higher temperatures or lower frequencies. In their article [7], V. Kaniskin and A. Tadjibaev established a correlation between this shift and mechanical parameters such as cold-resistance temperature, which allows for a quantitative assessment of the degree of aging and the prediction of the remaining service life of actual cable sections without their destruction. Despite its high information content, widespread adoption of this method is hampered by the need for sophisticated diagnostic equipment and an extensive reference database.

The modern paradigm, reflected in current research, suggests abandoning solely scheduled preventive maintenance in favor of a strategy of maintenance and repair based on actual condition [8]. The key to this is a comprehensive assessment of the technical condition, taking into account not only the calendar service life but also integral indicators such as the condition index or the exhausted service life calculated based on diagnostic data.

Conclusion

The analysis confirms the existence of a systemic problem in the fire safety of electrical equipment, manifested by a steady increase in the number of electrical fires. The main causes of fires are interconnected emergency conditions that form cascading processes with a synergistic effect. The key vulnerability initiating the development of most hazardous sequences is insulation degradation in cable and wire products.

Existing traditional monitoring methods based on measuring insulation resistance and dielectric loss tangent are reactive in nature and do not effectively predict the progression of failures. Modern diagnostic approaches, such as predictive modeling based on parameter dynamics, online monitoring methods (e. g., zero-sequence current analysis), adapted testing for combined effects, and advanced relaxation spectroscopy, offer opportunities for transitioning to residual life assessment and predictive maintenance. However, their widespread adoption is hampered by the need for complex equipment, reference databases, and adaptation to specific site conditions. To fundamentally improve the fire safety of electrical installations, a paradigm shift is necessary: abandoning solely scheduled preventive maintenance in favor of a predictive risk management strategy. This requires the development and implementation of comprehensive monitoring systems that integrate various diagnostic methods for continuous condition assessment, early detection of insulation degradation and contact deterioration, and forecasting the likelihood of emergency situations. This approach will enable a shift from post-mortem response to proactive fire prevention, minimizing loss of life and property damage.

References

1. *Fire statistics and their consequences for 2024. Information and analytical collection: Fires and fire safety in 2024.* — Balashikha: FGBU VNIPO EMERCOM of Russia, 2025. — URL: <https://fireman.club/literature/statistika-pozharov-i-ih-posledstvij-za-2024-god/>.
2. *Causes of electrical injuries at work and measures to prevent them.* — URL: <https://moluch.ru/archive/247/56930>.

3. *The main electrical causes of fires from electrical equipment.* — URL: <https://medvedskoe-r49.gosweb.gosuslugi.ru/deyatelnost/napravleniya-deyatelnosti/go-i-chs/pozharnaya-bezopasnost/osnovnye-elektrotehnicheskie-prichiny-pozharov/>.

4. Shablovsky, Ya. O. *Prevention of emergency situations caused by aging of electrical insulation of cables and wires / Ya. O. Shablovsky, V. V. Kiselevich // Emergencies: education and science.* — 2014. — Vol. 9, No. 1. — P. 133–139.

5. Soloviev Yu. V., Tadjibaev A. I., Nazarichev A. N. *Method for assessing the state of protected wires during electrical aging under conditions of increased pollution and moisture // Global Energy.* — 2015. — No. 1 (214). — P. 114–122.

6. Biryulin V. I., Kudelina D. V., Larin O. M. *METHOD FOR MONITORING THE STATE OF INSULATION OF CABLE LINES // Bulletin of the Voronezh State Agrarian University.* — 2020. — Vol. 13. — No. 3. — P. 38–45.

7. Kaniskin V., Tadjibaev A. *Determination of the residual life of power cables by non-destructive diagnostics // Electrical Engineering News.* — 2003. — No. 2. — P. 34–41.

8. *Fire prevention in electrical installations based on technical diagnostics of electrical equipment: monograph / edited by Doctor of Technical Sciences, Professor A. N. Nazarichev.* — Ivanovo: FGBOU VO Ivanovo Fire and Rescue Academy of the GPS of the Ministry of Emergency Situations of Russia, 2020. — 270 p.

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**SENTIMENT ANALYSIS OF CUSTOMER TEXTS WITH
DISTILBERT:
PROBABILISTIC SCORING AND TOKEN-LEVEL
INTERPRETATION FOR BUSINESS DECISION-MAKING**

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Abstract. *Digital customer interaction channels generate large volumes of short texts: comments in social media, product and service reviews, answers in surveys. For businesses, it is important not only to automatically separate negative messages from positive ones, but also to understand how reliable the model's predictions are and which words determine its decisions. This paper considers the task of binary sentiment classification for English-language texts based on the Stanford Sentiment Treebank (SST-2) dataset, solved in the transfer learning paradigm using DistilBERT as a frozen feature extractor and a compact fully connected classifier. On a custom split of SST-2 into train/val/test subsets ($\approx 80/10/10$) the model reaches an accuracy of 0.8812, macro-F1 of 0.8797 and Matthew's correlation coefficient of 0.7590 on the test set, with nearly balanced quality across classes. Analysis of the distribution of predicted probabilities, a reliability diagram and Brier score, a cumulative gain curve, the relationship between errors and text length, and local token-level contribution interpretation shows how probabilistic scoring with calibration assessment and explainability turns the model from a "black box" into a controllable business analytics tool for review prioritization and reputation risk monitoring.*

Keywords: *sentiment analysis, DistilBERT, transfer learning, probability calibration, Brier score, cumulative gain, interpretability, customer reviews, VoC*

Modern companies process substantial volumes of text messages from customers: marketplace reviews, comments under brand posts, answers in NPS surveys, utterances in support chats, and so on. Sentiment analysis of these texts is viewed as a key instrument in Voice of Customer (VoC) programs as well as a standard component of data-driven marketing and customer experience management, since it enables timely detection of negative signals and tracking of satisfaction dynamics without manually reading the entire stream of messages [1]. At the same time, a single accuracy number is insufficient to support managerial decisions: interpretability of probabilistic estimates is required, together with their link to the planned volume of manual review and an understanding of which parts of the text most strongly determine the final classification.

As an experimental basis we use the SST-2 subtask from the GLUE benchmark [2], [3]. The corpus contains short sentences from movie reviews labelled as positive or negative [2]. In terms of structure these are typical user comments (one–two sentences with a subjective assessment). After merging the original train and validation portions and removing technical records, we obtain a dataset of 67,850 labelled examples without missing values, where the field *sentence* contains the text and *label* is a binary sentiment tag (0 for negative and 1 for positive reviews). Class distribution is moderately imbalanced (about 44% negative and 56% positive examples), which is consistent with published SST-2 statistics [2], [8] and allows a standard stratified split into train/val/test subsets in proportions of approximately 80/10/10.

Text representation is based on the DistilBERT transformer — a compact distilled version of BERT [4]. The model is used in feature-extraction mode: for each sentence we compute a 768-dimensional embedding from the CLS representation, and on top of these features we train a small fully connected classifier in Keras (one hidden layer with ReLU and dropout, sigmoid output). DistilBERT remains frozen; only the classifier parameters are updated, with training performed using binary cross-entropy and the Adam optimizer with early stopping on validation accuracy. This design combines the advantages of the transformer feature space with low complexity of the trainable part, which makes the model convenient for subsequent production integration [3], [4].

On the held-out test set the final model demonstrates comparable quality on both classes. For the negative class (label = 0), precision is 0.8600, recall 0.8743 and F1-score 0.8671. For the positive class (label = 1), precision is 0.8986, recall 0.8867 and F1-score 0.8926. Overall accuracy is 0.8812, macro-averaged F1-score 0.8797, weighted F1-score 0.8811, and Matthew’s correlation coefficient (MCC) 0.7590. The confusion matrix shows that 2,576 negative and 3,403 positive texts are classified correctly, while 374 negative texts are assigned to the positive class and 432 positive texts are assigned to the negative class. In an applied setting

where the target class is negative sentiment, this error structure can be interpreted as a moderate bias towards conservative behaviour: the system is somewhat more likely to miss part of the weakly negative signals than to systematically mark neutral or positive messages as problematic [1].

For practical use, not only the magnitude of aggregate metrics is important, but also the shape of the distribution of predicted probabilities. The histogram of the predicted probability of the positive class for truly negative and positive texts (Figure 1) shows that negative examples are concentrated in the region of low probability values, whereas positive ones lie predominantly in the right part of the interval, with a noticeable overlap zone at medium values.

Figure 1 — Distribution of predicted probabilities $P(\text{positive})$ by true class on the test set.

Such behaviour is typical of a reasonably strong yet not perfectly separating model: the class densities differ substantially, which makes it possible to select thresholds that prioritize the most confidently negative or positive messages; however, an intermediate uncertainty region inevitably remains. In a business context this means that comments with extreme probability values may be automatically

treated as clearly positive or clearly negative cases, whereas the boundary zone requires more careful threshold selection and, if necessary, implementation of selective manual inspection.

Figure 2 — Reliability diagram and Brier score for probabilities $P(\text{positive})$ on the test set.

Assessment of probability calibration represents the next key aspect of the analysis. Modern neural models often exhibit overconfidence: a predicted probability of 0.9 does not necessarily imply that roughly 90% of objects with this value truly belong to the corresponding class [5]. To verify the consistency of predicted probabilities with empirical frequencies we use a reliability diagram and the Brier score (Figure 2) [6].

The diagram is constructed by partitioning the interval $[0, 1]$ into a set of bins and, for each bin, computing the mean predicted probability of class 1 and the observed fraction of positive examples. In the ideal case, points lie on the diagonal $y = x$. In our diagram the values for all bins are in the immediate vicinity of the diagonal; local deviations up and down are small and do not form a pronounced systematic shift. The corresponding Brier score confirms that the predicted probabilities are, overall, well aligned with the observed shares of positive examples,

and any potential biases are moderate. For a manager responsible for service quality this means that, for example, the interval 0.1–0.2 of predicted probability of the positive class is indeed associated with a high share of problematic messages rather than reflecting arbitrary internal model scores [5], [6].

Translation of probabilistic predictions into managerial decisions can be conveniently illustrated using the cumulative gain curve. To construct it, test-set objects are sorted by the predicted probability of the target class (negative sentiment). The X-axis shows the fraction of inspected objects in the ranked list, and the Y-axis shows the fraction of truly negative examples already covered by inspection. The model curve is compared with the diagonal corresponding to random selection. In our experiment the model curve (Figure 3) lies above the diagonal over the entire interval: the top percentiles by probability contain a substantially larger proportion of the target class than random ordering.

Figure 3 — Cumulative gain curve for the negative class: share of detected negative messages when inspecting the top X % of the queue sorted by probability of negativity.

In operational terms this means that reviewing the top part of the list sorted by the predicted probability of negative sentiment makes it possible to cover a significant share of problematic messages while inspecting only a limited percentage of the overall stream. The support team can choose a point on the X-axis based on

available resources and pre-estimate the fraction of intercepted negative signals, which simplifies alignment of quality targets and workload.

In addition, we analyze how classification quality relates to text length and the model’s confidence. The scatter plot (Figure 4) displays, for each example, its length in tokens and the model confidence $\max(P(0), P(1))$, together with an indication of whether the prediction is correct. Visual inspection reveals that for very short texts (on the order of a few tokens) the error rate is noticeably higher: the model often must decide under minimal context. As text length increases, the cloud of points becomes “denser” in the area of high confidence and most examples are classified correctly. Errors on long utterances are present but have a rather scattered than cluster-like pattern.

Figure 4 — Dependence of model confidence and error occurrence on text length in the test set.

From the viewpoint of formalizing business rules this enables a simple operational guideline: very short one-word or extremely concise replies, as well as very long, elaborate comments, can be treated as a higher-risk group and routed to manual review irrespective of the predicted probability value.

The final component of trust in the system is the ability to answer the question of why the model made a particular decision. For local interpretation we employ a token influence analysis: for a chosen text, the model is run repeatedly on modified versions where individual words are removed one by one, and the change in the

probability of the positive class $\Delta P(1)$ is measured. If removal of a word decreases this probability, the corresponding token is interpreted as supporting positive sentiment; if it increases the probability, the token is treated as contributing to a negative assessment. Conceptually, this approach is close to LIME and other local interpretability methods for text models [7]. Figure 5 shows three examples of local interpretation: a correct prediction with high confidence, a confident model error, and a borderline case with a probability close to 0.5. For each text, tokens are plotted on the vertical axis and the change in probability of the positive class $\Delta P(1)$ after token removal on the horizontal axis. Positive values mean that the word increases the probability of a negative assessment (without it, the probability of class 1 grows), whereas negative values indicate that the token supports positive sentiment.

Figure 5 — Token-level influence of words on the probability of the positive class for three examples (correct prediction, confident error, borderline case); horizontal axis shows $\Delta P(\text{positive})$ after token removal.

The contribution diagrams show that the largest-magnitude effects on class probability are produced by content-bearing, emotionally charged words — adjectives and adverbs that express an evaluation — as well as connective phrases that modify the utterance context. In a correctly classified example, the model relies primarily on clearly positive markers, whereas in the misclassified case negative nuances are “overridden” by stronger positive indicators. The borderline example illustrates a situation where contributions of different tokens are roughly balanced, and the final decision becomes sensitive to small changes in wording. For an analyst, such breakdowns on the one hand confirm that the model relies on sentiment cues that are interpretable from a domain perspective, and on the other hand make it possible to identify typical error patterns and refine both model parameters and business rules for its use.

Taken together, the described module constitutes a complete solution for sentiment analysis of customer texts that can be integrated into a digital business ecosystem. The practical novelty of the approach lies in the fact that a standard DistilBERT-based transfer learning pipeline is used not only to achieve high accuracy, but also to explicitly link probabilistic predictions to service management parameters: the share of intercepted negative messages, the volume of manual review, and a set of typical classification cases. The compact fully connected classifier on top of frozen embeddings provides sufficient flexibility to tune the system to the customer’s target business metrics, while the suite of visual diagnostics — distribution of predicted probabilities (Figure 1), calibration diagram with Brier score (Figure 2), cumulative gain curve (Figure 3), dependence of errors on text length (Figure 4) and local analysis of individual examples via token contributions (Figure 5) — turns the model from an opaque “black box” into a controllable analytical instrument. At the same time, the results are limited to an English-language corpus of short movie reviews (SST-2) and a binary sentiment scheme. Transferability of the conclusions to other domains, languages and more complex rating scales requires additional model adaptation and subsequent probability calibration on corporate data of a specific company. As further work, the approach may be extended to multi-class sentiment schemes and specialized sectoral domains (for example, reviews of financial products or medical services), as well as complemented by more advanced post-processing and calibration methods (Platt scaling, isotonic regression) and interpretability tools in production scenarios [1], [5], [7].

References

1. Medhat W., Hassan A., Korashy H. *Sentiment analysis algorithms and applications* // *Ain Shams Engineering Journal*. 2014. Vol. 5, No. 4. P. 1093–1113.
2. Socher R. et al. *Recursive Deep Models for Semantic Compositionality Over a Sentiment Treebank* // *Proceedings of EMNLP*. 2013. P. 1631–1642.
3. Wang A. et al. *GLUE: A Multi-Task Benchmark and Analysis Platform for Natural Language Understanding* // *Proceedings of ICLR*. 2019.
4. Sanh V. et al. *DistilBERT, a distilled version of BERT: smaller, faster, cheaper and lighter* // *arXiv preprint arXiv:1910.01108*. 2019.
5. Guo C., Pleiss G., Sun Y., Weinberger K. Q. *On Calibration of Modern Neural Networks* // *Proceedings of ICML*. 2017. P. 1321–1330.
6. Brier G. W. *Verification of Forecasts Expressed in Terms of Probability* // *Monthly Weather Review*. 1950. Vol. 78, No. 1. P. 1–3.
7. Ribeiro M. T., Singh S., Guestrin C. “*Why Should I Trust You?*”: *Explaining the Predictions of Any Classifier* // *Proceedings of KDD*. 2016. P. 1135–1144.
8. *Hugging Face Datasets*. *stanfordnlp/sst2*. URL: <https://huggingface.co/datasets/stanfordnlp/sst2>.

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PROMISING OPPORTUNITIES FOR INTERNATIONAL BUSINESS IN RUSSIA: INTERNATIONAL TERRITORIES OF ADVANCED DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: *in the context of turbulence in the global economy and instability in the international investment sphere, the Russian economy provides additional opportunities for international business by creating a regulatory framework for investing in international priority development areas (PDAs).*

Key words: *international business, global economy, investments, preferential regime, international territories of advanced development.*

The escalation of geopolitical tensions between the Global South and the West is negatively impacting the investment sector of the global economy. This is reflected in a decline in foreign direct investment (FDI) in the global economy: in 2024, the overall decline in global FDI was 11% compared to 2023 [1].

After 2022, the Russian economy saw a reorientation of FDI flows from West to East. While Western companies were the main investors in the Russian economy before 2022, they were replaced by companies from the Middle East (Turkey, UAE, Oman), Asia (Hong Kong, China), and the CIS (Armenia, Kazakhstan, Belarus, Kyrgyzstan) [2]. This reorientation contributed to the fact that, after an FDI outflow of \$ 15.2 billion in 2022, FDI in the Russian economy increased in 2024 and amounted to \$ 3,346 million [3].

To stimulate FDI inflows, countries offer various tools to enhance the investment attractiveness of their economies for foreign investors. One such tool is the creation of territories with preferential regimes.

In 2014, the concept of “priority development areas” (PDAs) was introduced into Russian legislation. These areas offer a special legal regime for conducting business and other activities in order to create favorable conditions for attracting investment and ensuring accelerated socio-economic development in specific territories across various regions of the country. These areas, with preferential treatment, are created by decision of the Government of the Russian Federation,

upon the recommendation of regional authorities, for a period of 70 years with the right to subsequent extension. Unlike special economic zones (SEZs), whose status was legally enshrined in Russia in 2005, PDAs are a more flexible tool for attracting investment for the development of a specific territory, which has proven itself in Russia's regions. By the end of 2024, according to the Russian Ministry of Economic Development, 92 PDAs had been created in Russia, attracting over 441 billion rubles in investment, and the revenue of PDAs residents amounted to over 1,939 billion rubles [4]. Successfully operating priority development areas are located in the single-industry towns of Kostomuksha, Naberezhnye Chelny, Sarapul, Cherepovets, and other single-industry towns in Russia.

Innovations for 2025 include an increase in the number of investment promotion tools for the development of Russia's geostrategic territory — the Far Eastern Federal District, a border region geographically close to the countries of the Asia-Pacific macroregion. Among the most significant investment tools are the PDAs, which will be established starting in January 2026 in the Amur Region, the Jewish Autonomous Region, and Primorsky, Transbaikal, and Khabarovsk Krai.

The implementation of a new instrument for attracting FDI to Russia's Far East is driven by several factors: first, to intensify investment processes in Russia's vast territories, which boast a significant resource base, and to integrate these resources into economic circulation; second, to create high-tech jobs for Russian citizens with a high level of education and qualifications; third, to strengthen economic cooperation and collaboration with countries of the Asia-Pacific region (APR), expand integration ties with countries of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO), and practically implement the concept of a Greater Eurasian Partnership; and fourth, to accumulate experience in the functioning of the PDA and test the effectiveness of the PDA concept itself before expanding it to other regions of Russia.

The creation of the International Development Initiative (IDI) reflects Russia's strategic approach to selecting high-tech investment projects when attracting FDI. In the 1990s, any influx of FDI was considered an economic benefit for the host country. Currently, a different government approach prevails: FDI should serve the national interests and technological development of the country. Russia's experience attracting FDI has shown that the advantages of FDI in attracting advanced technologies, as declared in investment theory, have not been borne out in the implementation of a number of investment projects. Moreover, the events of 2022 demonstrated the unreliability of foreign investors from countries that act unfriendly toward Russia. Seeking to create a crisis in the Russian economy, enterprises with foreign investment closed and left the Russian market [5]. In this regard, the role of government policy regarding the admission of FDI into the national economy is increasing.

FDI investments should result in high-value-added products in demand in high-tech markets in Russia and around the world, manufactured with consideration for

the global economy's transition to a new technological paradigm — Industry 5.0. This paradigm is defined by the entrenchment of Industry 4.0 advances (electric vehicles, robotics, 5G, digitalization, artificial intelligence, etc.), but is aimed at addressing the accumulated contradictions in the modern biotechnoecosystem associated with the implementation and widespread use of Industry 4.0 technologies.

The presence of the PDA in the border areas of Russia and China allows companies to take advantage of their proximity and reduce transaction and logistics costs. The PDA's preferential treatment ensures high potential returns for investment projects implemented by PDA residents. However, obtaining these preferences and PDA resident status requires capital investments of at least 500 million rubles. This opens up new opportunities for large high-tech international businesses with innovative ideas and production plans necessary to accelerate the development of the Russian economy. However, for small high-tech businesses, such capital investments will be virtually unaffordable.

The PDA is legally defined as a Russian territory with certain preferential treatment compared to other regimes (the SEZB TOR, the Free Port of Vladivostok, etc.) in terms of administrative, customs, and tax regulations. The total permitted area of the PDA is fixed at 20 square kilometers, sufficient to accommodate production facilities for high-value-added products.

Foreign investors' concerns about "secondary" sanctions illegally imposed by Western countries were taken into account when granting PDA residency status, the lists of which are not publicly available. By establishing a subsidiary to operate in the PDA or by obtaining PDA residency status in their own name, a foreign investor is not included in Russian information systems, and their information is confidential. Furthermore, for 15 years from the date of inclusion in the PDA residency register, PDA residents are not subject to state or municipal decisions that worsen the conditions for doing business, as stipulated in the agreement governing their activities in this territory.

New opportunities for international businesses to implement investment projects approved by the Presidium of the Government Commission for the Socioeconomic Development of the Far East are emerging in the area of taxation for PDA residents. A 10-year period for the preferential zero-rate income tax has been introduced by law. A significant potential for increasing the profitability of investment projects is provided by reducing insurance premiums to 7.6% of the payroll for a period of 10 years.

Subject to certain restrictions, PDA residents will receive additional benefits for customs clearance of imported and exported goods and material assets, in the form of exemptions from key customs procedures. This special preference, such as a free customs zone, will reduce business costs and logistics time.

Currently, Chinese, Belarusian companies and high-tech companies from friendly Asia-Pacific countries are showing interest in obtaining PDA resident status.

When creating a Far Eastern Economic Zone (MEZ) in the Far Eastern District, it is necessary to consider international competition for FDI. Many countries in the Asia-Pacific region have had zones with preferential regimes for foreign investors for many years. Therefore, Russian legislation on PDAs takes into account international experience, largely copying best practices. However, new PDAs must possess competitive advantages that existing PDAs in China, Vietnam, Malaysia, and other Asia-Pacific countries lack. Location, resource base, preferences, and confidentiality contribute to the attractiveness and competitive advantages of Far Eastern PDAs. However, in terms of economic preferences, foreign investors are offered a fairly standard set. Launching MTORs in new investment locations for foreign investors requires a more creative approach and innovative proposals for foreign investors, including access to government procurement of high-tech products, guaranteed sales, and the inclusion of innovative foreign and Russian small businesses as residents.

Thus, with the creation of the International Trade and Development Zone (ITDZ), international businesses from friendly countries have new, promising opportunities for investing in the Russian economy.

References

1. *World Investment Report 2025: International investment in the digital economy*. URL: https://unctad.org/system/files/official-document/wir2025_en.pdf (date of application 11/28/2025)
2. Platonova E. D. *International business in the Russian economy: history and new trajectories* / E. D. Platonova // *Transformation of the strategy of economic development of the Russian Federation taking into account the trajectories of global development: monograph* / edited by Z. O. Adamanova. — Simferopol, 2025. P. 165–225.
3. *Incoming Foreign Direct Investment: Russia*. URL: / URL: <https://statbase.ru/data/rus-foreign-direct-investment-inflows/> (date accessed 25.11.2025)
4. *Territory of advanced development*. URL: https://economy.gov.ru/material/directions/regionalnoe_razvitie/instruments_razvitiya_territoriy/tor/# (accessed November 20, 2025)
5. Platonova, E. D. *Foreign direct investment in the global economy: current trends and prospects* / E. D. Platonova // *Fundamental research*. — 2025. — No. 10. — P. 57–62. — DOI 10.17513/fr:43916

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5.2.3

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STRATEGIES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE REGIONAL INNOVATION INFRASTRUCTURE OF THE SKOLKOVO FOUNDATION'S ECOSYSTEM IN THE SYSTEM OF STATE PROJECTS IN THE RUSSIAN FEDERATION

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Abstract: *The article is devoted to the analysis of the development of Russia's innovative infrastructure in the regions, the problems of economic growth in the Russian Federation, based on the implementation of innovations, the training of regional labor resources, and the development of Skolkovo branches. The article also examines the participation of the Skolkovo Foundation as an element of Russia's innovative system, which ensures and supports these processes. Additionally, the Skolkovo Foundation serves as a tool for developing the competencies of labor resources in the regions, which contributes to the implementation of innovative technologies in various sectors of the country's economy.*

Keywords: *innovative infrastructure, problems of economic growth in the Russian Federation, development of labor resources, Skolkovo Foundation*

Introduction

The innovation ecosystem created by the Skolkovo Foundation is aimed at achieving the key goals outlined in the subprogram «Creation and Development of the Skolkovo Innovation Center» within the framework of the state program «Economic Development and Innovative Economy» of the Russian Federation [1]. These objectives include attracting investment in the high-tech sector, promoting the development of technology companies, and supporting their research and development activities. The Skolkovo Innovation Center is a territory and ecosystem that includes mechanisms for interaction between project participants and an infrastructure conducive to research and the commercialization of its results.

The scientific and technical potential of the Skolkovo Innovation Center is determined by the research and development centers of its industrial partners and the Skolkovo Institute of Science and Technology, established in 2011 as a key element of the system of development institutions. Its mission is to ensure technology transfer, develop, and replicate competencies that are underrepresented in Russia but are essential for modernization and enhancing the technological competitiveness of the country's economy.

Goals and objectives of the regional development strategy of the Skolkovo Foundation (Fig. 1):

Support for technological entrepreneurship in Russia and commercialization of research results [3]:

Creating and maintaining an attractive and self-reproducing innovation ecosystem aimed at increasing the effectiveness of interaction between its main elements: participants, industrial partners, investment institutions, and research and development centers

Establishing a network of official representatives of the Foundation in the regions to expand the opportunities for providing Skolkovo services to technology companies in the regions

Helping high-tech companies from Skolkovo transform from local industry leaders into global players recognized in the global market

Figure 1. Scheme of commercialization of the Skolkovo project.

The main goal of the Skolkovo Foundation in the context of regional development is to create a network of official representatives in various regions of Russia.

This significantly expands the Skolkovo Foundation’s ability to provide services to technology companies, regardless of their geographic location. An important objective is to ensure access to the Foundation’s cutting-edge innovative services and resources for all participants in the innovation ecosystem, thereby facilitating the balanced development of innovation across the country (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Structure of the Skolkovo ecosystem

The Skolkovo Regional Operator [4] is a regional technology park or other innovative infrastructure facility that develops the regional innovation ecosystem in accordance with the standards and practices of the Skolkovo Foundation. The regional operator’s primary functions include supporting innovative projects, localizing Skolkovo services, conducting educational and mentoring programs, and assisting in the commercialization of developments.

A regional representative is the official representative of the Skolkovo Foundation in the region, responsible for identifying new projects, commercializing the Foundation’s services, and synchronizing support measures. In regions without regional operators, regional representatives may be individuals appointed by the

governor. These representatives play a key role in identifying promising projects and integrating them into the Skolkovo ecosystem.

Regional operators and representatives are accredited by the Skolkovo Foundation in accordance with the requirements set forth in the Regulations on Interaction with Regional Operators and the Regulations on Regional Representatives. Accreditation ensures compliance with the Foundation's standards and guarantees the high quality of services provided.

The Skolkovo Foundation creates conditions for effective interaction with regional operators and representatives who play a key role in developing the innovation ecosystem at the regional level.

The main functions of regional operators and representatives include:

Formation of a project funnel

Increasing the number of project participants from your region.

Search and attraction of promising innovative projects.

Localization of Skolkovo services:

Ensuring accessibility of all Skolkovo services and facilities for resident companies at the regional level.

Adaptation of services to local conditions and needs.

Resident support:

Providing consulting and mentoring services.

Assistance in attracting investments and orders from industrial partners.

Assistance in protecting intellectual property and commercializing developments.

Conducting innovative events:

Organizing and conducting technology events and project pitch sessions for investors or business community representatives.

Participation in large-scale events and exhibitions.

Consulting for corporations and industrial partners on the regional development strategy of the Skolkovo Foundation ecosystem within the Russian Federation's innovative infrastructure development system for state projects.

The Skolkovo Foundation defines the following key functions for regional operators and representatives:

1) Formation of a project funnel

Regional operators and representatives should actively seek out and attract promising innovative projects, increasing the number of project participants from their region. This includes monitoring local innovation activity and engaging with local startups.

2) Localization of services to support technology companies

Regional operators are obligated to ensure the availability of all Skolkovo services at the regional level, adapting them to local conditions and needs. This includes creating infrastructure and conditions for effective support of innovative companies.

3) Support for residents with Skolkovo services:

Operators must provide residents with consulting and mentoring services, assist in attracting investment and orders from industrial partners, and assist in protecting intellectual property and commercializing developments.

4) Conducting innovative events:

Regional operators are required to regularly organize and conduct technology events, such as project pitch sessions for investors or business community representatives, and participate in large-scale events and exhibitions organized by Skolkovo.

Target audience of the regional development strategy:

Students

Startups

Universities

Industrial companies

Innovative infrastructure (Technoparks)

The Skolkovo Foundation plays a significant role in the Russian Federation's system of state projects to develop innovative infrastructure both domestically and internationally. The Foundation's effective, multifaceted work contributes not only to the creation of a favorable environment for innovation in Russia but also to the active participation of Russian technology companies in the international arena.

Conclusion: By supporting investment, creating infrastructure, and attracting leading global companies to the Skolkovo Innovation Center, the Foundation is fostering the formation of an integrated ecosystem capable of addressing key economic development challenges and enhancing the country's competitiveness. Projects implemented by the Foundation are focused on creating high-tech solutions capable of demonstrating significant economic impact and meeting strategic national goals.

Thus, the Skolkovo Foundation's efforts not only stimulate the development of innovative entrepreneurship and knowledge-intensive industries within the country, but also contribute to strengthening the international presence of Russian technologies and expertise, making it a key player in the global innovation arena.

References

1. *Resolution of the Government of the Russian Federation of April 15, 2014 No. 316 (as amended on November 20, 2025) «On approval of the state program of the Russian Federation «Economic Development and Innovative Economy» (as amended and supplemented, entered into force on November 28, 2025) [https://www.consultant.ru/document/cons_d\)oc_LAW_162191](https://www.consultant.ru/document/cons_d)oc_LAW_162191) (date of access December 6, 2025)*

2. Ershova N.A., Pavlov S. N. *Public administration and innovation policy.* — M.: RGUP, 2018. — 32 p.

3. *Development of technological entrepreneurship* https://www.economy.gov.ru/material/directions/np_effektivnaya_i_konkurentnaya_ekonomika/fp_razvitie_tehnologicheskogo_predprinimatelstva/ (accessed 06.12. 2025)

4. *Regional operators* <https://sk.ru/foundation/international/regions/regops/> (accessed 06.12. 2025)

5. *Regional development* <https://sk.ru/foundation/international/regions/> (accessed 06.12. 2025)

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BALANCE SHEET AS THE MAIN FORM OF REPORTING

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Abstract. *This article examines the role of the balance sheet in the financial reporting system and its importance for understanding an organization's performance. The balance sheet is viewed as a convenient and visual form that allows for a clear understanding of an organization's assets and the sources from which its resources are generated. It is emphasized that this reporting form remains relevant, even as entrepreneurship becomes faster and more complex, and information users demand greater transparency. The article explores the theoretical foundations of the balance sheet and its place among other reporting forms, describes the structure of assets and liabilities and their interrelationships, and reflects on the practical application of the balance sheet in analyzing an organization's performance and its importance for decision-making. Additionally, attention is paid to the limitations of the balance sheet and the need for its further improvement in the context of digitalization and increasing demands on the quality of reporting.*

Keywords: *balance sheet, reporting, assets, liabilities, financial position.*

The balance sheet of an enterprise is one of the key forms of financial reporting. It allows a person to clearly understand the economic position of an organization at a given point in time. The balance sheet is a table that, on the one hand, reflects the company's assets, i.e., the financial statements. All resources at its disposal, while liabilities represent the sources of their formation. Assets include tangible and intangible assets, cash, accounts receivable, as well as investments and other resources that could generate economic benefit for the enterprise. Liabilities, in turn, represent equity, liabilities to creditors, and other sources of financing.

The role of the balance sheet in the reporting system is difficult to overestimate. This is because it serves as the starting point for financial analysis, allowing one to assess the liquidity, solvency, and financial stability of an organization. It can be used to determine how effectively certain resources are being used, which areas of activity are generating income, and which still require optimization.

A properly constructed balance sheet:

- fully encompasses the business process in all its diversity;
- properly groups economic phenomena in accordance with the nature and purpose of the organization;
- to study the relationship between these phenomena and establish the correct correspondence between accounts, which will allow us to examine not only the financial position of the business owner but also the financial result [1].

Furthermore, the balance sheet is an important tool for interacting with external users of financial information. Investors, creditors, government agencies, and potential partners rely on the balance sheet when making decisions about investments, loans, or transactions.

The balance sheet is distinguished by its versatility and standardized form, which allows for the comparison of indicators across different organizations, including those in different industries.

For the balance sheet to be informative and the information contained therein to meet the needs of financial statement users, information about the company's financial position must be fully disclosed in accordance with the established structure and principles of preparation [3].

The balance sheet is compiled based on the accounting principles reflected in Table 1. Among these, the principle of double entry is paramount. This ensures the interrelationship of indicators and makes it possible to quickly identify deviations, errors, or inconsistencies in accounting.

Table 1 - Accounting principles

Name of principles	The essence of accounting principles
Double entry	Every business transaction is reflected simultaneously in assets and liabilities.
Separateness	The organization is treated as an independent entity, and only its assets and liabilities are reflected in the balance sheet.
Going concern	It is assumed that the company will continue to operate for the foreseeable future.
Monetary measurement	All accounting items are expressed in a single monetary unit.
Prudence	Potential losses are recognized in advance, and income is reported only when there is a high degree of certainty.
Reliability	The essence of this approach lies in supporting data with documents and accurately reflecting business facts.
Comparability	The need for consistent accounting.
Periodicity	Financial statements are prepared for specific periods (month, quarter, year) to assess the financial position.

Particular attention should be paid to the frequency of balance sheet preparation. Typically, a balance sheet is prepared at the end of the reporting period, allowing for the identification of trends in financial performance. Using a balance sheet in management activities helps make strategic decisions, adjust budgets, and plan cash flows. It can be used to assess risks, forecast financial needs, and optimize capital structure.

Thus, the balance sheet performs several functions: control, analytical, informational, and others. It not only reflects the status of assets and liabilities but also serves as a tool for planning, decision-making, and interaction with external stakeholders.

Furthermore, the preparation of a balance sheet is based on regulatory legal acts that establish the forms, deadlines, and rules for its preparation. Of central importance is the Federal Law “On Accounting” dated December 6, 2011, No. 402-FZ [4]. Accounting and reporting are also regulated by federal accounting standards (FAS) and accounting regulations (PRB). In particular, FASB 4/2023 “Accounting (Financial) Reporting” defines the composition, content, and procedure for preparing enterprise financial statements [5].

The primary requirement for compiling a balance sheet is its division into assets and liabilities.

Balance sheet assets are a system of indicators reflecting the composition, placement, and use of business assets, grouped into qualitatively homogeneous categories [2].

The asset section includes resources capable of generating economic benefits in the future. The primary content of assets is formed by property, cash, rights, and other valuables owned by the enterprise. This approach helps to understand the real foundation upon which production and financial potential are built.

Asset composition is traditionally divided into two groups: non-current and current assets. Non-current assets are resources that are used for a long period of time—more than one year. These include buildings, structures, machinery, equipment, land, intangible assets (IA), including patents, licenses, software, and long-term financial investments. These resources form the foundation of the production process and are not intended for quick sale or conversion into cash. Their value is gradually repaid through depreciation, reflecting wear and tear and the distribution of costs over time.

Current assets, in contrast, are characterized by a high degree of liquidity. This category includes inventories of raw materials, supplies, goods, work in progress, finished goods, accounts receivable, and cash. They contribute to current turnover and ensure business continuity. Current assets can be quickly converted into cash, making them a key factor in assessing current solvency. Accounts receivable represent amounts due from customers or other counterparties, while cash reflects the organization's immediate financial capacity. The higher the proportion of liquid assets, the easier it is for the company to meet short-term obligations and avoid cash flow gaps.

Liquid assets should also be arranged from the least current to the most mobile. This arrangement allows for an analysis of the organization's ability to quickly respond to financial challenges. A significant share of non-current assets demonstrates the investment nature of the business and long-term strategic goals, while a high proportion of current assets may indicate active trading or production activities.

The balance between these types of resources is crucial for business sustainability. A shortage of non-current assets can hinder development, while excessive accumulation of inventory or accounts receivable creates the risk of liquidity loss.

This approach to dividing the asset side of the balance sheet helps to understand the real basis upon which production and financial potential are built.

Analyzing the asset structure allows us to assess the organization's strategy: whether it is focused on long-term investments, accelerated capital turnover, or maintaining financial flexibility.

The balance sheet's assets help evaluate not only the current state of resources but also the effectiveness of their management. For example, an increase in accounts receivable may indicate problems with payment deadlines. An increase in inventory indicates a sales slowdown or an over-purchase. A change in the structure of non-current assets signals production modernization or infrastructure

expansion. Consequently, the composition of assets becomes an important information base for management decision-making, financial analysis, and long-term planning.

On the other hand, the balance sheet's liabilities reflect the sources from which an organization's resources are generated. The structure of liabilities is crucial for assessing sustainability, risk, and financial independence [6].

Liabilities consist of equity and liabilities (short-term and long-term). This division helps understand the financial nature of capital and assess the degree of a business's dependence on external sources.

Equity reflects the portion of it that belongs to the organization. It includes authorized capital, additional capital, retained earnings, and reserves.

Liabilities reflect the organization's debts to banks, suppliers, government agencies, employees, and other counterparties. They are divided into long-term and short-term. Sources such as long-term liabilities are typically used for large projects, production modernization, or business expansion. Their presence indicates long-term plans and an investment focus. However, a high proportion of long-term debt increases the financial burden in the future and also requires stable income.

Unlike long-term liabilities, short-term liabilities are repaid within a year. These liabilities are closely linked to operating activities and change regularly. To assess solvency, it is important to compare short-term liabilities with current assets, since current assets are used to repay them.

The structure of liabilities reflects the organization's financial strategy. A predominance of equity indicates independence and high stability, but may indicate limited growth due to a lack of external investment. A significant amount of borrowed funds allows for accelerated development, production expansion, and the development of new markets, but increases the risks associated with interest payments and liabilities [8].

Thus, the balance between equity and borrowed funds is considered an important indicator of financial health.

Liabilities are an integral part of a company's financial picture. It demonstrates the stability of a business, its ability to independently finance development, and the level of risk associated with its activities. Thanks to the liabilities side, users of the statements can draw conclusions about the organization's future financial position.

Overall, the balance sheet serves as the primary source of information for assessing an organization's financial stability. Using balance sheet data to analyze financial stability plays a key role for both internal and external users of the statements. It allows for an objective understanding of the company's solvency, risk level, and ability to develop without jeopardizing financial stability. Balance sheet

analysis helps formulate strategic and operational decisions aimed at maintaining stability, increasing profitability, and effectively managing capital.

The balance sheet data is the basis for calculating many indicators necessary for analysis. These include liquidity ratios, financial stability ratios, asset turnover, and return on equity. These indicators enable the prompt identification of deviations and the implementation of corrective actions.

Using the balance sheet as a management tool improves the efficiency of the enterprise and reduces the risk of resource misallocation. It provides a clear understanding of financial capabilities and liabilities, creates a basis for strategic planning, and improves interaction with external users of the statements.

Nevertheless, the balance sheet has a number of limitations that affect the completeness and accuracy of an organization's financial assessment. These limitations include the static nature of the data [7]. This is evident in the fact that the balance sheet reflects the position of assets and liabilities only on a specific date, without showing the dynamics of cash flows during the reporting period. This means that it does not always provide a complete picture of current financial flows, the rate of resource turnover, and the actual liquidity of the enterprise. Therefore, to obtain a more complete picture, it is necessary to compare the balance sheet with the profit and loss statement, cash flow statement, and other financial documents.

Another limitation is the principle of monetary measurement. All assets and liabilities are valued in monetary terms, which simplifies analysis but does not always allow for the qualitative characteristics of resources to be taken into account. For example, intangible assets such as reputation, brand, or customer base may be of significant value to a company but are not fully reflected on the balance sheet [9]. This creates a gap in assessing the company's potential and competitive advantages.

The balance sheet also fails to reflect risks associated with the economic environment, price changes, inflation, or exchange rate fluctuations. Despite the inclusion of items devoted to reserves and adjustments, it is not always able to fully reveal threats to the organization's financial stability.

Another limitation is the dependence of data accuracy on the accuracy of accounting. Errors in valuation and classification of assets and liabilities, or the untimely recording of transactions can distort indicators and lead to incorrect conclusions.

Areas for improving the balance sheet are related to the implementation of new approaches and technologies. Digitalization of accounting processes allows for more accurate and timely accounting, the integration of data from various sources, and the creation of interactive reporting forms.

Further improvements to the balance sheet are associated with expanded information on intangible assets, risks, and future liabilities. The introduction of

disclosures and explanatory notes helps financial statement users better understand the structure of resources and liabilities, assess risk, and plan actions. Increased transparency and data detail facilitate more accurate management decisions, enhance trust with external users, and strengthen the organization's financial stability.

As a result, the balance sheet occupies a central place in the financial reporting system. Analyzing its structure allows us to identify the strengths and weaknesses of financial performance, assess liquidity, solvency, and the degree of financial independence. The balance sheet serves not only as an internal management tool but also as a means of communication with external financial statement users, including investors, creditors, and government agencies.

It creates a basis for an objective assessment of resources and liabilities, maintains transparency and trust among all economic participants, and contributes to strengthening financial stability and effective capital management in a dynamic economic environment.

References

1. Amraeva, A. *Balance Sheet as the Main Form of Financial Reporting* / A. Amraeva // *Statistics, Accounting and Audit*. 2012. No. 2. pp. 27-31.
2. Mamoshina, O.V. *Balance Sheet as the Main Form of Financial Reporting (Part 1)* / O.V. Mamoshina // *Socio-Economic Phenomena and Processes*. 2013. No. 2 (048). pp. 67-73.
3. Mukhametzyanov, R.Z. *Balance Sheet as the Main Form of Financial Reporting* / R.Z. Mukhametzyanov, D.R. Khusainova // *Kazan Science*. 2017. No. 5. pp. 67-70.
4. *On accounting: Federal Law of 06.12.2011 No. 402-FZ (latest revision)* // *ConsultantPlus*. - URL: https://www.consultant.ru/document/cons_doc_LAW_122855/ (date of access: 08.12.2025).
5. *Federal Accounting Standard (FAS) 4/2023 "Accounting (Financial) Reporting"* (introduced in the Russian Federation by Order of the Ministry of Finance of Russia dated 04.10.2023 No. 157n) // *ConsultantPlus*. - URL: https://www.consultant.ru/document/cons_doc_LAW_472684/552e4f85ef02bf4fd-75d2ee6d478849e354d4dc9/ (date of access: 08.12.2025).
6. *Balance Sheet: Assets and Liabilities, Sections and Types [Electronic resource]*. - URL: https://nalog-nalog.ru/buhgalterskaya_otchetnost/godovaya_buhgalterskaya_otchetnost/buhgalterskij_balans_aktiv_i_passiv_razdely_vidy-23/ (date of access: 08.12.2025).
7. *How to Prepare a Balance Sheet [Electronic resource]*. - URL: <https://www.rbc.ru/base/10/07/2025/686cd88c9a7947146df28108> (date of access: 08.12.2025).

8. *Liabilities - the structure of balance sheet liabilities and their impact on the company's financial stability [Electronic resource]. - URL: <https://copy-mate.app/ru/blog/multi/%D0%BF%D0%B0%D1%81%D1%81%D0%B8%D0%B2%D1%8B-%D1%81%D1%82%D1%80%D1%83%D0%BA%D1%82%D1%83%D1%80%D0%B0-%D0%BF%D0%B0%D1%81%D1%81%D0%B8%D0%B2%D0%BE%D0%B2-%D0%B1%D0%B0%D0%BB%D0%B0%D0%BD%D1%81%D0%B0-%D0%B8/> (date of access: 08.12.2025).*

9. *What are non-current and current assets of an enterprise? [Electronic resource]. - URL: <https://ppt.ru/art/aktivy-i-obyazatelstva/chto-takoe-vneoborotnye-i-oborotnye-aktivy> (date of access: 08.12.2025).*

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FORMATION OF THE CONCEPT OF THE ECONOMY OF NATURE-LIKE TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract. *This article proposes a theoretical concept for the formation and development of a nature-based technology economy. Its socioeconomic essence is clarified. The development of nature-based technologies as artificially created “nature-like” production processes is revealed. Their key features are defined, and the advantages and benefits of their application in the modern economy are explored. The author’s concept of the essence of the “efficiency of a nature-based technology economy” is proposed. The development of criteria for assessing its effectiveness is described.*

Key words: *innovative economy; nature-like technologies; renewable technologies; recycling of economic resources; synergistic effect; efficiency of nature-like technologies.*

In the information and digital age, when scientific and technological progress has created the preconditions for revolutionary technological changes, one of the pressing problems remains the problem of developing the concept of an environmentally efficient economy based on the use of nature-like technologies.

The relevance of this issue is due to the large-scale processes of destruction of the natural environment as a consequence of the widespread introduction of industrial and information-digital technologies into the modern economy in the absence of effective tools for its restoration.

The nature-based approach is becoming especially relevant today in the process of the ever-widening spread of the latest industrial and information-digital technologies in economic activity, which often ignore the objective laws of nature and existence.

The relevance of the problem of forming economic systems of nature-like technologies has been repeatedly emphasized in the speeches of the President of the Russian Federation V. V. Putin: on September 28, 2015, at the plenary session of the 70th UN General Assembly, Vladimir Putin stated that in order to overcome the environmental crisis, it is necessary to use nature-like technologies in order to create a technosphere that harmoniously coexists with the biosphere and regional ecosystems; [5] in 2019 At the Global Manufacturing and Industrialization Summit (GMIS), Vladimir Putin noted that governments, scientists, and businesses must join forces in technological development and the development of nature-like technologies [7]. In 2023, Russian President Vladimir Putin signed a decree instructing the government to develop and approve an action plan for the development of nature-like technologies in Russia within six months [13].

The current situation urgently requires the search, development, and substantiation of new concepts for economic development based on fundamentally new nature-like technologies that would, to the greatest possible extent, ensure co-evolution and harmonious coexistence with the environment based on technologies for resolving the essential contradictions between the technological capabilities of society and the biosphere.

Currently, in scientific publications, many researchers note that the majority of technologies created by humanity in the process of historical development, used in the economy, are torn "... from the natural context, and are essentially poor copies of natural processes." [2] To overcome the consequences of the global technological crisis, new qualitative changes are needed, a leap forward, a transition to completely different principles of production and consumption, modeled on and similar to natural processes, which are capable of changing the entire appearance of the technosphere.

According to M. Kovalchuk, President of the National Research Center "Kurchatov Institute", the emergence of nature-like technologies "... is the pinnacle of technological evolution. They grew out of the synergy of scientific fields and opened

up opportunities for the creation of a nature-like technosphere and the solution of the greatest problems of our time..." [6].

At present, Russian economic science and practice are faced with the extremely urgent task of developing one of the most pressing problems of our time — the problem of economic development. Nature-like technologies, adequate to a fundamentally new technological era of human development — the information-digital technological mode of production and consumption [9].

In studying the semantic essence of the concept of "economy of nature-like technologies," an etymological approach was used, which allowed us to give the following definition: economics nature-like technologies are a type economics, based on technical solutions and technologies copied and imitated from natural phenomena, adequate to natural processes, not disturbing the natural circulation of natural substances and applied in the process of social production.

The nature-based economy represents an integrated approach that combines environmental responsibility, technological development, and economic growth. It facilitates the transition to sustainable development models that conserve natural resources and improve the quality of life. [4]

The economy of nature-based technologies is inextricably linked with the global community's transition to a fundamentally new information-digital technological mode of production and consumption, the basis of which should be technologies for the renewability and recycling of economic resources.

Technologies [12] are a set of methods and tools for achieving a desired result. In a broad sense, they are the application of knowledge, skills, and abilities in solving practical problems. In a more organizationally specific sense, technologies include a sequence of actions, methods, and modes of operation. The concept of technology encompasses not only the technical side of the issue, but also economic, socio-philosophical, and ethical issues.

The term "nature-like technologies" means that they are aimed at minimizing or reducing to zero the anthropogenic impact on the environment.

At the same time, according to N. E. Tereshkina and O. A. Khalturina, Currently, there is no clear conceptual approach to interpreting the term "nature-like technologies." The main problem is that the proposed interpretations of the term "nature-like technologies" are based only on the description of specific technical and technological characteristics that reflect their specific features in the process of interaction with the natural environment [11].

The goal of creating nature-like technologies is to copy and, to the greatest possible extent, imitate technical solutions for natural processes so that technologies used in social production do not disrupt the natural circulation of natural substances.

The essence of nature-like technologies lies in the possibility of using them to recreate, within the framework of artificially created technical systems, "nature-like

” production processes that are as close as possible to similar processes that arose in the context of evolutionary development in real-life natural systems.

The primary distinguishing criterion for classifying technologies as nature-like should be the presence of technical systems in which the reproduction process is carried out in a manner similar to and analogous to that of living nature. In these systems, technological processes, integrated into natural resource circulation, restore the disturbed balance between the biosphere and the technosphere without harming the natural environment [8].

The criteria for classifying certain technologies as nature-like are:

- the ability to reproduce natural resources used in social production based on copying and imitation of natural processes;
- ensuring a fundamental reduction in the scale of destructive man-made impacts on the life cycles of the biosphere;
- the ability to simulate nature-like technological processes using both traditional and hybrid technologies, etc.

The specific characteristics of nature-like technologies aimed at minimizing the negative impact of social production on the environment based on the integration of technological processes into natural cycles are:

- ability to self-organize, adapt, and be cyclical;
- focus on minimizing the negative impact of social production on the natural environment based on the integration of technological processes into natural cycles;
- the ability to respond flexibly to changes occurring in external and internal conditions and factors in order to ensure the stability of technical systems;
- the ability of technical systems to integrate into the natural environment;
- the use of natural materials in nature-like technologies that have the ability to flexibly change their state under the influence of external and internal factors;
- the response of nature-like technologies to various changes occurring in the external and internal environment, carried out in real time, etc.

It’s important to keep in mind that changes in nature-like technologies occur as a result of the transformation of the key imperatives of technological processes, regardless of their content and forms of ownership. These very characteristics must be taken into account in the future development and implementation of models for the formation of governance systems for nature-like technologies.

The advantages and benefits of using nature-based technologies in the modern economy are manifested in:

the nature-destroying technologies used in the modern world in the process of producing goods consumed by humanity and their irreversible destructive impact on nature, including environmental pollution, depletion of natural resources, climate change, etc.;

- in the transformation of applied industrial and information-digital technologies into technologies that reproduce the processes of the natural circulation

of substances and at the same time ensure the stable development of ecological-economic systems;

— in expanding the use of technologies that use renewable natural resources, while minimizing their impact on the environment, etc.

A fundamental issue in developing a theory of the economics of nature-like technologies may be the question of the essence and criteria of its effectiveness.

Today, the economic effectiveness of nature-based technologies is defined as their effectiveness in interacting with natural biological cycles. The key characteristics of effectiveness (efficiency) are:

— the degree of sustainability as the ability to ensure a balance between the need for resources and the possibility of their restoration based on the principles of recycling;

— the degree of self-regulation as an opportunity, based on production and natural cycles, to flexibly adapt to exogenous changes in the environment and optimize the use of resources; [3]

— the level of energy efficiency, which characterizes the low level of energy consumption as a consequence of the use of renewable energy sources and efficient methods of its conversion; [15]

— minimizing the impact on the environment — preserving biodiversity as a result of reducing emissions, reducing the hydrocarbon footprint and emissions of other pollutants, etc.; [1]

— cost-effectiveness, i.e., reduction of production and maintenance costs, while increasing the economic benefits from the implementation of nature-like technologies.

In accordance with the author's concept, the concept of the efficiency of the economy of nature-like technologies should be considered as the effectiveness of quantitative and qualitative changes in the process of introducing nature-like technologies into various spheres of economic activity.

The economic effectiveness criterion for nature-based technologies should represent a generalized view of the qualitative and quantitative changes resulting from the implementation of nature-based technologies. The selection of such a criterion should be based on the following principles:

— the comprehensiveness of taking into account the systemic and processual nature of the functioning of the economy of nature-like technologies;

— taking into account the specific functions and results of the economy of nature-like technologies [10].

This approach to the formation of evaluation results of the effectiveness of the economy of nature-like technologies will allow for its comprehensive integrated assessment taking into account:

— functional results — according to the degree of ensuring sustainability and balance in the development of the economy of nature-like technologies;

- economic results — cost-effectiveness, that is, reduction of costs for the production and maintenance of nature-like technologies;
- results of self-regulation — the degree of flexibility in adaptation to exogenous changes in the environment;
- results of energy efficiency — ensuring low levels of energy consumption;
- environmental results — minimizing the impact on the environment;
- production and economic results — reduction of costs for the production and maintenance of nature-like technologies.

The development and implementation of a concept for an economy based on nature-based technologies is one of the strategic directions for the development of the Russian Federation's domestic economy. Its development and implementation will significantly reduce the negative impact of many sectors of the national economy on the environment, thereby creating more favorable conditions for improving the standard of living and quality of life for the Russian population.

The concept of the economy of nature-like technologies must proceed from the basic position of the evolutionary adaptation of social production to the specifics and characteristics of the reproduction of the natural environment [14].

The implementation of the Decree of the President of the Russian Federation of November 2, 2023, No. 818 “On the Development of Nature-Like Technologies in the Russian Federation” **will serve to solve this important global socio-economic problem.** In accordance with the instructions of the President of the Russian Federation V. V. Putin contained in the Decree, a set of measures is being implemented in the country to form an economy of nature-like technologies and, in particular, to create hybrid technological processes and technological systems using natural components (additive technologies, biosensors, etc.); the development of bio-similar and combined structures and materials for nature-like technology; development of new nature-like energy technologies, including nature-like nuclear energy technologies; research in the field of synthetic biology, etc. In addition, their successful implementation will be significantly facilitated by the theoretical and methodological approaches proposed by the authors of the article for solving the problem of the formation and development of a nature-like technology economy in the country.

References

1. Sigmund G., Ogerstrand M., Brodin T., Diamond M. L., Erdelen W. R., Evers D. K., et al., *Expanding the use of chemicals to achieve biodiversity targets, Science*, 2022, 376 (6599), 1280

2. Kovalchuk M. V., Naraykin O. S., Yatsishina E. B. *Nature-like technologies: new opportunities and new challenges // Bulletin of the Russian Academy of Sciences*. 2019. Vol. 89. No. 5. Pp. 455–465. DOI: 10.31857/S0869-5873895455-465 EDN: FRDGCY.

3. *Metaphysics of nature-like technologies. / B. M. Popov. – Voronezh: Kvarta*, 2019. – 60 p.

4. Polyakov V. V. *Nature-like technologies as an innovative response to the challenges of the 21st century // Economy and ecology of territorial entities*. 2024. No. 3. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/prirodopodobnye-tehnologii-kak-innovatsionnyy-otvet-na-vyzovy-xxi-veka> (date of access: 06.12.2025).

5. *Nature — based technologies in Russia: plans, prospects, opinions. https://glayportal.com/materials/prirodopodobnye-tehnologii-v-rossii-plany-perspektivy-mneniya*. Accessed December 3, 2025.

6. *Nature-like technologies: new opportunities and new threats// Kovalchuk M. V., Naraykin O. S. Security Index*. 2017. Vol. 22. P. 103.

7. *Putin called for technological cooperation to reduce the negative impact on the environment. https://tass.ru/obschestvo/6646393*. Accessed December 3, 2025.

8. Rednikova T. V. *On the issue of the legal concept and criteria of nature-like technologies // Legal research*. 2025. No. 6. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/k-voprosu-o-pravovom-ponyatii-i-kriteriyah-prirodopodobnyh-tehnologiy> (date of access: 06.12.2025).

9. Savina M. V., Solodukha P. V., Stepanova A. A. *On the transformation of the concept of political economy // Creative Economy. — 2024. — Vol. 18. — No. 6. — doi: 10.18334/ce.18.6.121059*.

10. Stepanov A. A., Savina M. V., Stepanov I. A. *Efficiency of digital transformation: essence, content, evaluation criteria // Economic systems*. 2022. No. 1. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/effektivnost-tsifrovoy-transformatsii-suschnost-soderzhanie-kriterii-otsenki> (date of access: 04.12.2025).

11. Tereshkina N. E., Khalturina O. A. *Development of nature-like technologies in the world // Bulletin of the Altai Academy of Economics and Law*. 2024. No. 4–3. P. 504–508. DOI: 10.17513/vaael.3454 EDN: EFNNBX.

12. *Technology: Definition, Types, and Applications in the Modern World. https://znanierrussia.ru/articles/Технология*. Accessed December 6, 2025.

13. *Decree of the President of the Russian Federation of November 2, 2023, No. 818. http://www.kremlin.ru/acts/bank/49919*. Accessed December 3, 2025.

14. Fomina, A.N. *A nature-based, life-activity approach to managing innovations in the television industry in the context of digital transformation.* <https://www.e-rej.ru/upload/iblock/d83/d83636ce21612940790e487fc0925487.pdf>. Accessed 03.12.2025

15. Shklyarsky Y. E., Gubarev M. A., Vorobyeva V. A., Kuznetsova Y. N. *Analysis of existing methods for assessing energy efficiency using the example of renewable energy sources// Bulletin of Tula State University. Technical sciences.* 2022. No. 4. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/analiz-suschestvuyuschih-metodik-otsenki-energoeffektivnosti-na-primere-vozobnovlyaemyh-istochnikov-energii> (date of access: 06.12.2025).

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THE ROLE OF NEURO-LINGUISTIC PROGRAMMING IN BUSINESS AND HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

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Abstract. *The study investigates the role of neuro-linguistic programming (NLP) in sustainable business development and human resource management. The aim of this research is to analyze the possibilities and limitations of using NLP in business and human resources management, as well as identify its potential for improving communication efficiency, employee motivation, and sustainable human capital formation within organizations. The results demonstrate that applying NLP techniques contributes to enhanced self-esteem, reduced professional stress, and increased employee motivation, which are essential for optimizing organizational processes. Additionally, opportunities for implementing NLP in areas such as leadership, goal setting, team management, and flexible thinking development are explored. These findings can be beneficial for managers interested in effective human capital management and researchers focused on issues related to business sustainability.*

Keywords: *neuro-linguistic programming (NLP), management, human resources, business.*

Introduction. Sustainable business is a multifaceted construct whose investigation requires an interdisciplinary approach. This approach is based on a holistic concept that integrates economic, sociocultural, and personnel characteristics into a unified system [1]. It differs from analyzing individual elements of business because it relies on the principle of emergence — the appearance of new qualities when parts come together as a whole.

Within this framework, particular attention is given to the problem of human capital as a key element of sustainable development. Human capital is considered in the context of sociocultural factors, including education, health, physical and mental condition, as well as changes in mindset and lifestyle.

One tool contributing to the development of human capital is neuro-linguistic programming (NLP). This approach focuses on how people organize their thoughts, feelings, and speech, making it relevant for studying in an organizational context. NLP offers numerous opportunities for enhancing human capital by emphasizing flexibility of thought and readiness for change. In contemporary science, NLP is seen as a tool for improving communication, managing stress, motivating employees, and fostering commitment to the organization [2].

This article not only describes the advantages of NLP but also identifies its limitations, which is important for understanding its role in developing human capital and ensuring business sustainability.

Results and discussion. In the concept of sustainable human capital development, neuro-linguistic programming (NLP) can be viewed as a significant factor associated with cognitive flexibility among individuals. NLP is a paradigm that analyzes individual perception of the world to enhance personal success. It encompasses relationships between communication, ways of thinking, and various techniques aimed at improving communication and changing behavior to achieve goals.

NLP significantly influences both business and human resource management, serving as a powerful tool for enhancing communication, cultivating leadership skills, and optimizing employee behavior within an organizational context. Its application in business helps manage objectives more effectively, accelerating company growth and increasing overall performance. Specifically, NLP facilitates deeper insights into employee motivation and behavior, enabling closer connections with clients, optimized marketing strategies, and improved sales productivity. Techniques derived from NLP foster positive thinking, crucial for achieving goals at both individual and organizational levels.

A primary aspect of NLP lies in its ability to explain cognitive processes influencing human perception and behavior. By identifying how individuals interpret the world through filters like values, beliefs, and memories, NLP enhances personal and professional effectiveness. Furthermore, NLP plays a vital role in conflict resolution, leadership enhancement, and employee motivation, leading to the creation of agile, creative, and autonomous teams.

From the perspective of sustainable human capital development, NLP becomes indispensable in helping individuals adapt to change and improve their capabilities. This improvement benefits not only personal attributes but also interactions with colleagues and superiors, fostering skills critical for achieving organizational goals. NLP stimulates the development of cognitive flexibility necessary for overcoming challenges in rapidly evolving business environments.

It should be noted that NLP thoroughly examines visual, auditory, and kinesthetic representation systems, tracing transformations from surface-level linguistic structures to deep-rooted ones. This comprehensive paradigm clarifies complex

cognitive processes through which the brain interprets events, shaping emotions and behaviors via filters such as values, beliefs, memories, decisions, and meta-programs. As a potent catalyst for excellence and success, NLP empowers individuals and organizations to realize their aspirations by nurturing flexibility, creativity, and autonomy. In educational contexts, practitioners skillfully employ NLP techniques to resolve conflicts, enhance leadership abilities, and inspire staff toward achieving organizational objectives. NLP serves as a foundational element for continuous learning, skill development, and cultivation of dynamic competencies in professional settings.

NLP is a universal professional instrument applicable across diverse domains — personal development, therapeutic interventions, and varied organizational landscapes. It plays a pivotal role in enhancing communication efficacy, facilitating conflict resolution, and propelling individual and collective achievements to new heights [3]. Implementing NLP demands balanced consideration of its potential benefits alongside empirical validation and ethical considerations.

Specifically addressing business and human resource management, NLP’s applicability spans all organizational levels. Its techniques impact leaders, managers at every level, salespeople, customer service representatives, administrators, engineers, coaches, HR professionals, and consultants alike [4].

Business growth facilitated by NLP is achievable through appropriate methods and recognition of its immense potential. Utilization of NLP in sales, marketing, and general business communication substantially boosts business efficiency. NLP enables individuals and companies to adopt a developmental mindset, resulting in accelerated business expansion.

Key NLP techniques employed for efficient business building and personnel management are outlined in Table 1 below.

Table 1 — NLP techniques used in business building and personnel management [5]

Technique	Characteristics
Anchoring	Process of linking internal reactions to external triggers to quickly elicit these responses.
Anchors	Can occur naturally or deliberately created. They control both positive and negative states.
Stacking anchors	Linking multiple events to one anchor to intensify subject’s response.
Breaking anchors	Neutralizing negative states by simultaneously activating two incompatible reactions.
Chaining anchors	Creating a sequence of anchors leading from undesirable state to desired state.

Technique	Characteristics
Associated state	Fully experiencing a state to feel its kinesthetics. Past experiences involve reliving them firsthand.
Dissociated state	Recreating past experience from an observer's point of view without original emotion.
Double dissociation	Observing yourself watching a movie about your past experience. Useful for phobias and severe psychological trauma.
Calibration	Reading internal reactions during interaction by correlating observable behavioral signals.
Reframing history	Re-experiencing past situations selectively anchored with resourceful states to alter significance of past events.
Rapport	Understanding interconnection between thoughts and emotions, creating healthier habits for mind and body.
Reframe	Separating problematic behavior from positive intention and responsible inner part. New patterns maintain positive intent without side effects.
Strategy	Explicit set of mental and behavioral steps used to achieve specific outcomes. Sequence of representational systems.
Submodalities	Subclassification of sensory experiences. Breakdown into components of images, sounds, or sensations.

These techniques provide valuable tools for businesses seeking to optimize communication, develop leadership, and maximize employee potential. By integrating NLP practices, organizations can cultivate resilient, adaptive, and high-performance workforces capable of navigating today's fast-paced and competitive environment.

There are several dimensions where neuro-linguistic programming (NLP) finds practical applications in business settings:

Application of NLP techniques supports the following skills development:

1. Self-Management Skills:

- Demonstrate organizational skills, act instead of procrastinating.
- Showcase a positive attitude and self-motivation.
- Express confidence and control over oneself and emotions.
- Manage stress levels efficiently, becoming lighter and enjoying life more.

2. Effective Communication Skills:

- Understand others' perspectives and communicate accordingly.
- Display assertive behavior, knowing boundaries while being firm yet fair.
- Communicate clearly and effectively.

3. Interpersonal Skills:

- Exhibit confidence and effectiveness in negotiations, sales, and influence.
- Collaborate well with others.
- Resolve disagreements and handle conflicts adeptly.

4. Emotional Intelligence:

- Empathize with others’ points of view.
- Regulate emotional states of self and others.
- Properly express emotions.

5. Leadership & Management Skills:

- Coach appropriately, shifting styles from «teaching» to «questioning and supporting. »
- Delegate responsibilities clearly to minimize risks.
- Effectively manage change and transitions.
- Solve problems by getting to the root cause.
- Set clear, measurable goals and outcomes.

6. Meta-Skills:

- Continually increase productivity through advanced modeling techniques.
- Demonstrate flexible thinking, balancing details with broader perspectives.
- Consider long-term consequences of actions and decisions [6].

Inside companies, NLP techniques support organizational development in several ways (Table 2).

Table 2 — Organizational Development Through Application of NLP Techniques [7]

Method	Characteristics
Leadership & HR	From defining strategic direction to aligning behaviors with organizational goals, NLP models help ensure business activities reflect organizational aims, providing a foundation for effective performance management and positively influencing group and individual motivation.
Mission	Using language universally appealing encourages stakeholders to actively contribute towards collective well-being. Language models used by NLP specialists consider conscious and sub-conscious impacts of words and phrases.
Information Materials	NLP aids in identifying sources of misunderstanding and suggests preventative measures. Attention to subtle nonverbal and verbal cues can determine clarity versus confusion, transparency versus opacity.
Decision Making	During turbulent times, decision-making capability is a core leadership skill. Learning more about personal decision mechanisms, such as what we know and emphasize when deciding rationally, can overcome inertia and build confidence in uncertain conditions. Awareness of systemic ecology promotes accountability and informed judgment.

Method	Characteristics
Motivation & Team Dynamics	Understanding true motivators beyond formal exercises reveals value-driven approaches to encouraging collaborative efforts towards shared goals. Connecting with individual core values may allow full dedication to tasks.
Mediation	Addressing barriers to mutual understanding involves finding common ground. Gestalt-based methods reveal higher intentions behind less functional behaviors and uncover belief structures to resolve conflicts.
Presence & Personal Impact	Powerful state-management approaches facilitate genuine conversations in leadership, coaching, presentations, negotiations, facilitation, etc., fostering authentic engagement. Perceived status either enhances or hinders connection-building and involvement.
Stress & Anxiety Management	Recognizing the link between thoughts and emotions and devising methods to modify ineffective behavioral patterns improves resilience. Establishing healthy habits for mind and body ensures better coping in challenging circumstances.
Active & Progressive Insight	While the above list covers problem-solving areas, proactive understanding leads to advancements even when conditions aren't optimal.

Neuro-linguistic programming (NLP) has become increasingly prominent in recruitment processes. One of the main goals of any hiring process is predicting job performance accurately. Assessing candidates' personalities during selection is one of the most effective strategies, utilized by over 80% of successful organizations.

Properly conducted hiring and selection processes eliminate wasted time interviewing unsuitable candidates. Human Resources managers gain quick access to precise information regarding each candidate's critical aspects. Consequently, there is a greater likelihood of hiring suitable candidates who fit the position and organizational culture, thereby enhancing workplace efficiency and reducing turnover rates.

Let's explore the role of NLP in recruitment practice (Table 3):

Table 3 — Role of NLP in Recruitment. [8]

Direction	Characteristics
Enhancing Communication Skills	Mirror body language and ask metamodel questions to understand candidates deeply.
Interpret Verbal/Non-Verbal Signals	Track eye movement patterns, sensory, and linguistic cues to assess honesty and communication style.
Use Anchoring Methods in Interviews	Employ consistent positive gestures or phrases to create comfort and open dialogue.

Direction	Characteristics
Craft Effective Job Advertisements	Leverage persuasive language templates and result-oriented descriptions to attract motivated applicants.
Evaluate Culture Fit	Pose probing questions to select candidates aligned with organizational values.
Improve Candidacy Assessment Strategy	Ensure objective and bias-free decision-making in selecting candidates.

Thus, neuro-linguistic programming (NLP) is an integral component of a successful business built upon effective interaction both internally with employees and externally with customers and users.

Conclusions. Neuro-linguistic programming (NLP) has attracted considerable interest from researchers and practitioners for over three decades due to its innovative approaches to interaction, motivation, and management. It aims to enhance cognitive and communicative skills, promoting both personal and professional development.

NLP represents a promising tool in the realm of management, business, and human resource development. Its implementation enables leaders to improve communication, deepen insight into employee motivation, and align individual goals with organizational objectives. NLP creates an environment where employees feel engaged and motivated, actively participating in achieving a shared vision. Techniques such as modeling successful behavior, employing language patterns, and establishing rapport can significantly enhance team effectiveness.

Integrating NLP into management is particularly important in the face of a dynamic business landscape. Its principles assist organizations in adapting to change, solving emerging problems, and formulating clear, attainable goals. Such approaches ensure sustainable business development, making organizations more flexible, involved, and competitive [9].

However, despite its benefits, certain limitations must be acknowledged. A major limitation is the insufficient development of mechanisms for transferring tacit knowledge within organizations. NLP primarily focuses on individual cognitive processes, posing challenges for strengthening collective learning and sharing experiences. Effective utilization of NLP under these conditions necessitates a strategic approach, encompassing additional organizational measures such as engaging professional trainers, stimulating interpersonal interactions, and creating platforms for knowledge exchange among employees.

Despite existing constraints, NLP holds substantial potential for elevating managerial quality. It assists employees in developing skills and confidence, benefitting both professionally and personally.

Thus, neuro-linguistic programming can serve as an effective tool in advancing human capital and enhancing managerial effectiveness if its usage is supported by deliberate strategy and adaptation to organizational needs.

List of sources

Vorobyev, A. A. *Formation of conceptual model of sustainable enterprise development: strategy and prospects for development* / A. A. Vorobyev // *Strategic Decisions and Risk Management*. — 2022. — Vol. 13, no. 3. — pp. 226–233. — DOI 10.17747/2618-947X-2022-3-226-233. — EDN VVNIFA.

Razan, Mhanna *Mastering. minds: Unleashing the power of Neuro-linguistic programming in workplaces and schools* / Razan Mhanna, Hiba Abdo, Diana Ghanem, Mouna Chehabeddine, Georges Hatem // *Forum for Education Studie*. — 2024. — № 2 (1). — P. 378–390.

Lyubimov, A. *Brief Overview of NLP [Electronic Resource]* // Access mode: URL: http://www.syntone-spb.ru/library/news/?item_id=117 (accessed May 31, 2025).

Miroslav, Frankovský. *Implementing the Concept of Neurolinguistic Programming Related to Sustainable Human Capital Development* / Miroslav Frankovský, Zuzana Birknerová, Róbert Štefko, Eva Benková // *Sustainability*. — 2019. — № 11(15). — P. 436–442.

Mona, Mostafa. *El-Ashry the Importance of Neuro Linguistic Programming Skill as a Communication Tool in the Workplace* // *Journal of global science research*. — 2022. — № 6 (1). — P. 1108–1123.

Ileana, Georgiana Gheorghie. *Application of NLP Principles and Methods in the Personnel Recruitment and Selection Process* // *Economic Insights — Trends and Challenges*. — 2023. — № 1. — P. 159–166.

Yasuhiro, Kotera. *Organisational applications of neuro-linguistic programming: A systematic review* / Yasuhiro Kotera, William Van Gordon, David Sheffield // *ResearchGate*. — URL: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/328973451_Organisational_applications_of_neuro-linguistic_programming_A_systematic_review (дата обращения 29.11.2025)

Lim, Joey Can. *Neuro-linguistic programming (NLP) be used as contemporary and effective skill for an exceptional manager in an organization?* / Lim Joy, Rashad Yazdanifard // *International Journal of Management, Accounting and Economics* — 2021. — № 2. — P. 456–465.

Applied Aspects of Artificial Intelligence and Neural Network Technologies / A. N. Aleksakhin, M. A. Alymenko, A. Yu. Anisimov et al. — Moscow: Limited Liability Company «Rusajns», 2024. — 176 p. — ISBN 978-5-466-07072-9. — EDN DJPAKM.

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